

Ideate to Advocate: Exploring Creativity in the Statutory Advocacy Sector

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Abstract

The Statutory Advocacy (SA) sector in the UK plays a crucial role in supporting individuals to have their voices heard when in some challenging situations, including agreeing to health and social care needs. Despite its importance, the SA sector faces significant challenges due to financial constraints and increasing referral complexities. This study explores how creativity can enhance the operational efficiency and service delivery within this sector by being used as the fuel of innovation.

Employing a multiple case study methodology, this research examines the application of creative ideation and social innovation in SA organisations. The study aims to identify how these organisations encourage and support creativity, the types of organisational support required, and how resources are allocated to foster innovative practices.

Key findings reveal that a culture of creativity, combined with supportive practices, is essential for driving innovation within SA providers. The development of the Shepherd Ideation Model highlights the importance of Creative Unlocking and Idea Landing, which is vital to the ideation stage of social innovation.

This research contributes to the existing literature by bridging the gap between policy, practice, and theory in the statutory advocacy sector. It provides actionable recommendations for SA providers to enhance their creative capacities and improve service outcomes, ultimately advocating for a more innovative and responsive approach to statutory advocacy.

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Table 1 - Definition of Terms

In Text	Definition	Detail
Advocate		A trained independent person, that delivers services under legislation (DoLS).
Commissioner		A government employee that procures health and care services on behalf of their authority.
Commissioning		The process by which health and care services are planned, purchased, and monitored by relevant bodies.
DoLS	Deprivation of Liberty Safeguards	An amendment to Mental Capacity Act 2005, introduced in 2009. A procedure prescribed in law when it is necessary to deprive of their liberty a resident or patient who lacks capacity to consent to their care and treatment to keep them safe from harm.
IMCA	Independent Mental Capacity Advocates	Specially trained independent people who can support certain people under the Mental Capacity Act 2005.
IMHA	Independent Mental Health Advocates	Specially trained independent people who can support certain patients under the Mental Health Act 1983.
LPS	The Liberty Protection Safeguards	Introduced in the Mental Capacity (Amendment) Act 2019 and replaces the DoLS. Aims to deliver improved outcomes for people who are or who need to be deprived of their liberty. Target launch 2022.
MCA 2005	Mental Capacity Act 2005	Legislation designed to protect and empower people who may lack the mental capacity to make their own decisions.
MHA 1983	Mental Health Act 1983	Legislation designed to cover the reception, care and treatment of mentally disordered people including management of their property.

NESTA		The United Kingdom's Innovation agency for social good. A Charity that is funded by an endowment from UK National Lottery.
NFP	Not For Profits	Organisations that can make a profit and then reinvest the money back into the company.
Provider		An organisation that delivers statutory advocacy services.
SA	Statutory Advocacy	A legal entitlement to an independent person to help support.
SCIE	Social Care Institute for Excellence	Commercial organisation that focuses on co-producing, sharing, and supporting best available knowledge in social care sector.
SI	Social Innovation	innovative activities and services that are motivated by the goal of meeting a social need and that are predominantly developed and diffused through organisations whose primary purposes are social
TCA 2014	The Care Act 2014	Legislation that helps to improve people's independence and wellbeing by making local authorities to provide services aimed at preventing people developing needs for care and support or delaying people deteriorating such that they would need ongoing care and support.
The Young Foundation		A not-for-profit research organisation, working with communities, organisations and policymakers.

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Chapter 1: INTRODUCTION

Statutory Advocacy (SA) empowers individuals by supporting them in voicing their concerns and ensuring they are heard, particularly regarding their health and social care needs (Scottish Independent Advocacy Alliance). As an essential component of the social services sector, SA is facing significant challenges in providing crucial public services amidst an increasingly difficult environment.

Core funding from local authorities is under considerable strain, with one in five councils at risk of bankruptcy (Vaccari and Marique, 2024) and a 58% reduction in promised central government funding for adult social care (National Audit Office, 2023). This financial strain is exacerbated by the increasing complexity of referrals, which demand more resources (Smith, 2023), with SA providers at the forefront of managing increasing demand with reduced funding.

Innovation offers SA providers a well-established approach to develop services, optimise operations, and enhance business models to improve efficiency (Anderson et al., 2014, Bates, 2012). It allows organisations to increase their capabilities (Fagerberg et al., 2010), through the application of creativity to problems (Gilson and Litchfield, 2017), developing ideas which can lead to innovative outcomes (Van Dijk and Van Den Ende, 2002).

The challenges within the sector are expected to persist in the near future, underscoring the importance of showcasing the current creative responses within the sector. Doing so provides valuable learning opportunities for other providers and broader social work organisations. This research employs a multiple case study methodology to explore the application of creativity, ideas, and innovation within the UK SA sector.

1.1.1 Social Care Sector Overview

The social care sector is a crucial aspect of the foundational economy, providing support services for over 1 million users in 2019 (Fund, 2019). It covers a wide range of areas from mental health to elderly care and is identified as one of the 5 elements that make up the foundational economy (Bentham et al., 2013). This economy is characterised by markets that are isolated from significant competition, a balanced demand distribution and services that support everyday life, rather than high-tech or research-intensive industries (Heslop et al., 2019). This study aims to explore the significance of the social care sector and investigate its potential for innovation, considering the unique characteristics of this foundational economy.

Traditionally, social care has been provided by local authorities, but in recent decades there has been a shift towards a combination of for-profit (FP) and not-for-profit (NFP) providers (Fund, 2019). The Care Quality Commission (CQC) acts as the sector's ombudsman on behalf of the government (Commission, 2022). This creates a marketplace where public, private, and third sector organisations operate (Zappalà, 2001). In the third sector, organisations operate independently of government control, but may offer services that replace or complement state offerings, with a socially desirable outcome as their core (Lubienski and Perry, 2019).

Governments have increasingly outsourced their social responsibilities, leading to a shift from consolidated state delivery. This is driven by changing macro factors, with governments focusing on core activities and outsourced non-core activities (Salamon and Anheier, 1996). This policy is based on a neoliberal ideology, which emphasizes economic maximization and effectiveness, with the belief that competition and market forces will help solve societal problems (Henig et al., 2003).

The social care sector has been facing mounting pressure over the last decade, as it contends with a range of challenges. These include an ageing population, social isolation, a reduction in central government funding, changes to government policy, and most recently, the added impact of the COVID-19 pandemic. The sector requires heterogeneity to provide personalised approaches that meet the individual needs of its clients. However, this can create challenges in terms of service quality control (Zolkiewski, 2004), as service outcomes are dependent on customer engagement. Without engagement there is an increased chance of failure in the service (Bitner et al., 1997).

In the UK, New Public Management (NPM) has significantly transformed the public sector since the 1980s (Hood, 1991). Major reforms included the privatisation of state enterprises such as British Telecom, the introduction of internal markets within the NHS (Ferlie, 1996), and the expansion of managerial autonomy in local authorities moving away from centralised decision making (Whyman, 2006). There was a widespread adoption of performance measurement systems and public-private partnerships (PPPs) within the health care sector, aimed at enhancing efficiency and service quality (Dawson and Dargie, 2005). Public Choice Theory regarded citizens as rational customers, with the individual freedoms to choose their public services (Simonet, 2015).

Although these changes led to cost savings and increased efficiency, they were also critiqued for potentially reducing the equity and accessibility of services, especially for vulnerable groups, due to the oligopoly in the marketplace (Whyman, 2006). Competition was introduced to raise the utility level provided by social care providers, incentivising greater efficiency and effectiveness (McMaster, 2004). This public policy was founded on the goals of promoting growth and economic maximisation within the sector (Renouard, 2011). Furthermore, to foster the development of social capital and enhance utility, innovation was explicitly promoted as a crucial strategy (Chew and Lyon, 2012).

One consistent approach is to be implemented in all areas of social care, with the aim of integrating concepts such as Social Return on Investment (SROI) and Social Capital into the language and practices of third sector organisations (Providers). SROI was a little used measurement (Arvidson et al., 2013) until it was adopted by the UK government as a mechanism to define the impact of actions on socio-economic policy indicators and assigning them a monetary value (Hall and Millo, 2018). This was supported by the development of social capital, which was identified by Putnam (Helliwell and Putnam, 1995) as a community-level resource that encompasses all the norms, networks, and social trust that foster cooperation in society (Baum and Ziersch, 2003). Increasing social capital became a key policy focus (Lyons et al., 2012), reflected in changes to government approaches (Fyfe and Milligan, 2003b). Moreover, effectiveness became a key measure for providers, which, as an emergent property or a social constructivist approach, can be challenging to calculate (Balsler and McClusky, 2005).

The UK government has incorporated aspects of neo-communitarianism ideology into its social care policies, which emphasizes the importance of supporting economic development with social cohesion (Fyfe, 2005) and increasing social capital (Siisiainen, 2003) when working with third sector organisations. The idea of a third way, which combines elements of both the private and public sectors, was introduced by the Labour government in 1997, moving away from the traditional binary choices of big market/small state or small market/big state (Fyfe and Milligan, 2003b). Given the limited resources for health and social care in the UK, adopting utilitarian ethics provides a responsible approach to finances at a macro level (Morrell, 2006).

The social care sector in the UK has been divided into two approaches - a grassroots voluntary organisation or a more professionalised corporatist organisation (Knight, 1993,

Bryson et al., 2002, Milligan, 1998). The grassroots approach is usually associated with a charity ideology, with a cause at the heart of their mission. These organisations tend to have a more local vision and rely on volunteers (Milligan, 1998). They focus on a community-first approach, prioritising the creation of social capital over professionalisation (Taylor, 2015).

The social care providers have been pushed towards a more private sector approach, where they are expected to identify their strategic position and develop positioning strategies for their products and services (Bennett, 2008, Bennett and Savani, 2011, Chew and Osborne, 2007b). This policy has resulted in the sector operating in a unique way, with a combination of paid workers and volunteers completing tasks (Hwang and Powell, 2009), which is not seen in either the private or public sector. This shift has led to the development of a hybrid organisational form (Brudney and Meijs, 2009) where the traditional boundaries between the private, public, and third sector are becoming increasingly blurred.

Over the past 20 years, the social care sector has increasingly adopted private sector approaches, including a focus on growing social capital and delivering a positive return on government spending. One area of focus has been innovation, which can lead to increased efficiency and effectiveness. However, this has added complexity for providers who are still adjusting to a more professional and strategic approach.

The field of statutory advocacy is not well-known; thus it is essential to establish the context from which the case studies will be selected.

1.1.2 Defining Statutory Advocacy

Advocacy can be defined as a mechanism to “*support individuals to express and have their views heard. It aims to redress any imbalance of power between the individual and professional. It is concerned with empowerment, autonomy and self-determination, the safeguarding of citizenship rights and the inclusion of otherwise marginalised people*”(Eames, 2007, p. 2). Advocacy can be divided into statutory and non-statutory categories, which are delivered by different groups. Statutory advocacy is highly regulated and governed by legislation implemented by representatives of central government, while non-statutory advocacy is usually a more informal, community-based approach.

Each country has adopted its own legislation and responded to the duty of care in different ways, the tables below set out the current legislation that is applicable to each area.

Table 2 English Advocacy Legislation

Type	Legislation	Detail	Responsible
Care Act Advocacy	Care Act 2014	Facing needs assessment, care planning or review under The Care Act Assessed having ‘Substantial difficulty’ when trying to be involved; Have no appropriate family or friends to consult	Local Authorities
IMHA	Mental Health Act 1983	You are sectioned under the Mental Health Act On a Community Treatment Order (CTO) Under Guardianship Order A conditionally discharged restricted patient	
IMCA	Mental Capacity Act 2005	Facing decisions about change of accommodation, serious medical treatment, safeguarding or Care review and: Have been assessed as lacking capacity to make these decisions, and Have no appropriate family or friends to consult	
RPR	Mental Capacity (Amendment) Act 2019	When a DoLS authorisation is granted a referral for a professional RPR should be made if there is no one suitable or available to undertake the RPR role. The RPR will visit the person regularly, ensure that the DoLS continues to be appropriate and the relevant criteria and any conditions attached to the DoLS continue to be met.	
NHS Complaints	Independent NHS Health Complaints Advocacy	make a complaint about any care you have received from a service run by the NHS,	

Table 3 Welsh Advocacy Legislation

Type	Legislation	What	Responsible
Care Act Advocacy	Care Act 2014 S35	Facing needs assessment, care planning or review under The Care Act Assessed having ‘Substantial difficulty’ when trying to be involved; Have no appropriate family or friends to consult	Health Boards
IMHA	Mental Health Act 1983 S130E	You are sectioned under the Mental Health Act On a Community Treatment Order (CTO) Under Guardianship Order A conditionally discharged restricted patient	
IMCA	Mental Capacity Act 2005	Facing decisions about change of accommodation, serious medical treatment, safeguarding or Care review and: Have been assessed as lacking capacity to make these decisions, and Have no appropriate family or friends to consult	
RPR	Mental Capacity (Amendment) Act 2019	When a DoLS authorisation is granted a referral for a professional RPR should be made if there is no one suitable or available to undertake the RPR role. The RPR will visit the person regularly, ensure that the DoLS continues to be appropriate, and the relevant criteria and any conditions attached to the DoLS continue to be met.	

Table 4 Scottish Advocacy Legislation

Type	Legislation	What	Responsible
Independent Advocacy	Mental Health (Care and Treatment) (Scotland) Act 2003	People with “mental disorders”. This means people with mental illness or a mental health condition. People with learning disabilities, autism and/or dementia.	Health Boards and Local Authorities

Table 5 Northern Irish Advocacy Legislation

Type	Legislation	What	Responsible
Advocacy	Human Rights Act 1998	The Human Rights Act 1998 (which made the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR) enforceable in Northern Ireland courts)	Local Authorities
	Northern Ireland Act 1998	Public authorities to have due regard for the need to promote equality of opportunity between persons of different religious belief, political opinion, racial group, age, marital status or sexual orientation.	
	Chronically Sick and Disabled Persons Act 1978	Gives rights to disabled people in relation to practical assistance in the home, provision of meals and participating in services - including through advocacy	Department of Health and Social Services for Northern Ireland
	Disabled Persons (Northern Ireland) Act 1989.	Allows for authorised representative to act on behalf of the disabled person.	

An example of how advocacy can be used to support those that lack a voice, the Deprivation of Liberty Safeguards (DoLS) is a legal protection under the Mental Capacity Act 2005 (MCA 2005) for individuals who lack capacity and are deprived of their liberty. To ensure their best interests are safeguarded, an advocate is appointed, who must be qualified to Independent Mental Capacity Advocate (IMCA) level (Dixon et al., 2020, Dawson, 2015). A set of questions called the 'acid test' has been developed to determine when DoLS applies (Court, 2016).

The acid test questions are.

1. Does the person lack capacity to consent to the arrangements?
2. Is the person subject to continuous supervision and control?
3. Is the person free to leave?

If individuals lack capacity, are subject to continuous supervision or control and they are not free to leave then this would be classified as a deprivation of liberty. In this case then an advocate would be assigned to the case under the statutory duty.

1.2 Statutory Advocacy Sector Overview

In response to the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (UNCPRD), the UK government introduced the Care Act in 2014, which brought a duty of care to local authorities (Government, 2014, Newbigging et al., 2021). This act introduced a statutory duty for governmental organisations to provide independent advocacy if required when decisions are being made about social and health care for citizens (Richardson, 2012). For individuals with complex needs, this may involve the use of an independent advocate who acts in their interests (Dawson, 2015, Dixon et al., 2020).

1.2.1 Delivering Statutory Advocacy

Statutory Advocacy is a crucial element of the social care sector, as it supports vulnerable individuals who may be deprived of their liberty. Local authorities are responsible for delivering these services, which have become increasingly challenging due to rising demand and financial pressures. To address these challenges, local authorities have adopted outsourcing that prioritize efficiency and effectiveness (Newbigging et al., 2021, Janssen et al., 2017).

Over the last few decades, there has been a change in the role of charities, driven by governmental policies and outsourcing of social duties (Salamon and Anheier, 1996). This

has led to a greater dependence on public sector funding for charities instead of private donors (Parry et al., 2005). These changes follow a neoliberalist ideology, which expects the state to adopt an economic maximisation process focused on effectiveness, with the belief that competition and market forces will benefit society (Henig et al., 2003).

The ideology behind the current approach for statutory advocacy services is based on a rationally led, economics-based agenda approach, with the belief that charities exist to solve market or governmental failures (Dart, 2004, Liu, 2017). Local authority commissioners put out tenders covering all the requirements of the Deprivation of Liberty Safeguards (DoLS) for their area and independent organisations are responsible for delivering the services. This has resulted in a crowded marketplace, with competition from for-profit organisations, leading to a move away from informal volunteer-based non-profit organisations (Providers) to a mixture of paid and voluntary professionals (Fund, 2019, Newbigging et al., 2021). However, this has also brought challenges such as uncertain government funding and competing economic and social pressures (Akingbola, 2013, Bessant and Maher, 2009). The focus is on fulfilling customer needs and cost efficiency rather than growth opportunities (Minna et al., 2014).

The social care sector has seen competition between organisations that chase the same funding sources, leading to a shift toward hybrid organizational models combining processes from both the third, public, and private sectors to deliver services more effectively (Evers, 2005, Cabinet Office, 2006). However, this neoliberal approach has been criticized for not providing the comprehensive answers that were expected of the ideology (Davies, 2012) and for expecting rational consumer behaviour when users with literacy issues or mental health conditions may be excluded (Valentine et al., 2017). For-profit providers may cherry-pick contracts, ignoring those unlikely to lead to at least full cost recovery (Henderson et al., 2019). Moreover, service users are integral to successful outcomes, and without engagement, failure is likely (Bitner et al., 1997), which is complicated by mental health issues and challenges to rational decision-making.

It is important to note that while providers may operate in a neoliberal marketplace, they may not adopt this philosophy as their organizational approach. Instead, the focus is often on maximum impact from resources, which could be classified as adopting a utilitarian approach, while delivering deontological services and operating in a neoliberal marketplace. For-profit providers, aim to maximize their organizational returns, leading to challenges in

providing personalized approaches to meet individual needs. The SA sector requires a heterogeneous delivery to be effective, but waiting lists for some services are growing, making it difficult for organisations to recruit, train, and retain IMCA's or IMHA's. In recognition of the legislative burden created by DoLS, the government has decided to simplify the law with the Liberty Protection Safeguards, targeted to launch on April 1, 2022, although this has been delayed numerous times already and is still in the pipeline. However, there is no clear national picture of demand for advocacy, and there are inconsistencies in delivery across England, with some authorities only instructing a few IMCAs, while others have over 100 ongoing cases (Mercer, 2019).

To summarize, the social advocacy (SA) sector, which provides support for vulnerable individuals who lack capacity to make decisions, has received little attention in academic literature. However, it plays a crucial role in delivering governmental services to this group. This thesis will focus on providers that operate in the SA sector and will examine their approach to promoting and supporting creativity in organizational innovation. By creating case studies of these organisations, the thesis aims to increase awareness of this sector and its importance.

1.3 Social Innovation

Social innovation refers to the development and implementation of new solutions to address social challenges, often involving novel ideas, practices, or partnerships (Chew and Lyon, 2012). These innovations are not just limited to products or services but include new ways of organizing, new interactions, and new forms of collaboration, often transcending traditional boundaries between public, private, and nonprofit sectors (Adams and Hess, 2010).

The core aim of social innovation is to create positive social change, improving the well-being and quality of life of individuals and communities (Murray et al., 2010). It has been designed to support initiatives that would like to tackle challenges including poverty, health, environmental sustainability and community development. Successful social innovations are sustainable and scalable, meaning they can grow and be replicated to benefit a broader audience beyond their initial context.

For instance, in the UK, social innovations in social work, such as integrated care systems, demonstrate significant impacts on community well-being. These systems coordinate services across healthcare, social services, and community organizations to provide holistic support to

individuals, especially the elderly and those with complex needs (Hughes, 2019). This approach not only enhances access to necessary services but also streamlines care delivery, reducing redundancies and improving efficiency. By focusing on collaborative practices that align various sectors, these innovations reflect how strategic, community-focused solutions can significantly improve social care outcomes and foster a more interconnected approach to welfare and support in the UK (Chalmers, 2013).

1.3.1 Statutory Advocacy Innovation

The current approach to procuring statutory advocacy services is characterized by a top-down model, where the future direction is determined by commissioners. However, this model has limitations in terms of promoting innovation within the sector. This is partly due to the prescriptive nature of key performance indicators (KPIs) that focus on reactive solutions, rather than proactive ones. Additionally, the risks involved in deprivation of liberty and other life-changing types of care can discourage providers from taking risks and making significant changes. Therefore, there is a need to explore alternative approaches that promote innovation while ensuring the safety and well-being of service users.

Innovation tends to come from new entrants to the marketplace (Kirkman, 2012), top-down tender-driven change (Newbigging et al., 2017), or imitative organizational innovation (Kattel et al., 2013). This suggests that the current procurement process may not be fostering a culture of innovation and may be limiting the ability of established providers to drive change. The lack of response in the statutory advocacy sector may be influenced by various factors, such as the dual role of providers (Svensson and Mahoney, 2020), where they must balance their altruistic values and a focus on social innovation rather than profit (Mulgan et al., 2007). In contrast, for-profit organisations tend to prioritize creating a competitive advantage (Kankanhalli et al., 2017) to maximize their profits, which may result in delivering the minimum social impacts (Mulgan et al., 2007).

According to Tidd and Bessant (2020), new organisations are often more innovative due to their lack of institutional inertia and greater willingness to take risks. They are unencumbered by established processes or structures, leading to increased strategic agility and ability to respond to change. This concept aligns with the idea that innovation can be treated as an R&D process in public sector management reforms (Kattel et al., 2023).

The process of procuring statutory advocacy services is often done using tenders. This approach can give the commissioner a lot of power, which can have consequences for how

change and innovation are driven within the sector. According to Newbigging et al. (2017), relying on tenders for innovation can result in a top-down approach, where change is driven by the tender process itself. This can be a challenge for smaller organisations with limited resources, as they may struggle to take risks or deviate from the tender brief. However, it is important to note that the procurement process is a complex one (Glasby, 2012), and it is not just a matter of one party having all the power.

In the statutory advocacy sector, both the top-down tender driven approach and the imitative approach can lead to a network of isomorphic organisations. While conforming to industry norms can confer legitimacy (Deegan, 2006), there are concerns that it can also create an "iron cage" that limits creativity and innovation (DiMaggio and Powell, 1983). Given the potential costs of failure in this sector, adopting this approach may be seen as a safe bet, leading to institutional memetic isomorphism (Tan et al., 2013) where organisations converge around similar templates (Greenwood and Suddaby, 2006). As a result, there may be a quasi-marketplace where organisations are competing using very similar approaches, as the risks associated with being different are too great.

The discrepancy in response to increased competition may place providers at risk, necessitating the need to boost their productivity through innovation (Chew and Lyon, 2012). This knowledge gap emphasizes the need to identify and establish an effective innovation model for providers in the sector (Pedersen, 2020), starting with ideas (Van Dijk and Van Den Ende, 2002)

1.3.2 Social Idea Generation

There are multiple social innovation models that can be used as the basis for research in the sector, which will be covered in-depth as part of the literature review. One key influential approach is The Process of Social Innovation (Murray et al., 2010), which calls the idea generation stage Proposals.

Figure 1 - Process of Social Innovation (Murray et al., 2010)

Ideation, the process of generating ideas, is a crucial element that is shared by all social innovation models, making it relevant to the Statutory Advocacy sector. As a creative act, ideation requires a specialized skillset and has been identified as a key driver of innovation (Dorta, 2008, Björk, 2012). While ideation is recognized as a part of the social innovation process, it is often treated as a mere checklist of activities rather than being examined in its contextual environment.

Given the focus of providers on creating ideas with social impact, ideation is crucial to the potential success of innovation in the sector. Despite this, there is a lack of literature that specifically addresses the process of idea generation in the SA sector and the wider third sector.

1.3.3 Social Creativity

Employee creativity is at the heart of idea generation, as it provides the resources for the development of practical ideas (Van Dijk and Van Den Ende, 2002). As an essential element of ideation, it is important that the research examines how providers foster and develop creativity in their organisations.

The use of ideas, whether new or old, in a creative way and applied to problems, has been identified as a key way to drive success for organisations (Hargadon and Sutton, 2000). Systematically developing a creative culture, is likely to lead to improved idea generation through concepts such as knowledge- brokering.

The Van Dijk and Ende (2002) creativity transformation model (Figure 2) highlights the factors that are useful to creating ideas from initial stages of creativity. This can be used as the basis for investigating creativity and idea generation within the organisations.

Figure 2 - Creativity Transformation Model adapted from Van Dijk and Van Den Ende (2002)

It is these two stages of idea creation and idea landing that will be used as the basis for the case study approach of the thesis. The research will focus on how ideas are encouraged by the provider, what organisational support is available for creativity and what committed resources are available.

1.4 Research Rationale

The statutory advocacy field in England has received limited academic attention compared to the broader health and social care sector (Boyle and Organization, 2011, Baxter et al., 2018, Smith and Wilkins, 2018). This presents an opportunity for research, particularly in examining the potential for providers in SA to operate in a more innovative way, to maximize their social return on investment. While previous research has examined clinicians' attitudes (Luke et al., 2008), sociological concepts (Flynn, 2010), spiritual rights (Morgan, 2017), and service use (Roberts et al., 2012, Dementia), there is a gap in the literature around the ideation process for SA providers. Previous research in this field has either focused on service users or examined the commissioning process, leaving a gap for research that combines policy, practice, and theory to drive systemic change.

While there is literature on providers funding (Casey, 2013, Bennett and Savani, 2011), social innovation (Chew and Lyon, 2012), and their role as a CSR link with for-profit organisations (Holmes and Smart, 2009), there is a lack of research on creativity management for

providers, especially in comparison to the wealth of research on private sector product development (Setnikar Cankar and Petkovsek, 2013). Furthermore, there is limited literature on the conceptual clarity, conceptual frameworks, and organizational capacity for providers to innovate (Osborne, 2013), and previous research has assumed innovative behaviour exists (Kendall, 2000) or reduced it to a generalized model based on a small sample size (Brooks et al., 2011).

As ideas are the fuel for the innovation process, ideation is a crucial stage in developing the SA sector (Amabile, 1998). By examining how creativity is fostered in the SA sector through a multiple case study approach, this research can identify potential areas for improvement for providers, potentially improving the success of the innovation process and optimizing the use of providers resources to produce the best results in the local sector (Goodin, 2021).

1.4.1 Research Aim

The research aim is “a critical examination of how providers in the Statutory Advocacy sector, currently encourage, support and resource creativity for organisational innovation.”

1.4.2 Research Objectives

1. Explore how encouragement can help organizations in statutory advocacy to create a culture of creativity and innovation and identify effective methods to encourage innovation and sustain it in these organisations.
2. Identify the types of support that organisations in the statutory advocacy need to be more creative and innovative.
3. Investigate how statutory advocacy providers use their resources to support creativity and find out what factors influence their decisions on innovative projects.

1.4.3 Research Questions

The research questions that will be explored through qualitative interviews are.

- I. How do SA providers invest their resources in support of creativity and innovation?
- II. What organisational support is needed for providers in SA sector to foster creativity and innovation?
- III. How do SA providers utilise a culture of creativity to drive innovation?

1.4.4 Contribution

This research aims to bridge the gap in existing literature that addresses either the commissioning process or the service user experience. Combining these two elements (idea generation and SA) will allow this piece of research to offer an insight into how providers currently undertake ideation in the statutory advocacy sector. The use of a multiple case study approach may allow for the development of idea generation context for the sector.

This approach will identify the similarities and differences in the idea generation approaches, which focuses on the wider sector development rather than individual organisations (Kattel et al., 2013). This may help organisations meet the twin needs of contract fulfilment and social change. The model will build on the NESTA Social Innovation framework (Murray et al., 2010), developing a focus around the creativity in organisations and highlight how ideas are created then delivered by providers, thereby provide an original contribution to knowledge.

1.4.5 Conclusion

This chapter has outlined the statutory advocacy sector and highlighted the significant challenges it encounters. It has stressed the need for research focused on exploring how creativity contributes to idea generation, which is essential for driving innovation within the Statutory Advocacy sector. Considering the sector's fragmented nature, employing a multiple case study approach is an effective strategy to tackle this issue and fill the existing gap in literature concerning idea generation. This method allows for a detailed examination of diverse instances within the sector, providing a comprehensive analysis that can inform and enhance future advocacy efforts.

Chapter 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter will provide an extensive review of literature around change, innovation, creativity, and the links to statutory advocacy as part of the social care sector.

The chapter is broken down into different key areas including the third sector discussion, social innovation, idea generation and creativity.

2.1 The Third Sector

The focus of this thesis is to examine the role of creativity in the statutory advocacy sector, which is considered a part of the health and social care sector in the third sector. Before delving into the topics of change and innovation, it is essential to provide a definition of the third sector. This is important because the sector faces distinct challenges that differ from the other two sectors.

One of the simplest ways to establish the third sector is to apply Paton's three stage model, which simply defines organisations in one of the corners of a triangle (Alcock and Kendall, 2011) clearly demarking the difference in the approaches. This forces organisations to be categorised as operating in one area - state, market, or civil society. It is a simplistic overview but one that sets out the path for discussion around civil society and the organisations that operate within it. From this model, civil society can also be termed the third sector, being clear that it is not one of the two options, although this simple explanation hides the fact that there is a lack of consensus around the definition of the term itself (Grotz, 2009). It identifies organisations that operate in the space beyond state control and free marketplaces (Alexander, 2010). It is in this space that the UK government has developed a civil strategy approach, published in 2018, that develops close coalitions between all three elements (Jones, 2021).

A more detailed model helps to highlight the complex power dynamics and interchanges that may exist, linking further elements such as formality or profit focused organisations. These organisations can be considered mixed, with a range of objectives, demonstrated more clearly in Evers & LaValle's model (Alcock, 2010). It is this space that has been termed a 'baggy loose monster' (Kendall and Knapp, 1995) as it contains a range of stakeholders, each with widely differing needs and lacking a unified ideology (Osborne, 2008).

By applying Paton's three-stage model, it becomes apparent that the third sector is a heterogeneous entity that defies a single definition (Halfpenny and Reid, 2002). This is because the sector is influenced by political and cultural contexts, which shape the organisations that operate within it (Alcock, 2010). The sector encompasses a diverse range of topics, from homelessness to education and animal welfare, each requiring a unique approach (Corry, 2010). Despite the differences, all third sector approaches share a common goal of driving social and economic change within communities (Alcock, 2010). The complexity of the third sector underscores the need for a more detailed model, such as Evers and Laville (2004a), which highlights the power dynamics and interchanges that exist between different types of organisations (Alcock, 2010). Overall, the third sector is a heterogeneous space that defies simple categorization and requires a multifaceted approach to address its unique challenges.

Attempting to define the third sector as a singular entity can lead to two different approaches, one being the definition based on what the organisations consist of and what they do not, and the other being a more process-oriented view of society (Corry, 2010). However, the reality of the third sector is far messier and complex, with various factors and contexts shaping the organisations within it (Alexander, 2010). The health and social care third sector is a rapidly evolving environment driven by sociological issues. Thus, a definition of the third sector that accurately encompasses statutory advocacy should recognize the intermediaries that deliver services to both public and private sectors, creating a unique social economy that bridges the gap between the state and private sectors. These intermediaries can include cooperatives and charities, among others (Evers, 2005, Defourny and Nyssens, 2008).

The measurement of social value within the social economy is a topic of ongoing debate (Auerswald, 2009, Kroeger and Weber, 2014), but this falls outside the scope of this research.

For this thesis, organisations that contribute to the social economy and generate collective wealth, rather than solely focusing on individual investment returns, are considered part of the third sector (Evers and Laville, 2004b). However, there is still a grey area as some providers may aim to achieve both objectives, particularly when bidding for service contracts.

2.1.1 Change in the Third Sector

Before delving into the topic of social innovation and ideation, it is important to explore the underlying concept of the need for change in an organisation or sector. Some may argue that without the requirement to change, innovation becomes irrelevant as the focus should be on

optimizing the delivery of products and services for cost-effectiveness. However, the reality is that the need for change is a constant force for organisations, driven by both external and internal pressures within the marketplace (Moran and Brightman, 2001). In fact, it has been suggested that stable organisations are the exception, with marketplaces characterized by constant change and evolution (Tsoukas and Chia, 2002). This means that providers, like other organisations, must look beyond their own walls and keep a finger on the pulse of the dynamic changes happening around them (Arvidson, 2018).

External pressures can stem from various factors, including political, technological, economic, and social trends, while internal pressures can arise from employees within an organisation (Burnes, 2004). In the case of the third sector, change can be driven by new market entrants, technological advancements, and legal regulations, among others (Alcock, 2010). Providers operate in a complex environment with multiple stakeholders, each with different needs and demands (Arvidson, 2018). It is widely accepted that change is not the exception but rather the norm in most marketplaces (Leifer, 1989). Theoretical discussions of change typically categorize it as either planned or emergent, and as continuous or discontinuous, depending on its nature (Bamford and Forrester, 2003, Meyer et al., 1990).

Change can be unpredictable in terms of its strength, timing, and size. Therefore, it is important for organisations to build in the ability to adapt as a key element in their plans, whether they are strategic, tactical, or operational (By, 2005). Interestingly, this unpredictability can also classify change as discontinuous, meaning that it comes in leaps and bounds rather than gradual progression (Nelson, 2003). Whether discontinuous change is incremental or radical, the definition of evolution via punctuated equilibrium tends to resonate in the marketplace (Sabherwal et al., 2001).

As mentioned earlier, the sources of change are diverse, ranging from political to natural disasters. The third sector is not exempt from these forces of change, and it can be argued that change is an intrinsic aspect of the sector. The third sector operates within a dynamic environment shaped by interactions between market and state, making change a vital element of the sector (Kendall, 2000). The third sector offers a strategic unity approach, taking into account the needs and requirements of all three key parties - state, market, and civil society - to develop solutions to social and economic challenges (Alcock, 2010).

Providers can face various sources of change, including resource dependence and goal interdependence (Arvidson and Linde, 2021). When providers accept external funding from

the state or market, they give up a significant amount of their organisational autonomy (Ebrahim, 2003). This interdependence between providers and the state has led to concerns about the ability of organisations to achieve their stated objectives (Arvidson, 2018). Political factors such as legislation and government policies can be powerful drivers of change within the third sector (Akingbola et al., 2019).

Brexit has led to an increased level of uncertainty in the third sector (Westerman, 2020). This uncertainty has the potential to create challenges for the third sector, including a potential loss of funding and a decrease in volunteer participation (Ferrell-Schweppenstedde, 2017, NCVO, 2018). However, some argue that the uncertainty may also create opportunities for the third sector, including a deeper understanding between the UK government and civil society (Mills, 2022). The creation of the civil society forum allows for discussions around post-Brexit third sector developments, aligning with European bodies (Mills, 2022).

External funding can come with its own set of challenges for providers, as it can be tied to personal interests rather than community needs. This means that providers may need to be agile in their service delivery to meet donor expectations (Martin and Osberg, 2007). However, this can also lead to greater donor control over the activities undertaken by providers, which can limit opportunities for innovation as the funder may influence the outputs of the organisation (Barman, 2002). It is important to note that true autonomy is the ultimate aim for any organisation, which means having freedom from external mechanisms of control such as funding or directed activities (Salancik and Pfeffer, 1978). A potential solution is to find a midpoint through the concept of discretion, which allows organisations to maintain a level of autonomy while meeting the needs of external funders (Arvidson and Linde, 2021).

The COVID-19 pandemic has caused significant disruptions across various sectors, and the third sector has not been an exception. As Jones (2021) notes, the pandemic has led to a complete re-evaluation of some services, with others forced to adapt to new ways of operating. The pandemic has resulted in an increase in demand for services, coupled with a decrease in funding and resources (Institute of Fundraising, 2020). Besides the practical implications, the pandemic has also served as a driver for change, prompting society to reflect on its needs and values (Barr, 2020). In this regard, the pandemic has created an opportunity to challenge sedimental approaches to consolidation that may exist in the third sector (Alcock, 2010).

The COVID-19 pandemic has created tension within the third sector, leading to a need for innovative approaches, alternative sources of funding, and creative working practices (Hyndman, 2020). However, not all conflict between priorities is negative, as it can create space for innovation to occur (Evans, 1999). Competition in the sector has led to tension between social mission and innovative responsiveness to the external environment, and a focus on innovation could potentially address this challenge and improve productivity in the sector (Chew and Osborne, 2007a, Kattel et al., 2013). The pandemic has led to an unprecedented level of innovative response, with organisations bypassing small, incremental changes and instead opting for more revolutionary changes (Woolliscroft, 2020).

2.1.2 Innovation

Innovation is a deliberate process that can help drive change in an organisation. While there are various definitions of innovation, they all share the idea that it is a purposeful approach to managing change within an organisation (Murray et al., 2010). It can help organisations grow and develop in the marketplace or simply help them maintain their position. However, some argue that constant change can negatively impact an organisation's goals and effectiveness in the long term (Rieley and Clarkson, 2001), and that routines are needed to minimize risk (Luecke, 2003). Innovation offers a proactive approach that can help organisations move away from a reactive approach to change. Providers in the third sector may particularly benefit from identifying and strategically using innovation drivers to create positive change (Luecke, 2003).

Within private sector markets, competition has been met by innovation in response to macro-economic trends (Gomulka et al., 1990). Competition in the providers has led to tension between social mission and being able to respond innovatively to external environment (Chew and Osborne, 2007a), a suggested focus on innovation could potentially address this challenge and improve productivity in the sector (Kattel et al., 2013).

The complexity of the third sector has led to an increasing use of innovation practices copied from the private sector market (Salamon et al., 2017). This porting over of approaches has led to challenges around adopting homogenous practices, creating isomorphic providers, which reduces the impact of innovation through a lack of diversity in the relevant sector (Dolnicar et al., 2008).

Whilst organisational innovation is purposeful, the underpinning drivers for innovation can range from accidental all the way through to planned changes. The drivers can be singular or can be a cocktail of reasons for innovation – internal and external.

2.2 External Forces

Macro forces such as industry deregulation, globalization, and technological innovation can also drive change beyond organisational boundaries, impacting all three sectors - private, public, and third sector (Graetz and Smith, 2010). The ability to cope with these changes through reflexive actions of individuals and collectives is a hallmark of successful organisations. In fact, it leads to a view of an organisation as an outcome of responses to external stimuli rather than an abstract entity (Tsoukas and Chia, 2002).

Health and social care services are positioned between the private, public, and third sectors, owing to the neoliberal philosophy currently embraced by the UK government (McGregor, 2001). The outsourcing of public health and social care delivery, with local authorities retaining only funding and direction control, exemplifies how financial considerations can be a significant driver of change (Salamon and Anheier, 1996). Another critical factor is political will to establish these quasi-market forces, which is expected to promote economic maximization through neoliberalism (Henig et al., 2003). This political agenda is not only limited to national contexts, as evidenced by the global shift towards more liberalised marketplaces that prioritize limited government intervention (McGregor, 2001).

2.2.1 Neoliberalism

The government's adoption of the neoliberalist philosophy has positioned health and social care in the middle of the three sectors, with the outsourcing of public health and social care delivery being an example of how finance can be a significant driver (Salamon and Anheier, 1996). This political agenda is driven by the desire to create economic maximisation through neoliberalism, and is aligned with the global trend towards more liberalised marketplaces and limited government intervention (McGregor, 2001). This has led to the emergence of quasi-market forces, the rise of strategic management, and the growth in managerial roles as key drivers of change in the sector (McNulty and Ferlie, 2002). However, marketplaces are not linear, and changes can lead to failure even when following a defined approach (Edwards et al., 2020), posing risks that can be passed on to non-state actors.

Combined with a three stage neoliberalist approach of individual choice, decentralisation deregulation, this political philosophy can be viewed as one of the biggest macro drivers of change in the social care sector (McGregor, 2001).

The neoliberal approach has attracted some criticisms, with some commentators suggesting that it struggles to offer the answers that the Chicago school set out to offer (Davies, 2012). An additional critique goes to the heart of the neoliberal approach, as it expects consumers of products and services will act rationally (Van Houdt et al., 2011), with price being a key mechanism for social coordination in communities (Davies, 2012).

This top-down technocratic approach adopted by governments assumes that individuals act rationally, allowing for a one-size-fits-all approach to be identified and scaled across society (Taylor, 2015). However, this approach ignores the reality that individuals do not make purely rational choices based on full information, but rather as part of interrelated networks that make choices in a more habitual way (Davies, 2012).

2.2.2 Communitarianism

A counter to this neoliberal approach has been the development of a communitarian ideology, that changes the focus away from the individual and thinks of nations as a set of communities (Van Houdt et al., 2011). This communitarian approach emphasizes the importance of social capital and the collective action of communities to solve societal problems (Putnam, 2000). It recognizes the importance of social networks and relationships in shaping individual behaviour and decision making (Davies, 2012). This perspective suggests that social care and other public services should be provided by locally based and community-driven initiatives rather than through the market or the state (Taylor, 2015).

Communitarianism tries to strike a balance between the individual and their social rights and responsibilities (Etzioni, 2007), creating a multi-layered citizen who is a member of numerous communities, which then creates value in society (Van Til, 1997). However, this idea can be left open to criticisms of the approach, especially as some commentators see communities as a mechanism of normalization and control of those who have a societal disadvantage, rather than a unifying synergistic ideology (Etzioni, 2009).

Neocommunitarianism aims to strike a balance between individual rights and responsibilities, while keeping the cost to the state in check. It is located in the middle ground between communitarianism and neoliberalism, using a liberal ideology as its basis (Hyland, 2002). The success of neocommunitarianism depends on individuals recognizing their rights and

responsibilities and using them to become active members of society (Van Houdt et al., 2011).

The neo-communitarian approach emphasizes that social cohesion is not built on marketplace pricing and choice, which rely on quantitative mechanisms, but rather on a qualitative methodology that involves citizens being active in communities rather than passive consumers (Davies, 2012). It holds that individuals not only have to obey the political entity of the state, but also have a responsibility to contribute to society by fostering a sense of shared values through their links to the community (Van Houdt et al., 2011).

Whilst the UK government has mainly utilised neoliberal approaches, it has in recent years added more elements from a neocommunitarianism ideology when working with the third sector, focusing on supporting economic development with social cohesion (Fyfe, 2005) and a drive to increase social capital (Siisiainen, 2003). It started with the labour government in 1997, who actively worked to change their relationships with third sector through the concept of a third way (Kendall, 2000), a blend of private and public sector solutions – a move away from the binary choices of either big market/ small state or small market and big state (Fyfe and Milligan, 2003a).

2.2.3 Political Priorities

The priorities and expectations of the health and social care sector can influence the need, urgency, and support for innovation. These sectors are often seen as innovation-rich areas, with funding available for studies and a political will for successful outcomes to be replicated throughout the sector. However, there is a perceived disparity between health care and social care, with most funding directed towards physical outcomes through the NHS, leaving social care as the poor relation. The adoption of a minimised governmental approach, including introducing competition via market forces, has been a predictable linear change over the last decade, influencing all levels from long-term strategic goals to day-to-day operational planning for organisations. (McGregor, 2001; By, 2005; Burnes, 2004).

Unexpected events such as Covid-19 in turn can have an outsized impact on the marketing place. Resources available to societies and all three sectors have been stretched, speeding up the rate of change or even creating new opportunities in response (Taylor-Gooby et al., 2021). The impact of the Covid-19 pandemic has seen a radical change in behaviours including available funding, with predictions of an ‘economic storm’ (Atay et al., 2020).

Due to the unpredictability of change, organisations tend to adopt a reactive approach, responding to the stimulus beyond their control (Luecke, 2003).

2.2.4 Societal Changes

Wider macro factors can also be innovation drivers, politically changing the prime minister or even the party in charge can offer opportunities for innovating. Change does not exist in a vacuum and therefore the context surrounding it is key, especially in a healthcare setting (Dopson et al., 2008). External pressures, due to the shifting demographic and sociological changes of the population, require healthcare providers to change as they need to deliver low cost safe care for their patients (McGinnis et al., 2013). Planned change in health care tends to be driven from the top and slow to be delivered, to manage the risk versus reward equation (Bamford and Griffin, 2008)

Operating with service users can also mean that the driver for innovation may come from service users. A move to digital technology, different forms of communication or even change in behaviour post covid, can all lead to a factor that will drive change. Tax regimes, investment approaches or even law around charitable statuses can be other factors that force change and in turn offer opportunities for innovation at an organisational level.

External forces are often only interpreted through the lens of current organisational ability, with the ideology that change is a perception by internal stakeholders (Dopson et al., 2008). This can be important as the outcomes are influenced by the internal stakeholders individual ideologies and responses to this perception (Poole et al., 2000).

2.2.5 Competition for Funding

A strong factor amongst all the macro factors is the access to and sources of finance, within the respective sectors. Private sector organisations may need to reflect the needs of their shareholders, whilst public sector may need to respond to the needs of their stakeholders (Donelan et al., 1999).

A key mechanism to drive this change was centralised funding, accessed through a tendering process which follows a homogenous fiscal approach, utilising return on investment (ROI) as the base line measure (Baines et al., 2011). This is notionally increased accountability of providers, (Hwang and Powell, 2009) and allowed different organisations in nonaligned markets to be compared, using market forces to meet the social demands that exists (Davies, 2012).

The increased competition in the third sector (Bennett, 2003) has put a premium on being successful at accessing funding (Zappalà, 2001), with a growing importance on effectiveness and efficiency (Glennon et al., 2017) when delivering community based services (Bittschi et al., 2015). Success can hinge on offering the best ROI or social return on investment (SROI) (Arvidson et al., 2013), prioritising efficiency over effectiveness (Herman and Renz, 2008). SROI tries to include the concept of social capital in an easily shared metric (Classens, 2015), as it is linked to fiscal responsibility whilst measuring positive community contribution (Nicholls, 2009). The heterogenous nature of the third sector and the subjectivity of measurement, can mean that SROI is challenging to use when benchmarking performance of organisations (Ryan and Lyne, 2008).

The changes have increasingly blurred the boundaries between private and public sectors (Lubienski, 2001) leading to traditional approaches not being so clear cut (Gulosino and Lubienski, 2011) with the blend of economic and social capital being drivers for change (Baines et al., 2011). Social capital was identified by Putnam (Helliwell and Putnam, 1995) as a community level resource which encompassed all the norms, networks and social trust that build cooperation in society (Baum and Ziersch, 2003).

Borrowing the term from accounting, this capital is an accumulation of individuals contributions to a society including all the interconnected networks and soft skills which are created (Siisiainen, 2003, Winter, 2000). The link between neoclassical economics and a psychological critique has created a new mindset that ascribes value to the individual elements such a networks, desires and happiness (Davies, 2012). A subject centred approach which embraces conflict and can be directly linked to economics is a powerful narrative for society (Cronin, 1996). It was proposed as a mechanism to allocate value to intangible activities and connections, which could be linked to the economic health of a nation (Putnam, 2000). Taken at an individual level, social capital can be examined by looking at the bonds, bridges and linkages that each member of the community creates (Coleman, 1988), the total of this value then could be considered as part of the health and wealth of societies and communities (Putnam, 2000).

2.2.6 Social Capital

Identifying, valuing and objectively calculating the social capital in a society can be challenging, calculation of the individual outputs was felt to be lacking by some

commentators, so a more rounded Bordieuan approach was offered as a preferred option (Siisiainen, 2003).

Social capital can be shaped by the trust and common values that are shared when working in formal and informal roles (Lee and Brudney, 2012). This why researchers favour a quantitative methodology to calculate the social capital (Baum and Ziersch, 2003), although there have been attempts to try to identify and value qualitative connections (Grootaert and Van Bastelar, 2002). The drive to increase social capital (Lyons et al., 2012) within the UK economy led to a change in the government policy in the 1990's (Fyfe and Milligan, 2003b) making the third sector organisations that are offering services, compete for a share of centralised funding opportunities (Jäger and Beyes, 2010).

2.2.7 Social Return on Investment

Providers of funding for delivery of SA, were continually looking for an improved return on investment through financial and social capital (Fyfe and Milligan, 2003a). Effectiveness became a new key driver for social organisations, which was hard to judge as it can be seen as an emergent property or a social constructivist approach (Balser and McClusky, 2005). This pitched providers against each other when it comes to delivering services, in an already crowded marketplace, with competition coming from for profit organisations (Bennett, 2003) leading to a move away from informal volunteer-based providers to a mixture of paid and voluntary professionals (Salamon, 2003). The third sector grew to accommodate these new demands with current estimates putting employees at around 800,000 employees (Geyne-Rajme and Mohan, 2012), with a push to build capacity in local communities to replace centralised state services (Milligan and Fyfe, 2005). To survive and compete in the changing sector, organisations need to innovate to meet the new demands (Parsons and Broadbridge, 2004).

2.2.8 Organisational Structures

This forced providers to adopt one of two approaches – a grass root voluntary organisation or a more professionalised corporatist organisation (Knight, 1993) (Bryson et al., 2002) (Milligan, 1998). The grassroots approach stayed more focused on the social ideology with a cause at the heart of their mission, often being identified by a looser collective with a local vision and relying on volunteers (Milligan, 1998). These providers tended to focus on a community first approach, which helps create social capital, swapping this as a trade-off for professionalisation (Taylor, 2015).

The corporatist structures tend to follow a professionalised bureaucratic hierarchical system, basing their approach on some private sector organisations (Fyfe and Milligan, 2003b). It also included a move towards the concept of social enterprise, with a more entrepreneurial approach (Zappalà, 2001). The traditional form of providers were felt to be run by do-gooders, which did not offer the level of accountability and responsibility that governments expecting from their service providers (Hwang and Powell, 2009).

Corporatism creates a highly structured top down framework local, regional or national level organisations (Fyfe and Milligan, 2003a), which incorporates the private sector approach of development through strategic plans and formal policies or practices, all of which is aimed at helping organisations achieve its purpose (Young, 2001). This approach led to a change in the dynamics of charitable organisations, with a focus on them becoming a provider of services, delivered by paid and highly trained volunteers, with users becoming clients with their own rights and responsibilities using terminology such as clients (Milligan and Fyfe, 2005).

In further steps towards a private sector approach, providers have increasingly been expected to identify their strategic position (Bennett, 2008) and develop positioning strategies for their products and services for their clients (Chew and Osborne, 2007b). The outcome of the market shift is that the third sector now operates in a unique way (Brudney and Meijs, 2009), with tasks being completed by paid workers, volunteers, or a combination of the two (Hwang and Powell, 2009), something that is not replicated in either the private or public sector. There are increasing pressures to change due to economic and social issues, yet these are not aligned and may be in competition with each other (Bessant and Maher, 2009).

2.3 Internalised change forces

Change drivers are not only found beyond the organisational boundaries, some of the most powerful are stakeholders. They are often more than just passive recipients to the process, they can be agents for and against change, responding to the change forces in a myriad of ways (Dopson et al., 2008). Stakeholders ideologies can not only define the organisational response to change, in many cases it can alter the perception of it in a first place which is often as important as the outcome (Poole et al., 2000).

The change lens of an organisation can define the size, role and reaction to change events, with the consequent framing impacting the organisational ability (Dopson et al., 2008).

Whilst all the external forces can create a challenging operating environment, the ability to surf the challenges between tension and ambiguities, can open the reflective organisation to innovation success through creativity (Graetz and Smith, 2010) (Evans, 1999).

2.3.1 Organisational Efficiency

Driving organisational efficiency is one reason for adopting innovation, trying to do more or the same, with less (Anheier and Seibel, 1990). This could be a positive change (improvements in technology have reduced the need for staff) or a change that comes from a challenge (reduction in funding opportunities). The result can be economies of scope, scale, density, and learning – all of which offer efficiency gains through process reengineering, technology implementation or other approaches (Bovaird, 2014).

Innovation that increases efficiency in the third sector, is seen to deliver more personalised and also social value (Kelly, 2007). This can be achieved by radical or incremental approaches which both can offer large impact on efficiency of organisations services. Increased efficiency that is at the heart of change with the third sector (Bovaird, 2014).

Limited resources available for the third sector (Jenei and Kuti, 2008), does mean that often the focus is on optimising the current rather than inventing the new. Small & medium sized providers find that they can eventually be ‘hollowed out’ due to a lack of resources and ability to engage meaningfully with government funders (Aiken and Harris, 2017).

Achieving both service improvements and savings through optimising organisation, offering shared services, and changing delivery models, has been used as rationale for adopting a more neoliberal approach within the health care sector (Cram, 2012). For a sector that is both highly complex and mostly heterogenous, trying centrally to optimise services can be seen as a bewildering approach (Kelly, 2007).

Whilst this can be seen as a negative force, often resource constraints can support innovative organisations, as it can boost the return on investment. Developing technical and managerial innovation ideas, supported by a progressive strategic mindset offers a way for organisations to deliver superior returns (Tuominen and Hyvönen, 2004)

2.3.2 Knowledge Acquisition

One area that can drive innovation is the development of knowledge for an organisation. Linked to the idea of knowledge-based value (KBV), creativity and innovation stem from an organisation’s ability to manage their knowledge (Zhou and Li, 2012). Knowledge itself has been identified as a strategic asset, allowing organisations and sectors to create differentiation

(Hsu and Sabherwal, 2011). Organisations that listen and act on feedback from their client or engage in knowledge transfer partnerships, ultimately will grow this asset and increase their KBV (Zhou and Li, 2012).

Learning more about your client base, developing new methodologies of work or adoption of an open innovation approach can all increase the organisational capability (Chen and Huang, 2009) Knowledge can come from horizon scanning, partnerships, knowledge transfer partnerships and other forms of collaboration. An organisation that is continually engaging the most current thinking can utilise this to create a competitive advantage in the field, whether it be using a business model from an adjacent industry or flexing some current thinking elsewhere (Hult et al., 2004).

Experience is often one of the key drivers for innovation on a micro and macro scale. Learning from problems that are faced, getting feedback from relevant stake holders, and tapping into the corporate memory can generate opportunities for change and growth. Developing organisational capabilities around knowledge based values can be even more important within the third sector (Arvidson, 2009).

2.3.3 Organisational Change

A more tangible driver of change and in turn innovation, is through organisational change. Staff members joining or leaving, can all add or subtract from the corporate knowledge available- (Tidd and Bessant, 2020). Knowledge and corporate memory can be viewed as an asset, which allows organisations the ability to increase their efficiency through continual learning (Chosnek, 2010).

This might have more of an impact in the third sector, as most of the organisations operate in a very lean and flat structure, which is highlighted as factors that can feel the change most acutely (Chosnek, 2010).

Taking a wider view - It does not just have to be employees, it can also include external stakeholders who may drive the innovation agenda – often they are viewed as passive recipients by providers, yet they can be powerful agents for and against change (Dopson et al., 2008).

Organisational changes can also be a driver of innovation for a company. Key people leaving or different skill sets becoming apparent inside an organisation can be really a good way to deliver change. It requires a level of awareness coupled with a responsiveness that allows the

charity to benefit from this wider stakeholder groups can also be drivers for change. For example, getting funding that focuses on a certain demographic or even a set of board members who have a different mindset can ultimately drive innovation (Werther and Berman, 2001).

2.3.4 Organisational Growth

Organisational growth is a key factor that may lay at the heart of innovation. Growth allows for fixed costs to be shared over more products or services (Stigler, 1958) as well as potentially making the organisation more stable due to a differentiated revenue base (Panzar and Willig, 1981). This can bridge the internal and external stimulus for change.

Providers are not immune in the need to chase economies of scale and scope, in fact the demands placed by reduction in funding for sectors has led for organisations to become adept at doing more with less (Dees, 1998). The pressure for a growth approach can come from either an external pressure – funders want to deal with fewer but bigger organisations (Bovaird, 2014), or an organic mindset which identifies economies of scale associated with the approach (Minna et al., 2014). Therefore, growth can be a very powerful driver for change and innovation for providers.

2.4 Social Innovation

Social innovation has a rich history, with the ideas launched that tried to meet the growing complex social challenges need of citizens over time (Westley et al., 2016). The term was first thought to have been used by James Taylor in 1970, referring to community development in Kansas (Moulaert, 2013). Although this is when the specific term came into being, there has been a project that can be considered SI, driven by social movements including increasing urbanisation, feminism and trade unions, which can be linked to the approach (Mulgan et al., 2007).

The coalescence around SI as a functional area began in the late 1980's (Jessop et al., 2013) and has accelerated over the decades since (van der Have and Rubalcaba, 2016). The last ten years has seen an increasing use of SI as a field of research and application (Adams and Hess, 2010). Van der Have identifies that prior to 2003 on average less than 5 journals year were published (2016), with over 450 being published in 2021 (Shepherd, 2022)

The research reflects the increasing complexity of civil society with deepening links between socioeconomic and socio-political events happening in the 21st century (Swyngedouw, 2005).

The economic liberalisation from the 1980's through to the adoption of neoliberalist approaches in to previously state run sector, created a mechanism of New Public Management (NPM) (Lévesque, 2013). SI tied in with the release of control from centralised public sector and the drive towards empowerment within society (Van de Walle and Hammerschmid, 2011). This perspective put the onus on the producers to create and implement innovation, which then needed to be aligned with the public sector social values (Lévesque, 2013).

Mainstream innovation has on the whole ignored SI as a niche approach (Edwards-Schachter et al., 2012), with research focus often on the adoption of technology in manufacturing processes (Windrum et al., 2016, Drejer, 2004). This can partly be attributed to the fact that technological innovation in manufacturing will provide quantifiable data, whereas social interventions tend to provide data that is either qualitative or at best quantitative but subject to multiple factors.

Proponents of SI outline how technological innovation can fail unless it is supported by a development in the social sphere (Moulaert, 2016), identifying the value of pursuing both approaches. It is argued that technological innovation can only be analysed through the framework of the social order that it pertains to (Moulaert, 2016).

There has been a delineation between the sociological focus of SI rather than an economic approach (van der Have and Rubalcaba, 2016). The prior focuses on social practices whereas the economic conceptualisation is much more outcome based – identifying products and services to meet society's needs (Europeia, 2013). SI by its nature, creates approaches that require collective action or social structures, based around more open flow of ideas which is at odds with the closed look innovation methods of private sector (Moulaert, 2013)

2.4.1 Defining Social innovation

Linked to the viewpoint that innovation can be defined simply as new ideas that work (Mulgan et al., 2007), the social element of the approach is the focus of the innovation direction (MacGregor and Fontrodona, 2008). The innovation should have an explicitly stated benefit to society, which may create a social relationship or meet the needs of a community in a more effective approach (Nicholls and Edmiston, 2018). The fields that are related to social innovation are wide and can be everything from improving happiness through to climate change processes (Mulgan et al., 2007).

A definitive concept of SI has been hard to pin down with the social part referring to the methodology of approach, community based value or the intent of for profit organisations to have a positive impact by their actions (Mulgan et al., 2007). This has led to fragmentation of the field, although there have been attempts to create a unified approach (van der Have and Rubalcaba, 2016). The knock on effect of a disintegrated field is that theories and models struggle to create generalizations which would allow for scalability and applicability (Raasch et al., 2013)

The historic viewpoint that SI was a separate entity to traditional innovation (Taylor, 1970) has been superseded by more nuanced approach led by social scientists (Caulier-Grice et al., 2012) that understands it as a facet of classic models (Hochgerner, 2011, Howaldt and Schwarz, 2010, Cajaiba-Santana, 2014).

2.4.2 Economic Models of Social Innovation

The economic model of SI focuses on the creation of outputs and in turn value within society. How this is delivered can in turn be categorised in two methods (Defourny and Nyssens, 2013). The first approach is that of earned income – the idea that third sector organisations can operate in a commercial way, creating a source of revenue that allows for the non-profit making activities (Kerlin, 2006). This can be seen as a social enterprise approach and could be defined as a mission-driven business (Yunus et al., 2010). This approach favours established organisations, with activities that can be marketable. It can diversify the revenue sources for organisations, offering a mechanism to hedge risk (Defourny and Nyssens, 2013) and decouple SI from politically driven agendas (Henig et al., 2003). The challenge of utilising the earned income model for SI, is that it creates a duality of purpose (Svensson and Mahoney, 2020) which can create a tension between the social and commercial missions for the organisations (Chew and Osborne, 2007a).

The alternative is that economic value of SI is delivered through entrepreneurs who have a social mission attached to their idea (Defourny and Nyssens, 2013). Individuals or small groups work on projects that can deliver social change through outcome focused innovation (Murray et al., 2010). The second approach ignores the issue of funding or existing marketplaces, putting emphasis on the new or novel ideas to change the market. Ignoring the existing market in turn can lead to a devaluing of previous investment (through time or money) and the creation of a sector where change comes from challengers rather than incumbents.

Although SI has somewhat of a reputation about being a buzzword (Grisolia and Farragina, 2015), there is a strong argument to be made that as an interdisciplinary approach it can offer a positive way to increase social value (Moulaert, 2013).

2.4.3 Social Innovation Models

Over the last two decades, there has been a push to develop innovation models that are directly applicable to the social sector. This is allied to the concept previously discussed that societal challenges such as an ageing population and a low carbon community, can only likely be achieved through successful social innovation. (Mulgan, 2012). SI has become increasingly important as part of the new innovation paradigm (Domanski et al., 2020) , with academics and practitioners all recognising this fact (Moulaert, 2013). With the importance of social innovation highlighted, models and theories that can deliver results have been developed, often building on the traditional mechanism of private sector industries. This is in part due to the limited research around the innovation process within the social sector (Butzin et al., 2014)

The models themselves are often ported over from private sector, rather than being organically developed through analysis of social organisations. One of the reasons that the models originate elsewhere, is that social innovation as an approach is poorly understood (National Endowment for Science and Arts, 2008). The basis then of the models tends to be relying on Schumpeter's approach of technological innovation through the use of best practice (Moulaert et al., 2005).

Management of innovation has been highlighted as something almost impossible to achieve, due to the complexity and constant change. The best that can happen is a degree of facilitation rather than aiming for total control (Mowles, 2015). Despite this understanding there is a drive to use a standardised approach, often predicated on a rational stakeholder behaviour model (Butzin et al., 2014). Never more clearly has innovation pathways been seen as messy spaghetti like delivery rather than a linear orderly process reflected in the models (Tidd and Bessant, 2020). On the contrary, scholarship on innovation processes makes clear that the journey from idea generation to diffusion rarely follows a predictable, staged pattern (van de Ven, Polley, Garud, & Venkataraman, 1999). It is more accurate to categorise innovation processes in organisations as 'complex, iterative, organic and untidy' (Greenhalgh, Robert, Macfarlane, Bate, & Kyriakidou, 2005).

Whilst badged as innovation stages or models, it is perhaps better to view the innovation approach as a journey, open to changes in direction, deadlines and with unexpected issues showing up (Butzin et al., 2014). The imposition of a top-down model has been argued that it does not reflect the realities of operating in a social sector. As previously discussed, working providing services to society creates heterogeneous approaches, with factors such as geography, economic status and even sex creating complexity for use.

The Minnesota Innovation Research Program developed an innovation journey based on real life rather than a simplified journey (Van de Ven, 2017). Whilst this study looked at innovation generally, SI is more complex as it deals with society's wicked problems (Brown et al., 2009).

Therefore, numerous social innovation models have been developed to try and identify approaches that could be chosen to deliver success and drive systemic change.

2.4.4 Logue Social Innovation Model

Rather than striving for a singular definition and application of SI, Logue has developed a model that links the three elements of value creation, capture and distribution (Logue, 2019). By adopting a different starting point, the model tries to create a common language around the outcomes of the SI process.

The benefit for that is that it can apply to multiple heterogeneous organisations, in a multitude of sectors. It can also highlight the phases that an organisation must go through to create systemic change in society. It avoids forcing organisations to adopt isomorphic tendencies by allowing a large degree of freedom when utilising SI.

At its heart the model conceptualises social innovation as a form of value creation and then distribution, within society. Providers achieving this will fill the void between government and private marketplace, often creating value in underserved areas.

The strength of this approach is that it is a framework that it is not exclusionary or fixated on a methodology of delivery. Rather than seeing the diversity in the third sector as a hinderance, it is adopted as a nature of the market.

The first stage emphasises the need for organisations to source ideas, practices and models that are focused on generating social value. This social value is in addition to exist ideas, thus creating net overall benefit to society. Capture and Distribution stages aim to take the ideas and share them for most utilitarian value, which in turn legitimises the SI undertaken.

This model is promoted as an abstract idea that tries to give some shape to SI in practice. Created with both academic and practitioners in mind, it tries to adopt a pragmatic approach to the process. This is the downfall of the model as it falls between being practical or a scholarly model. Whilst emphasizing the broadness of the approach, the lack of clarity means that for most organisations it will be a very difficult tool to use.

Another challenge with the model is that it heavily linked to the economic value of SI, and in turn the providers using it. It does allow SI to become part of the conversation around SROI and the value creation previously. Bu the big drawback is that it can ignore those innovation approaches that do not create economic value or even remove harm from the system. The model uses the concepts of customers and beneficiaries, which further moves providers down the path of economic rationality (Logue, 2020). This model then has very limited use for an organisation as it does not offer a clear pathway on how to undertake SI.

2.4.5 6 Pathways Social Innovation model

A different way of modelling SI is to look at the conditions that need to exist to drive successful outcomes. The 6 pathways model uses a fsQCA approach to create a set of approaches that are more likely to deliver successful innovation (Oeij et al., 2019).

Table 6 - 6 Pathway Model (Oeij et al., 2019)

Innovation process elements leading to the adoption of social innovation			
Path	Approach	Elements Present	Elements Absent
1	Filling a gap	Stakeholder commitment Infrastructure	Financial and political support
2	Self-reliant empowerment	Financial and political support Infrastructure	Stakeholder commitment
3	Incremental progress	Consensus Infrastructure	Overcoming setbacks
4	Power-based design	Stakeholder commitment Financial and political support Consensus	
5	Powerful people and leadership	Availability of staff Leadership Infrastructure	
6	Resilient goal-getting	Stakeholder commitment Overcoming setbacks Infrastructure	Availability of staff

Using examples of successful SI and then analysing the elements that need to be present, allows for the model to build a consensus overview from a range of subjects.

The model also highlights what needs to be absent if the innovation is to be a success. This can help organisations identify which of the pathways is more likely to be relevant to their approach and in turn optimise their resources. At its heart it avoids creating a singular approach which suggests there is one best way to deliver successful SI. Whilst the model offers a range of pathways, which should be applicable to a range of sectors, the challenge is that by trying to be open the approach does not offer a concrete approach for organisations.

There is no discussion around resources allocation, the skills needed or how to follow each of these pathways. The model does highlight the need for infrastructure to be embedded to deliver success, but without going into too much detail about what this looks like or how to do it.

The innovation pathways model is an interesting academic overview of SI but would have limited practical use for organisations looking to adopt a more innovative approach.

2.4.6 Social innovation process model

A more practical model is that proposed by Beckman, Painter & Rosen ((Beckman et al., 2020) which build an iterative process focused around for key stages.

Figure 3 – Social Innovation Process (Beckman et al., 2020)

The model identifies four key points for SI – Co produce, Pilot, Scale and Diffuse. Of these elements is focused on delivery SI to the marketplace, rather than an academic discussion around approach.

The strength of this model is that it identifies the need for feedback loops at each stage, highlighted by the concept of learning. The authors state that even when moving closer to scaling the product it is still necessary to go back to the start stage if you have acquired new knowledge.

Reiteration can help to generate more effective responses to challenges, especially those that are dealing with wicked problems (Zivkovic, 2018). Social challenges tend to be multi-dimensional and complex, meaning that the solutions often exhibit the same characteristics. They also highlight that you can jump up or down in size throughout the process, responding to the success or challenges offered by the project. The drawback of the model is that it is very top level and does not help organisations or sectors plan for SI. It requires the use of skilled practitioners or those with experience in the process to help make it work for the users.

2.4.7 Six Stage Social Innovation Model

The Young Foundation, working with the government agency NESTA, developed a social innovation model based around six key stages. These are prompts, proposals, prototyping, sustaining, scaling and systemic change (Murray et al., 2010).

The six stage process of social innovation model can be found in the Open Book of Social Innovation (Murray et al., 2010), created jointly between the Young Foundation and NESTA. These two key organisations in the third sector, created the approach based on research from hundreds of global organisations.

Figure 4 – Social Innovation Model (Murray et al., 2010)

The model offers six very clear steps, that will seem logical and natural to anyone who has worked in the third sector. In simple terms SI comes from a set of prompts, which then allows organisations to make proposals that address these issues or challenges. The best of these will be then prototyped to demonstrate the efficacy, before moving to a more sustainable model if successful. The model then encourages successful organisations to think about scaling up their innovation, which ultimately can result in systemic change through the process. The model is reminiscent of a traditional stage gate innovation approach, with clearly defined stages, that often will require different skills and knowledge in each stage.

It offers a good starting point for organisations looking to attempt to manoeuvre their innovation, without being too prescriptive as can happen with other models. The Young Foundation are clear that it is a start of defining an SI approach, with the intent to develop the work overtime.

The definition of the stages reinforces some of the key elements that exist when trying to use innovation to address a prompt. A good example is that by creating a prototype stage, the model is encouraging experimentation as part of the process rather than just creating a tunnel of ideas that gets launched. This naming convention explicit aims for innovation that is more than just an amendment to the status quo, highlighting the possibility that being successful can lead to systemic change. Whilst the 6-stage process model offers a clear methodology for SI, it is not without its issues. The open book of social innovation (Murray et al., 2010) in which the model is developed runs to over 200 pages, with a deep dive into each stage.

Firstly, in supporting materials to the stages, the authors state that the stages are not always sequential and there are feedback loops between them” (Murray et al., 2010). As previously discussed linear innovation models are based on a rational step by step approach (Butzin et al., 2014), which is by consensus a long way from how SI happens (Tidd and Bessant, 2020). For the authors to acknowledge this yet produce a model that just reinforces the sequential steps is at best misleading. The simplicity of the model offered therefore is lost, due to the need to read the accompanying materials, adding barriers to the process.

The introduction to the book, highlights that it is a knowledge sharing approach, with the six stages more a reflection of the general themes from the research. For each stage, examples are included from a range of organisations around the world and suggested activities are highlighted. This moves it from a process focused approach to a more holistic knowledge sharing concept, reflecting on what has been used rather than creating a model that can predict future outcomes.

So, a model which at first glance offers a clear process driven method for SI, becomes much more of a fluid framework reflecting the previous discussions around the challenge of managing innovation. The authors have explored each stage in depth, but it can feel like it is a list of what others have done in that stage rather than offering a workable model. This effectively creates an inductive theoretical model. There is no suggestion that organisations followed this prescribed model, so the successes may be difficult to replicate due to the complicating contextual factors.

Previously we have discussed the challenge in the third sector, a heterogeneous group of organisations with complex stakeholders often delivering services, which would make the use of a generalised model challenging. It is open to debate about how effective a hegemonic idea deriving a centralised idea of a one size fits all approach, can be in practical use. The model also presupposes that there is only a single answer amongst the ideas. It does not build room for a multi angled approach. Systemic change just comes from putting ideas into the system rather than something separate that needs to be worked at.

The assumption that an answer exists for the prompt is also made in the model’s presentation, it may be that an answer is not available or does not fit an innovation approach. It suggests that there is an end to the innovation approach, rather than building a concept which demonstrates reflectively and ongoing change. It provides a 2d approach to dealing with a 3d

world. A logical and classical model – ignores approaches that may have developed in a more technologically developed world.

2.5 Idea Generation

Comparing the models, the different steps can be distilled into three broad areas that are common to each approach. These can be broadly labelled as issue diagnosis, idea generation and then launching innovation.

Figure 5 Simplified and Combined Social Innovation Processes

Some of the models then go on to focus on creating wider change as part of their actions, but from an organisational perspective these are the three key elements. Of interest to this research is the idea generation stage, below the table highlights where this appears in each model

Table 7 - Social Innovation Models with Idea Generation Highlighted

Name	Number of stages	Stages	Year
Process of Social Innovation (Murray et al., 2010)	6	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Prompts. 2. Proposals. 3. Prototypes. 4. Sustaining. 5. Scaling. 6. Systemic Change. 	2010
Social Impact Framework (Bates, 2012)	6	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Define Social Challenge. 2. Understand & Prioritise needs. 3. Examine the opportunity. 	2012

		4. Devise a workable solution. 5. Develop a business model. 6. Diffusion of Innovation.	
Logue Model(Logue, 2019)	3	1. Value Creation 2. Capture 3. Distribution	2019
Social Innovation Process (Beckman et al., 2020)	4 (nonlinear)	1. Co-produce 2. Pilot 3. Scale 4. Diffuse	2020

Generating and then delivering innovative ideas is key to the success of organisations (Chesbrough, 2006). Idea generation is a key element, but one that is only touched upon briefly in most of the social innovation models (Girotra et al., 2010).

Idea generation or Ideation as it is termed, is often overlooked due to the focus on delivery of innovation in organisations (Kornish and Hutchison-Krupat, 2017). The lines between idea generation and innovation are often blurred in the research literature. Warr and O’Neil’s unified model of creative process, links this step with problem preparation and idea evaluation, as the initial process needed before starting innovation itself (Warr and O’Neill, 2005).

This help reinforce that ideation is the first stage in problem solving, also considered one of the most important (Sowrey, 1990), where ideas are created that offer potential solutions to the situation in hand (Nijstad and Stroebe, 2006). This step requires a level of personal and organisational creativity, which can offer competitive advantages (Cook, 1998). Ideas that are generated at the early stage, often do not die, but can be used throughout the innovation process (Herring et al., 2009). Therefore creating a rich and diverse set of ideas early on can greatly impact the likelihood of success for organisations (Osborn, 1953).

Ideation is vital for organisations to develop responses to the changing environment, design new products or services and to improve the efficacy of existing approaches (Toubia, 2006). The research into the area of idea generation tends to be split focusing on either how to create many ideas or tries to empirically measure the quality of ideas (Girotra et al., 2010). Ideas

are the raw materials for innovation (Gilson and Litchfield, 2017), with the focus on developing large numbers to increase the likelihood of success (Osborn, 1953).

Innovation theory focuses on divergent and then convergent thinking as a mechanism for creativity (Toubia, 2006). Ideation itself is concerned with mostly focusing on divergent thinking (Gurteen, 1998), trying to get participants to develop different perspectives, which in turn allows the opportunity to allow for new approaches to problems (Kuhn, 1977). Convergent mechanisms are used by organisations to filter, select and deliver appropriate ideas to market as it is based around logical and linear steps (Smith, 1998). The ability of organisations to identify needs, and then deliver solutions to market can be key to success (McAdam and McClelland, 2002). It is important to separate out the creativity surrounding ideation, and the implementation of those ideas – innovation itself (Zhuang, 2005).

The IR3 Idea Generation Process Model (Herring et al., 2009) takes the unified creative process model and further develops it to consider the divergent thinking needed for idea generation. It achieves this by adding a feedback back loop, which incorporates research (could be drawing on lived experience), representing (a sketch or verbal description) and refining (reducing complexity). The nonlinear approach to creativity, with its focus on non-distinct phases using a cycle, is a good starting point for idea generation.

Ideation sits at the crossroads of multiple social science areas including psychology. One of the seminal approaches to idea creation is that of Osborn brainstorming method, from his 1957 book – applied imagination (Girotra et al., 2010). This introduces the concept of using interaction between participants allied to creative stimulus to develop a process to create ideas.

It is also important to highlight that creativity is not linked to concepts such as intelligent quotient level, but open to anyone with ‘normal capability’ (Hennessey and Amabile, 1998). The use of creative techniques can improve idea generation in individuals (Farr and Ford, 1990) which helps to overcome some of the systemic issues that exist, due to traditional education systems focusing on analytical ability rather than creative thinking (Eskildsen et al., 1999).

The output of research is often balanced with anecdotal discussions around the efficacy of ideation within organisations, (Sutton and Hargadon, 1996). There is broad agreement that creativity is quite a complex process (Finke et al., 1996), with lots of ways to develop ideas

ranging from very formalised approaches to informal discussions (Smith, 1998). It has been argued that at heart, creativity is just a method of making connections between different ideas, which can then be applied to a problem (MacCrimmon and Wagner, 1994).

Research is mixed about the difference in individual approaches to ideation versus group-based development. The number of ideas created is significantly higher when working alone, versus when attempting brainstorming as part of a team, which feels counterintuitive (Mullen et al., 1991). There is a belief that group idea generation offers interaction with different points of view, experiences, and knowledge, which helps stimulate creativity (Paulus and Yang, 2000). Some studies have found that this is not the case, with controlled research showing that groups produce less ideas and of lower quality than individual work (Mullen et al., 1991). Group interactions can be seen as creating interference in the idea generation process, reducing the efficacy of the 'cognitive process' (Nijstad and Stroebe, 2006). The larger the group, the bigger this impact seems to be, with a productivity loss increasing as the size increases (Mullen et al., 1991), restricting the development of imaginative new ideas (Titus, 2000)

It has been suggested that tests that take place in a lab, differ greatly from real life experiences, often due to contextual pressure (Sutton and Hargadon, 1996). Elements such as organisational structures are highlighted as something missing from lab studies (Singh and Fleming, 2010). Creativity can be seen as a process that relies on context to develop ideas, with the restrictions, constraints and environment all shaping the outputs (Farr and Ford, 1990).

The diversity that can be present in teams, will obviously be lacking in when an individual undertakes ideation, which can enhance the ideas created which is more reflective of real-world environments (Kavadias and Sommer, 2007). Research has demonstrated that collaboration can improve the quality of ideas through reducing the number of 'bad' ideas proposed (Singh and Fleming, 2010). Group idea exchange can lead to stronger ideas and help overcome some of the challenges such as group think and social influences (Paulus and Yang, 2000).

Group ideation allows for ideas to build on each other, creating stronger concepts as they are developed, something that can be hard to replicate when conducting it individually (Toubia, 2006). Kirton's adaption-innovation (KAI) theory splits individuals into different groups – innovators and adapters (Stum, 2009). By blending innovators (who look for step change

ideas) with adapters (those who focus on incremental improvements based on current approach) team ideation can open new pathways that wouldn't be explored by individuals (McAdam and McClelland, 2002). If the group has some initial training to begin with, then creativity can be enhanced (Puccio et al., 2006).

Regular brainstorming with different groups has been adopted by some organisations, such as the design group IDEO. These sessions offer a way to capture the knowledge capital that exists inside the organisation and provide opportunities to use shared information to build new products or services (Paulus and Yang, 2000).

Prescriptive approaches to ideation can ignore the uniqueness of each group, problem, and situation. Typical idea generation techniques tend to be generic, open ended and requiring the users to not only create the ideas, but also to manage the process (Smith, 1998). These approaches can end up with variations of existing ideas, due to the nature of the approach. It also requires the participants to adopt different roles – with very different skillsets.

2.6 Creativity

Amabile (Amabile, 1998) highlights that there are three components of creativity – expertise, creative thinking skills and motivation. For ideation to be successful all these elements need to be present. As discussed, previous, providers in the statutory advocacy sector, alongside most providers, lack any expertise in idea generation. Van Dijk and Van Den Ende (2002) also highlights that creativity is an essential ingredient, when working on innovation.

Creative thinking skills may be present in the sector, but often are a secondary thought to the focus on delivery of services to the users. Motivation is the one area that advocacy does benefit from. Therefore, there are gaps in two out of the three components for creativity and in turn ideation.

One approach to resolve this issue is to develop an external resource that can share expertise and develop the creative thinking skills needed for idea generation. An ideation facilitator or facilitation team – like an intermediaries, would be of great benefit in the divergent stage. The natural approach for organisations and participants is to look for the end solution, thinking about elements such as resources and how the idea would work in practice. The focus is often to get to an idea as quickly as possible, rather than spending the time being creative.

Ideation managed by a skilled facilitator can minimise this rush to a convergent phase and allow exploration of a range of ideas. The challenge of relying on a facilitator is that the participants must trust the approach, be clear about what is expected and avoid solutioning straight away. Idea generation techniques are often packaged and sold in a user-friendly manner without putting any emphasis on the running of the session (Smith, 1998).

Frameworks have been developed to identify the ingredients of problem solving including 101 techniques which are broken down into over 50 methods of ideation (VanGundy, 2008).

Good ideation should include mental states, cognitive process, and creative thinking activities, which will vary by team make up, location, problem addressing and many other contextual factors. Far from being a one size fits all answer, loved by business consultants, each session should be a bespoke development, utilising all aspects of creativity (Smith, 1998). The creative process can easily be inhibited by personal bias, assumptions, and conventions. Breaking these barriers down, is key to deliver stronger and more numerous ideas (Herring et al., 2009). Money for staff that have innovation backgrounds or creative skills is often scarce, with the key focus on delivery of services. This coupled with limited internal time resource mean that creativity can be killed easily if used in a closed organisational setting (Amabile, 1998).

Van Dijk and Van Den Ende (2002) created a model that capture the three key stages of creativity, idea generation and innovation. This model highlights the need for having an organisational structure and culture that will support innovation. The ability to transfer creativity into innovation, was seen as a key capability for organisations wanting to success.

Innovative environments tend to flourish when they are short lived, heterogenous and favour a democratic style (Anderson, 2018). All these conditions are more likely to be achieved through an external open ideation approach than in a structured organisational environment, where the natural hierarchy and homogenous ideas are likely to dominate.

2.7 Research Focus

Examining creativity and the development of ideas into organisational or sector-wide innovation is crucial, particularly in the under-researched area of the social sector. This area has a paucity of literature and therefore is open to further investigation, especially given that current social innovation models only briefly address ideation as one step of the process, often lacking in-depth methodologies for the necessary divergent thinking.

Most service providers in the social sector are primarily configured for delivery, with minimal resources dedicated to nurturing and integrating new ideas. While commissioners are tasked with driving innovation within the sector, they typically depend on existing providers to propose solutions.

Developing multiple case studies that showcase how creativity and ideas are currently utilised by providers could yield substantial benefits. Such studies would not only facilitate systemic change but also begin to gather critical data on a neglected sector. This is particularly vital for delivering services to some of the most vulnerable populations. With the rising pressures from the cost-of-living crisis, shrinking local authority budgets, and increasing demands on services, the importance of fostering social innovation and creativity has never been more evident.

The research will be grounded in three key academic approaches, which together provide a distinctive perspective on creativity within the sector and form the conceptual backbone of this thesis. At its core, the study draws on the social innovation model proposed by Murray et al. (2010), which offers a structured framework tailored to the needs of TSOs. This foundation is further enriched by integrating the theoretical perspectives of Van Dijk and Van Den Ende (2002) and Amabile (1996). Both approaches focus on the utilisation of creativity, illustrating how it can be effectively harnessed and transformed into actionable ideas. These combined frameworks are crucial to understanding the ideation stage within the social innovation model and its application to the statutory advocacy sector, offering insights that will underpin the thesis's key arguments and findings.

Chapter 3: METHODOLOGY

This chapter outlines the methodology for investigating creativity in statutory advocacy providers in the United Kingdom. Due to the complex nature of creativity that exists in the organisational settings, the thesis has adopted a qualitative research approach utilising semi-structured interviews.

It will explain the philosophical and methodological foundations that guide the research strategy and design decisions (Hallebone and Priest, 2017)

The approach for data collection, ethical consideration and sampling choices are discussed with a focus on clarity of the research, analysis, sampling choices, as well as ethical considerations. This ensures rigour and transparency in the study (Creswell and Poth, 2016). The aim is that all the elements of the research align to contribute to achieving the research objective (Priest and Hallebone, 2009)

This chapter will cover research strategy, interview design, participant selection, data collection procedures, and analysis methods, supporting the study's aim to contribute valuable insights into the research area.

3.1 Research Strategy

In this thesis, it is crucial to outline the research paradigms and philosophical orientations as they form the underpinning approach of the study. These paradigms provide overarching perspectives that guide how phenomena are understood, and knowledge is generated.

The range of approaches can include a range of philosophical orientations such as positivism, interpretivism, critical theory, and post-positivism, each offering unique viewpoints on reality, knowledge acquisition, and the researcher's role. Supporting that are the fundamental beliefs about reality, knowledge validation, ethics, and suitable research methods. By engaging deeply with these paradigms and orientations, researchers can shape their research questions, choose appropriate methodologies, interpret their findings, and make meaningful contributions to knowledge in their fields.

This chapter will explore the choices made for this thesis, explain how these were made and highlight any alternatives that were considered.

3.1.1 Ontological Approach

When exploring creativity dynamics within the UK statutory advocacy sector, critical realism serves as a foundational philosophy. Drawing from the theories of Roy Bhaskar (Bhaskar et al., 1998), this approach offers a nuanced perspective on reality, distinguishing between the 'real' (underlying structures), the 'actual' (events), and the 'empirical' (observable occurrences). In the context of statutory advocacy, critical realism allows for an exploration of how underlying social and institutional structures influence the expression and acknowledgment of creative practices. This viewpoint becomes particularly significant in comprehending how systemic elements, such as policy shifts or organizational norms, impact the innovative outcomes within advocacy endeavours. This allows researchers to investigate how advocacy professionals navigate these frameworks, crafting inventive solutions within intricate, sometimes constraining, regulatory environments. Notable works offer guidance on integrating critical realism into social science, while literature on creativity within professional domains sheds light on the sector-specific dynamics of innovation and adaptation (Bhaskar et al., 1998, Bhaskar, 1989).

To examine creativity in professional sectors, alternative ontological approaches can provide different insights compared to critical realism. One such approach is social constructivism (Schunk and Usher, 2012), which posits that our understanding of reality, including concepts like creativity, is constructed through social interactions and cultural contexts (Kim, 2001). This perspective emphasizes the role of language, communication, and social processes in shaping our understanding of creativity (Binks et al., 2006). It would examine how collective meanings and perceptions about creativity are developed and sustained within professional environments (Amineh and Asl, 2015).

Another approach is phenomenology (Moran, 2002), focusing on the lived experiences and subjective perspectives of individuals (Flood, 2010). In the context of creativity in professional sectors, phenomenology would explore how individuals personally experience and make sense of creative processes (Cerbone, 2014), potentially revealing diverse and nuanced understandings of creativity that are overlooked by more structural approaches.

A third approach is post-structuralism, which challenges the notion of fixed or inherent meanings (Devetak, 2009), including the concept of creativity. From this viewpoint, the study of creativity in professional sectors would involve deconstructing the established norms and power relations (Olssen, 2003) that define what is considered 'creative', revealing how these

definitions are contingent, fluid, and influenced by broader socio-political dynamics (Dillet, 2017).

Each of these ontological approaches offers a unique lens through which to explore creativity, emphasizing different aspects such as social construction, individual experience, or the deconstruction of established norms and power dynamics.

After careful consideration, critical realism was selected as the preferred ontological framework for researching the statutory advocacy sector. This choice acknowledges the subjective nature of creativity within the sector and aims to explore how underlying social and institutional structures shape its manifestation and recognition.

3.1.2 Critical Realism: applicability and assumptions

Whilst the ontological approach may be aligned with the thesis topic, applying critical realism to study creativity in professional sectors, such as the statutory advocacy sector in the UK, presents unique challenges.

Critical realism, with its layered understanding of reality, provides a nuanced framework to address the inherent subjectivity in defining and measuring creativity, especially in professional sectors. This philosophy acknowledges that perceptions (the empirical) are not always a direct reflection of the underlying realities (the real) (Pernecky, 2016).

In the context of creativity for SA providers, this means that what is perceived or recognized as creative in a professional environment is influenced by underlying structures and power dynamics, which may not always be visible or quantifiable. Critical realism thus allows the thesis to look beyond subjective assessments of creativity, exploring the deeper, often hidden, generative mechanisms that enable or constrain creative expression (Sayer, 2004). This approach is particularly valuable in understanding how institutional norms, cultural expectations, and socio-economic factors shape our definitions and measurements of creativity, leading to a more holistic and less biased understanding of creativity in the workplace (Groff, 2004).

The two main reasons for applying critical realism to SA providers builds on the previous theoretical discussion.

Firstly, critical realism's emphasis on underlying structures and mechanisms can be difficult to operationalise in empirical research, especially when examining abstract concepts like creativity (Jansen, 2020). It requires a careful balance between acknowledging the unseen

generative forces and the observable creative outcomes (Bhaskar et al., 1998). The study focused on senior leaders within SA providers as they were expected to offer insights into the organization's broader approaches to creativity. However, a potential limitation was that these leaders might overlook subtle, everyday instances of creativity, such as practitioners gradually enhancing work methods.

Secondly, capturing the dynamic interplay between individual agency and structural constraints in creative processes demands methodologically diverse and often complex approaches (Sayer, 2004), which can be resource intensive. Moreover, critical realism's critique of positivist methodologies can clash with prevalent research norms in some professional fields (Vega and Chiasson, 2019), necessitating a nuanced approach to integrate its philosophical underpinnings. Lastly, translating the theoretical insights of critical realism into practical recommendations for fostering creativity within professional contexts can be challenging, as it involves not just understanding, but also altering, deep-seated institutional and social structures (Groff, 2004). The SA providers typically gather and organize quantitative data to report progress on contracts and grants. This presents a positivist data collection opportunity that might have simplified the thesis's approach. However, upon examination, it was deemed unsuitable for assessing creativity within the organizations due to the failure to capture the nuances of actions.

3.1.3 Assumptions

The critical realist approach chosen is underpinned by three key assumptions, which will be explored below. Investigating these assumptions is vital as they will inform the findings and discussion.

One aspect is the acknowledgement that an objective reality exists (Sayer, 2004), which remains beyond complete human understanding, shaping behaviours within organisations. This reality also affects informal structures and social groupings within the SA provider. This perspective of ontological realism implies that while research may seek objectivity by examining participants' actions, it recognises inherent limitations (Bhaskar et al., 1998).

The next assumption is that critical realism includes epistemological relativism which states that knowledge is not absolute but rather context-dependent and subject to interpretation (Patomäki and Wight, 2000). For this thesis this perspective suggests that different individuals or groups may perceive and interpret reality differently based on their unique experiences, beliefs, and cultural backgrounds. As a result, there may be multiple valid

perspectives on a given issue, and knowledge claims are understood within the framework of their specific cultural and social contexts(Sayer, 2004). In the context of the SA provider, epistemological relativism implies that understanding of creativity and its manifestations may vary among different stakeholders, reflecting diverse viewpoints and interpretations. Therefore the research will outline in the limitations section the challenges this poses when only interviewing singular members of staff at each organisation. This will be explored in more detail in the next section.

A third assumption is that judgmental rationality, as advocated by critical realism, will form a vital part of the process, underscoring the importance of critically evaluating theories and evidence(Groff, 2004). While acknowledging the inherent limitations in human knowledge, this perspective emphasises the role of critical examination and comparison in advancing understanding. The research will adopt a critical approach, assuming that reasoned judgments can be made through careful analysis of available theories and empirical evidence. The literature review of the thesis will outline the key theories that will be used to underpin the research, which will allow for critically assessing diverse perspectives and identify the strengths and weaknesses of different experiences. This will lead to a more informed and nuanced conclusion about the nature of creativity within the SA provider. This emphasis on judgmental rationality underscores the pragmatic and evidence-based approach advocated by critical realism (Danermark et al., 2019), guiding research efforts towards greater clarity and insight into complex organisational phenomena.

Outlining these assumptions and applicability underpins the choice of critical realism for the thesis. This is because a critical realist approach often leads to an examination of deeper underlying mechanisms (Bhaskar et al., 2005)and structures that generate observable phenomena, acknowledging complexity, context, and the limitations of knowledge, while striving to provide informed and rational explanations (Sayer, 2004).

3.1.4 Epistemological Relativism

Epistemological relativism, which views knowledge as relative to various perspectives, contexts, and cultures(Luper, 2004), offers distinct advantages for understanding creativity in statutory advocacy. By recognising that different cultural and individual perspectives may offer valid yet diverse interpretations of reality, this philosophical approach promotes tolerance and encourages dialogue among various groups which is vital when working with providers.

Such open-mindedness can enhance cultural understanding and foster harmony within the sector, especially one that has paucity of literature currently. This approach encourages critical reflection of the researchers own assumptions, which may highlight how social and cultural factors shape knowledge. Embracing epistemological relativism leads to a more inclusive and nuanced approach to understanding creativity in advocacy (Baghramian and Coliva, 2019), recognising the varied ways it can manifest depending on different organisational cultures and contexts.

Some criticisms of this approach including the risk of devolving into radical scepticism, where all knowledge claims hold equal weight, potentially reducing the amount of meaningful knowledge gathered (Siegel, 1987). Despite this challenge, recognising the role of cultural and contextual influences on knowledge is essential while also striving for empirical validation and rational justification in this thesis.

Applying epistemological relativism to explore how SA providers utilise creativity offers insights into the current mechanism of organisational operation in the sector. It acknowledges the diversity of creative perceptions shaped by varying backgrounds and experiences within the advocacy sector. It provides a framework for understanding the contextual factors that affect creativity in advocacy, such as organisational structures and resource limitations. By integrating epistemological relativism, this research can develop a deeper, contextually informed understanding of how creativity is leveraged in statutory advocacy.

3.2 Research Methods

The Research Methods section of the methodology chapter delves into the specific approaches and techniques employed in this study. It comprehensively outlines the methodologies chosen, including their theoretical underpinnings and practical applications. This section aims to provide a clear understanding of how these methods facilitate the exploration of the research questions, ensuring a robust and credible research framework.

3.2.1 Participant Selection

The selection criteria for the research were designed to ensure that participating organizations shared certain similarities in their services. To achieve this, specific inclusion and exclusion criteria were developed and implemented during the participant selection process.

3.2.2 Inclusion Criteria

The organisational inclusion criteria ensured that the research was focused on providers of Statutory Advocacy in England, Scotland, Wales, and Northern Ireland.

These two organisational criteria were.

Provides Statutory Advocacy	The organisation had to provide at least 1 form of statutory advocacy. This is defined as “Advocacy Services that are fulfilling a legal duty and are funded by the government.”
England, Scotland, Wales, and Northern Ireland	Must be providing services on behalf of one of these governments

The participants had to be in a senior role within the organisation, ideally with strategic oversight of the statutory advocacy. The rationale was that the research will focus on building multiple case studies of how organisations currently use creativity when providing SA.

3.2.3 Exclusion Criteria

The exclusion criteria further refine the choice of organisations that could be approached for this research.

Other stakeholders	The research decided to ignore the other stakeholders including commissioners, service users and funders of SA.
Republic of Ireland and other countries	The differences in funding and legislative environment were the reason for excluding countries outside of the UK & Northern Ireland.
Non Statutory Advocacy Providers	The research excluded providers who offered non statutory only services such as drug and alcohol provision.

Beyond the organisational exclusions, the research also excluded participants that were not in a senior role or did not have an active role in providing statutory advocacy.

3.2.4 Sampling

For this study, a purposive sampling approach was utilised as the multiple case study approach required a set of organisations that had shared characteristics (Miles and Huberman, 1994). This meant that these characteristics had to be planned into the sampling technique (Punch, 2016). The purposive sampling technique ensured that that the providers invited to take part in the study could be included as they met the initial criteria (Robinson, 2014) study. The need for a degree of homogeneity amongst the case studies (Campbell et al., 2020), would allow for alignment with the study's goals and objectives,

By drawing from a list of organisations that had engaged in government tender processes (UK Government), the research likely included a diverse range of participants, reflecting varied capabilities and experiences in handling government contracts. This diversity was beneficial for the comprehensive analysis and reliability of the research outcomes, providing a broader insight into the sector's dynamics.

This resulted in 61 organisations that met the criteria.

Table 8 Statutory Advocacy Providers in Sample

Advocacy Alliance	Healthwatch Wakefield
Advocacy Highland	independent advocacy
Advocacy Matters	Independent Advocacy Perth & Kinross
Advocacy Support Cymru	Inspire Wellbeing
African Advocacy Foundation	Living Options Devon
ASA	Local Solutions
Asist	Ncompass
Barnet Mind	NYAS
BATIAS	Onside Independent Advocacy
BIAS - Borders Advocacy	Oxleas NHS Foundation Trust;
Bryson Care - Independent Advocacy	People First Advocacy Services
Central and North West London NHS Foundation Trust	Perth Kinross Independent Advocacy
Certas	Pohwer
Choices Advocacy	Rethink
Circles Network	Sefton Advocacy
Cloverleaf 2000	Solihull Action through Advocacy
Community Links	southern advocacy services
Coram	Speak Out Advocacy project
Craig-Milburn	Swan Advocacy
Darlington Association on Disability	Swindon Advocacy Movement
DIAS Dundee	Teeside Mind
Disability Action	The Advocacy People (SEAP)
Dumfries Galloway Advocacy	The Advocacy Project
EARS	Together
Embrace Wigan	Touchstone - leeds
Empowerment	Vocal Advocacy
Engaging Communities Solutions CIC	Voiceability
Forth Valley Advocacy	Who Cares Scotland
Gaddum	You First Advocacy
Hammersmith and Fulham (provided by Libra)	Your Voice Counts
Healthwatch Bucks	

3.2.5 Recruitment

Following the selection of the organisations, the initial contact strategy involved utilising LinkedIn. The primary individual to be approached was the CEO of each organisation. In instances where the CEO did not maintain a LinkedIn profile, a thorough investigation was conducted to ascertain the presence of other senior executives who were active on LinkedIn. This approach ensured that communication was established with key decision-makers within the organisation, facilitating a direct and efficient interaction channel for the study.

The use of LinkedIn facilitated the visibility of the potential participants work history and background to the researcher. The aim was to utilise this transparency to enhance the

response rate for the initial interviews, as potential participants could be verified that they meet the criteria and are relevant to the study. It also allowed the potential participant to see the background of the researcher, which could potentially increase response rate.

The CEO's or other relevant senior leaders in the organisation were contacted through LinkedIn messages to ask about whether they would like to take part in the research.

The outcome of this approach did not yield any actual results, leading to a shift in strategy where organisations were contacted directly. This contact was made through company emails, and whenever possible, through the direct emails of CEOs or other senior leadership team members. These email addresses were sourced from the organisational websites or from publicly published government tender contracts.

This revised approach resulted in 14 interviews being conducted for the research, encompassing a range of organisations from England, Scotland, Wales, and Northern Ireland. The split between the countries can be found below.

Table 9 Number of Providers per country

England	7
Wales	2
Scotland	4
N.I	1

3.3 Data Collection

The Data Collection section of this methodology chapter details the systematic approach undertaken to gather information relevant to the study. It outlines the specific strategies and tools used for data acquisition, emphasizing their alignment with the research objectives. This section also explains the rationale behind choosing these methods, ensuring transparency and rigor in the process of data collection.

3.3.1 Online Interviews

At a very early stage in the development of the research, it was decided to hold the interviews online via a digital video service. This was for a few key reasons including accessibility, geographic sampling, and data collection (Oliffe et al., 2021).

3.3.1.1 Accessibility

The decision to utilise online video interviews for this research was driven primarily by the need to ensure accessibility and inclusivity, allowing for the engagement of a diverse array of interviewees from various locations (Deakin and Wakefield, 2014). Following the COVID-19 pandemic (Van Zeeland et al., 2021), many organisations across the UK have integrated video conferencing into their daily operations, making tools like MS Teams a commonplace aspect of professional communication (Oliffe et al., 2021). This widespread adoption reduces barriers to participating in online interviews, as most individuals are now familiar with navigating these platforms (Saarijärvi and Bratt, 2021).

MS Teams was chosen due to its ease of use and robust digital security features, ensuring that both the research process and the data collected are protected. The platform is user-friendly, requiring minimal technical knowledge, which lowers the barrier to entry for participants who may not be tech-savvy (Thunberg and Arnell, 2022). Additionally, MS Teams facilitates the scheduling of interviews by allowing sessions to be arranged well in advance, thereby minimising potential timing conflicts related to travel or other commitments.

This approach not only streamlines the interview process but also enhances the overall efficiency of data collection. By using a platform that is both secure and familiar to most participants, the research benefits from increased participation rates and richer data quality (Wahl-Jorgensen, 2021). The use of MS Teams thus supports a more comprehensive and accessible research methodology, making it an invaluable tool for this thesis.

3.3.1.2 Geographic reach

Online interviews offer a significant advantage in widening the geographic scope of sampling for research purposes. By leveraging digital platforms like Microsoft Teams, the research can transcend geographical boundaries and engaging with SA providers located in diverse regions, both regionally and nationally. This expanded reach facilitates the inclusion of a more diverse and representative sample (Oliffe et al., 2021), enriching the depth and breadth of insights garnered from the study. This allowed providers from England, Scotland, Wales, and Northern Ireland to take part in the research.

Additionally, online interviews eliminated the logistical constraints associated with traditional face-to-face interviews, such as travel time and expenses, making participation more accessible to individuals residing in remote or hard-to-reach areas (Maldonado-Castellanos and Barrios, 2023). As a result, the research was able to access a broader pool of

potential participants, enhancing the diversity of perspectives and experiences represented in the study. This geographical expansion not only enriches the research findings but also contributes to a more comprehensive understanding of how creativity is used by SA providers in this research.

3.3.1.3 Easy Data Collection

MS Teams offers a streamlined approach to data collection during interviews, enhancing the efficiency and effectiveness of the research process. One key feature of online video conferencing platforms is its ability to record interviews (Oliffe et al., 2021). This functionality allowed the interviewer to capture every detail of the conversation without the need for manual note-taking or additional recording devices. As a result, the interviewer can devote full attention to the interviewee, fostering a more engaging and interactive dialogue. This is vital when conducting semi structured interviews, as the responses to questions can influence the next line of questioning. This focused engagement also allowed for building rapport and trust, which are vital for encouraging openness and candour in responses. This approach then allowed the interviewer to delve deeper into subjects, ask follow-up questions, and explore nuances in the interviewee's responses in real time, knowing that the details are accurately captured in the recording. Also the recorded data can be reviewed multiple times, ensuring thorough analysis, and helping to avoid misinterpretation or loss of crucial information.

At the end of the interview, the recordings would be automatically captured and stored via MS Teams. This allows for simplified data management and not only saves time during the data collection phase but also enhances the reliability and validity of the research by providing a verbatim account of the interviews.

3.3.2 Challenges for online interviews

Using online interviews for research can present several challenges that can affect the quality of data collected. Technical issues such as connection disruptions, poor audio or video quality, and software glitches can happen, potentially interrupting the flow of conversation and causing loss of valuable data. The online format can often limit the ability to observe non-verbal cues like body language and facial expressions, which are critical for fully understanding responses. This may lead to misinterpretations or an incomplete grasp of the interviewee's intent. This can also impact the rapport during an interview, which may impact on the levels of honesty of responses.

Utilising MS Teams might exclude individuals who lack access to necessary technology or are uncomfortable using digital tools, resulting in a sample bias that is not fully representative of the target population. Privacy and security concerns can also be an issue, as the recording must be kept in line with UCLAN research policies to ensure that data protection regulations are complied with to safeguard sensitive information. A final consideration is that the research will not be able to control the participant's environment, which can be filled with distractions and interruptions, including digital or physical interruptions (Maldonado-Castellanos and Barrios, 2023).

On balance the benefits outweigh the negatives associated with conducting online interviews via MS Teams, therefore the research chose this as the primary data collection method.

3.4 Pilot Interviews

The first two interviews were planned to be a pilot to test the initial set of questions and assess their feasibility (Leon et al., 2011). A set of semi structured questions were developed that maximised the areas to be covered during the interview. The preferences and circumstances of the pilot interviewees, as recommended by King and Horrocks (2010) and Hill et al. (2019), were considered, these are senior leaders in busy organisations so therefore limited time was an important consideration and a pilot approach could highlight areas of adjustment (Kim, 2011).

During the interviews, notes were taken to highlight key areas and identify follow-up questions. This notetaking was crucial in emphasizing important topics and guiding the direction of subsequent inquiries (Savenye and Robinson, 2013). It allowed the interviews to become more in-depth and responsive, adapting to the emerging themes and enhancing the data collection process.

Taking notes during the pilot interviews was pivotal for refining the questions in the semi-structured interviews for the rest of the study. This initial phase provided a practical understanding of how questions were interpreted and answered (Sampson, 2004), revealing areas for improvement, for example the pilot interviews highlighted that the number of questions that were prepared, far exceeded the time available.

Notes captured not just the responses, but also nuances like hesitation in answering the question or areas that would be emphasized, offering insights into the clarity and impact of each question. This feedback loop allowed a revision to take place after the pilot stage,

reducing and tailoring the questions, making them more effective in eliciting comprehensive and relevant information (Wray et al., 2017). It ensured that subsequent interviews were more focused and productive, facilitating a deeper exploration of the themes central to the study.

The pilot interviews also highlighted that a more fluid approach was required due to the participants having very different experiences and wanting to explore it during the study. This iterative process was essential in honing the interview guide to better suit the study's objectives (Sampson, 2004), ultimately enhancing the quality and reliability of the data collected.

3.4.1 Interviews

Interviews were conducted online using Teams, primarily considering factors such as geographical distance, time constraints, and compliance with GDPR regulations (Gray et al., 2020). This online approach, while limiting the ability to observe body language and nonverbal cues as Bryman (2016) points out, was chosen to enhance accessibility to a wider range of participants. The inherent limitations of not observing nonverbal communication were recognized, yet the importance of participant access was prioritized (Krouwel et al., 2019).

The interviews, conducted as video calls, aimed to maintain a semblance of face-to-face interaction (Irani, 2019). This method sought to balance the need for detailed qualitative data while adhering to logistical and ethical requirements. The approach was intended to unlock deeper insights, a process underscored by the research of Lincoln and Guba (1985), by allowing a comfortable and flexible environment for participants especially as they may be working from home.

3.4.2 Transcription

In this study, the interviews were conducted with SA providers to explore their utilisation of creativity in advocacy practices. As set out in the ethics application form, Microsoft Teams was employed as the primary platform for conducting these interviews, with its built-in transcription feature utilized to transcribe the interview recordings. This approach offered a convenient and efficient method for remotely conducting interviews while ensuring accurate documentation of the conversations (Wollin-Giering et al., 2023). By utilizing Teams for both interviews and transcription, this study aimed to gain insights into how statutory advocacy providers harness creativity within their advocacy efforts, while also acknowledging the role of technology in facilitating the research process.

3.4.2.1 Benefits

The researcher employed Microsoft Teams for interviews, which were subsequently transcribed by the software, offering several advantages that significantly enhanced the research process. Microsoft Teams provided a convenient platform for conducting interviews remotely, enabling participants to connect from any location with an internet connection. This removed the need for travel and was particularly beneficial for participants who were geographically dispersed.

The use of Teams also enhanced accessibility for individuals who faced mobility challenges or other constraints that made in-person interviews difficult. The platform's features, such as closed captioning, supported inclusivity by accommodating participants with disabilities.

In terms of efficiency, Microsoft Teams was equipped with tools for scheduling, file sharing, and real-time communication, which streamlined the interview process significantly for both interviewers and participants. The transcription feature of Teams offered a notable advantage by automatically transcribing the interview recordings, thereby saving considerable time that would otherwise have been spent on manual transcription (Oliver et al., 2005).

Although the transcription software did not always deliver perfect results, it generally provided a fairly accurate transcript of the interview proceedings, creating a good enough representation of the interviews (Bokhove and Downey, 2018). These transcripts were then reviewed and edited as necessary to ensure that crucial information and insights from the interview were accurately documented.

Furthermore, Teams facilitated collaboration among interviewers and researchers by enabling them to review and analyse interview transcripts together in real-time. This collaborative approach supported more effective data analysis and interpretation, helping the researchers to identify themes, patterns, and insights more efficiently.

Finally, Microsoft Teams included robust security features to protect sensitive interview data. With encryption, access controls, and compliance with data protection regulations, the platform ensured the confidentiality and integrity of the interview data throughout the transcription and analysis process (Ilag and Sabale, 2022).

Overall, the use of Microsoft Teams for interviews that were then transcribed by the software significantly improved the efficiency, accessibility, accuracy, and security of the interview process, contributing to more effective research outcomes.

3.4.2.2 Drawbacks

The researcher identified several limitations associated with using transcription software for interviews. Firstly, the quality of transcription was a significant concern. While transcription software automated the process, it produced transcripts of varying accuracy. Factors such as accents, background noise, and technical limitations impacted the quality, potentially leading to errors or misinterpretations in the recorded data. Additionally, there was a marked dependence on technology, which introduced the risk of technical issues such as compatibility problems, software glitches, or poor internet connections. These issues could disrupt the transcription process, causing delays and resulting in frustration.

Privacy concerns also arose from transcribing interviews electronically, particularly if sensitive or confidential information was discussed. Despite the implementation of security measures, there remained a risk of unauthorized access or data breaches, especially in the absence of robust security protocols (Gauthier and Husain, 2021).

Another issue was the loss of context. Transcription software often failed to capture the full context of conversations, including non-verbal cues like body language and tone of voice. This limitation could reduce the richness and depth of the transcribed data, making it harder to accurately interpret participants' responses. This could be overcome by reviewing the recorded video alongside the transcription, so this could be considered a small impact on the platform.

3.4.3 Alternatives

The alternative to automated transcription is to conduct manual transcription or outsource to transcription services, both of which offered potential advantages they over MS Teams offer, particularly in terms of accuracy and flexibility.

Manual transcription in which the researcher would convert the recordings into a text document offered the potential to improve on the accuracy on the output, this can be classed as local manual transcription (Wollin-Giering et al., 2023). A human can often capture subtle nuances in speech such as accents, dialects, and even non-verbal cues, that an automated transcription may miss. This is also key when dealing with technical terms, related to the research project. However, manual transcription has its challenges; it can be both time-consuming and costly, particularly with lengthy or complex recordings. The research included over 14 hours of recordings to transcribe, which may take up to 56 hours in total to complete (Poland, 2003) The need for skilled transcribers, proficient in language

comprehension and fast typing, may also limit the availability of qualified professionals, potentially extending project timelines.

Outsourcing transcription services presents another alternative, where the work can be sent to external professionals or freelancers to handle the transcription (Oliver et al., 2005). This option may result in high-quality transcripts, as the contracted transcriptionists are typically well-trained and experienced in producing accurate transcriptions. This approach may save considerable time and effort, as it allows the researcher to focus on other aspects of their research while the transcription tasks are handled externally (Wollin-Giering et al., 2023). Outsourcing provides scalability, allowing researchers to adjust the volume of transcription work according to their project's needs. However, it can incur additional costs, depending on the pricing model (e.g., per minute of audio or per word). Additionally, finding reliable transcription providers and managing the transcription process effectively can pose significant challenges.

Both manual transcription and outsourcing are considered in response to limitations found in automatic transcription tools like Microsoft Teams, which, while efficient, may struggle with accuracy when dealing with complex audio inputs. These human-powered solutions enhance the reliability of the data captured in qualitative research, providing a more nuanced and contextually rich transcription.

3.5 Data Analysis

The data analysis phase of this doctoral research project was pivotal in fulfilling the study's objectives and answering the research questions posed. This chapter outlined the methodological approach employed to analyse the collected data and elucidated the rationale behind the chosen analytical methods. Data analysis is key to this thesis as it allows extraction of meaningful insights, patterns, and relationships from the data collected. By examining the data through a systematic and rigorous process, the research uncovered key findings that contributed to the knowledge in SA sector especially around the use of creativity by the providers.

This section will set out how the thematic analysis was completed with a two stage approach utilising Artificial Intelligence and traditional data analysis technique. Through transparent and methodologically sound data analysis procedures, the research aims to produce robust and reliable conclusions in the SA sector.

3.5.1 Thematic Analysis

Thematic data analysis is a widely used method in qualitative research for identifying, analysing, and reporting patterns, themes, and meanings within a dataset (Braun and Clarke, 2006). This approach involved systematically organising and interpreting qualitative data to uncover recurring themes and insights that emerged from the data. Thematic analysis was often applied across various fields, including social sciences, psychology, health sciences, education, and business, to explore complex phenomena and understand the experiences, perspectives, and behaviours of individuals and groups (Bell, 2019). Through a rigorous and iterative process of coding, categorising, and interpreting data, thematic analysis enabled the researcher to generate rich and nuanced insights into the underlying themes and patterns that characterised the dataset (Bryman, 2016). By providing a systematic and transparent framework for qualitative data analysis, thematic analysis contributed to the development of evidence-based theories, concepts, and interventions, thereby enhancing the understanding of the social world, and informing practice and policy decisions.

3.5.1.1 Strengths of thematic analysis

Thematic analysis is a highly flexible tool in qualitative research, adaptable to a variety of research questions and contexts. This flexibility is one of its primary strengths, as it is not bound to any specific theoretical framework or methodology. Researchers can tailor the process to suit different types of data, whether they are derived from interviews, focus groups, observations, or textual documents. This versatility ensures that thematic analysis can be applied effectively across various studies, making it a valuable method in the diverse field of social sciences.

Another significant advantage of thematic analysis is its accessibility. It is considered one of the more straightforward methods for analysing qualitative data, which does not necessitate the use of sophisticated software or advanced statistical skills. This makes thematic analysis particularly appealing to researchers who may not have extensive experience in qualitative methodologies or those from disciplines where qualitative research is a newer practice. Its user-friendly nature allows for wider adoption and facilitates a deeper understanding of the data, regardless of the researcher's prior experience.

Additionally, thematic analysis is extremely useful for making comparisons across different case studies or data sources. It enables researchers to identify and analyse common themes that emerge within and across diverse datasets, providing a robust basis for comparative

analysis. This aspect of thematic analysis is particularly beneficial in studies aiming to understand patterns or variations in phenomena across different groups or settings. By drawing out these comparative insights, thematic analysis helps researchers build a more comprehensive understanding of the subjects under study.

3.5.1.2 Weaknesses of thematic analysis

One significant weakness of thematic analysis is the level of subjectivity involved in identifying themes. The process of coding data and defining themes can be highly influenced by the researcher's personal perspectives, biases, and interpretations. This inherent subjectivity can affect the consistency and replicability of research findings. Different researchers might interpret the same data in various ways, which could lead to different conclusions being drawn from identical datasets. Ensuring objectivity in thematic analysis thus requires careful attention to the researcher's role and biases, which can be challenging to manage effectively.

Another potential drawback of thematic analysis is the risk of oversimplification. In the effort to distil complex data into identifiable themes, important nuances and subtleties may be overlooked or understated. This can result in broader themes that fail to capture the depth and diversity of the data, thereby losing critical insights. Researchers might inadvertently prioritize themes that align with their expectations or hypotheses, thereby neglecting less obvious but equally important patterns. This simplification can diminish the richness of the data and limit the depth of understanding that thematic analysis strives to achieve.

Lastly, the flexibility of thematic analysis, while a strength, can also lead to concerns about reliability and validity. The absence of a standardized method for theme development means that the analytic process can vary significantly between studies, challenging the assessment of the quality and rigor of the analysis. Without consistent procedures, it becomes difficult to ensure that the analysis is replicable and robust. To address these issues, researchers must be meticulous in documenting their coding and theme development processes and strive for transparency in their methodological decisions. This approach can help enhance the reliability and validity of the findings and provide clearer guidance for other researchers attempting to replicate the study.

3.5.2 Alternative techniques

The data from the interviews could have been analysed using content or discourse approaches.

Content analysis is a method that systematically evaluates the presence of certain words, themes, or concepts within qualitative data (Bell, 2019). It can be employed to quantify and analyse the frequency, patterns, and meanings of such elements in a dataset, making it suitable for studies that aim to objectively evaluate trends or patterns within textual information (Bryman, 2016). This method is particularly beneficial for bridging qualitative and quantitative approaches, as it allows for a systematic classification of data and can involve statistical analysis. This could be seen as offering a more robust output to the thesis due to the introduction of a quantitative method. The key weakness is that it tends to focus more on the quantity and less on the quality of information, potentially overlooking the deeper, more nuanced aspects of textual data. This can lead to a superficial understanding of the content without fully capturing the underlying contexts or subtleties expressed by the participants. In a sector such as Social Care, where every case is heterogeneous, this could be viewed as too reductive and restrict the exploration of unforeseen themes that can emerge from the data.

An alternative approach to reviewing the data is to use discourse analysis techniques. This is a qualitative research method that examines the ways language is used in texts and spoken interactions to understand how it influences and is influenced by social and cultural contexts (Bryman, 2016, Van Dijk, 2009). This approach can be effective when exploring the construction of identities and social relationships through language, as well as how power dynamics are manifested and perpetuated. It also can reveal the underlying assumptions, values, and power structures that are embedded in communication, providing insights that are often not accessible through more traditional methods (Gill, 2000). The challenge for this research is that there is a high level of subjective interpretation required, which can lead to accusations of bias or inconsistency in analytical conclusions. The rationale for using multiple case study methodology was due to the paucity of literature in the area, so relying on the researcher to interpret the discourse with limited exposure to the field may yield weaker results.

Due to the nature of the study, it was decided that thematic analysis is a preferred method for data analysis.

3.5.3 Thematic Analysis Tools

There are many different tools that allow researchers to conduct thematic analysis on qualitative data. For this research NVivo and Atlas.ti were chosen as the preferred tools.

3.5.3.1 Atlas.ti

Utilising AI offered the opportunity to analyse the data from a different perspective. The tool chosen was Atlas.ti which was able to automate certain aspects of the analysis process, such as data coding, categorization, and pattern recognition (Hwang, 2008). By leveraging machine learning algorithms, Atlas.ti can rapidly process large volumes of qualitative data and identify recurring themes, patterns, and relationships that may not be immediately apparent to the researcher (Smit, 2002). This approach may offer a mechanism to save time and effort, although with the technology in its infancy it was felt that it shouldn't be the primary data analysis tool in the study.

The tool easily coded the interviews in under 5 minutes each, constructing word clouds and other visual representations of the data. The speed of the system offers a great advantage, although challenges were two folds. Firstly, the number of codes generated were over 1000 for each interview, which offered a level of granularity to the data analysis but needed refining for the thematic approach. Secondly any jargon or industry specific words that may be important were sometimes missed, meaning that the outputs could be lacking some vital knowledge.

The AI tool offered a mechanism to speed up data analysis, although it required post processing analysis to understand the limitations of the approach.

3.5.3.2 NVivo

The initial coding of the research data was conducted using Atlas.ti, with the analysis later expanded using NVivo to refine the numerous codes into a focused set of relevant themes. Atlas.ti provided a foundation for the coding process by leveraging its AI capabilities to identify preliminary patterns and insights within the data. Building on this, NVivo, a powerful qualitative analysis tool, was utilised to manage and organise the data further (Dhakal, 2022). NVivo's comprehensive features allowed for a more detailed and systematic review of the initial codes, facilitating the identification of themes.

After the transcripts were initially coded in Atlas.ti, they were uploaded into NVivo for a second stage of analysis. In NVivo, the researcher manually reviewed and recoded all 14 interviews, ensuring consistency and analytical depth. This dual-software approach added rigour to the study by combining AI-driven insights with a manual coding process. NVivo's visualisation tools, such as data connection maps and hierarchies, were instrumental in

simplifying the analysis of 14 hours of interviews, making the data more interpretable and actionable.

The themes generated in NVivo were grouped into broader categories that underpinned the research findings. These themes were prioritised based on the frequency of their codes, creating a hierarchical structure that highlighted key insights. Recognising the potential for bias and the researcher's limited experience in this type of analysis, the dual approach—first using AI coding in Atlas.ti and then manual refinement in NVivo—ensured a more robust and comprehensive examination of the data, reducing the risk of overlooking critical insights.

The outputs of Atlas.ti were then combined with NVivo results to create a stronger set of hierarchical themes from the research, which were then used for the discussion section of the thesis.

3.5.4 Conclusion

The methodology chapter has outlined a systematic approach for conducting the primary data collection for this study. It has defined the research design, data collection procedures, and analytical techniques, providing a clear and transparent framework for carrying out the research. The choice of thematic analysis as the primary methodological strategy facilitates a thorough exploration of the research phenomena in the SA sector, enabling the identification of key themes and patterns within the dataset. The findings from this data will be discussed in detail in the subsequent chapter.

Chapter 4: FINDINGS

This chapter presents the findings arising from multiple case study research encompassing advocacy providers located in Scotland, England, Wales, and Northern Ireland. The methodology adopted for this study addresses both the benefits and challenges associated with engaging a diverse array of providers, each characterized by unique and distinctive operational frameworks including relevant legislation.

Within the following sections, the chapter delineates the outcomes derived from a qualitative thematic analysis of the 14 interviews conducted, illuminating the commonalities and distinctions unearthed through this analytical process. The socioeconomic and geographic diversity inherent to the research context warrants thorough examination, and as such, while this chapter facilitates comparisons, it is also cognizant of the limitations surrounding the applicability of certain approaches across the breadth of advocacy providers.

This research utilizes a semantic inductive approach, analysing qualitative data to identify underlying themes. By adopting an inductive approach nuanced meanings emerge naturally through the research. This is key when operating in a research area that has a paucity of data. By adopting a thematic analysis methodology, it allows the researcher the key benefit of reviewing a rich source of data in a flexible approach (Braun and Clarke, 2006).

The selection of organisations featured in this study spans four distinct regions within the United Kingdom, albeit not distributed uniformly across these areas. The subsequent table provides a detailed breakdown of the number of interviews conducted within organisations situated in each respective region.

The following table offers a comprehensive breakdown of the number of interviews conducted within organisations located in each respective country:

Table 10 Country breakdown of participants

Country	No. Int	%
England	7	50%
Scotland	4	29%
Wales	2	14%
Northern Ireland	1	7%
	14	100%

This tabulation provides a clear understanding of the distribution of interviews across different geographical regions. The research aimed to engage SA providers across the UK, regardless of size, provided they met the participation requirements. Currently, there are three major providers with multiple statutory advocacy contracts, none of which participated in this research. Two declined to participate, and the third did not respond. This limitation may overlook insights from larger groups, potentially affecting the study's findings and the replication of its outputs, as they may not apply to large SA providers in the sector.

To maintain consistency across the findings, each interview was anonymized in accordance with the University of Central Lancashire ethical approval guidelines. As a result, unique codes were assigned to each interviewee to ensure confidentiality while analysing the data. To preserve the anonymity of all involved parties, specific locations, regions, or organisations have been anonymized using letters where relevant.

The data obtained from the interviews underwent analysis using Atlas.ti, serving as the initial stage for coding in the research process. Following an extensive review of the initial dataset, which comprised over 600 codes, a thematic review was conducted. This involved grouping similar codes and subsequently identifying and developing relevant themes. The resultant themes were categorized into two distinct groups: those demonstrating similarities across multiple interviews, termed "Shared Themes," and those present in only one or two interviews, categorized as "Differences in Themes."

4.1 Creativity and Ideas

This study delves into how organisations providing statutory advocacy services, alongside other functions, have harnessed creativity to foster idea generation and in turn innovation. Despite the presence of legislation outlining minimum legal requirements for statutory advocacy services, the scope for innovation in this realm is limited.

Interviewees were questioned about the challenges their organisations encountered and the creative strategies they employed in response. This chapter focuses on the outcomes of these endeavours, shedding light on the shared and different outcomes of creativity within the organisations.

Statutory advocacy services are bound by legal frameworks that prescribe specific standards and procedures, leaving little room for innovative practices. However, organisations have grappled with various challenges, prompting them to devise inventive solutions. These challenges could range from resource constraints and operational inefficiencies to evolving user needs and external pressures.

The responses provided by interviewees reflect a diverse array of creative approaches adopted by organisations to navigate these challenges. Some organisations may have implemented unconventional methods to enhance service delivery, such as leveraging technology to streamline administrative processes or developing novel advocacy models tailored to specific user demographics. Despite the constraints posed by statutory requirements, organisations have demonstrated resilience and adaptability by fostering a culture of innovation. This has involved fostering an environment where new ideas are encouraged, and experimentation is embraced. Additionally, collaboration and knowledge-sharing among advocacy providers have facilitated the exchange of innovative practices and solutions.

This chapter explores the multifaceted nature of creativity within the context of statutory advocacy services, examining both the commonalities and distinctions in the creative responses employed by organisations. By identifying and analysing these creative endeavours, we can gain valuable insights into the adaptive capacity and problem-solving abilities of advocacy providers in addressing complex challenges within their operational environments.

4.1.1 Shared Creative responses.

Across the diverse case studies, common themes in creative strategies emerged, supported by relevant interview quotes. This section delves into these themes, shedding light on creative strategies within organisations.

One overarching theme consistently found was a deep commitment to innovative solutions, particularly in response to the post-COVID era's cost of living challenges and the evolving

landscape of the advocacy sector. This central theme can be further divided into three key sub-themes.

The first sub-theme revolves around adaptability in the structure and culture of the organisation, encompassing flexibility in staff locations and working hours. Organisations demonstrated a strong commitment to addressing these issues through innovative organisational solutions. Additionally, ongoing training and development programs played a vital role in enhancing the capabilities of both staff and volunteers, with creative teaching methods optimizing the sector's response.

The second theme, evident in nearly all the interviews conducted as part of the research, pertained to various organisational aspects. Discussions often revolved around organisational culture, management styles, vision, and the distinct focus of advocacy providers. These dimensions collectively emphasized the significance of organisational factors in the implementation of creative strategies.

Lastly, a prominent commonality in the research was the integration and use of technology. This theme was consistently discussed in the context of the evolving advocacy landscape and the challenges faced by providers. The various aspects of technology utilization will be explored in more detail in the following sections. In the upcoming sections, the analysis of these common themes will be provided, supported by empirical evidence from the extensive research conducted.

The word cloud presented below illustrates the frequency of key concepts derived from all the interviews conducted.

Table 11 provides an overview of the frequency with which key themes emerged across the 14 research interviews. This quantitative representation highlights the prominence of specific themes, offering insight into their relative importance within the dataset. This structured approach ensures clarity and analytical rigour in presenting the findings.

Key Theme	No of times
people	739
advocacy	478
service	323
staff	214
time	213
organisation	212
contract	198
work	197
team	185
year	181

Table 11 Count of key theme words

		Thematic Codes										
Interview Reference		people	think	advocacy	work	time	need	staff	health	support	service	
	E1		101	70	42	32	21	19	15	11	10	8
			3.8%	2.6%	1.6%	1.2%	0.8%	0.7%	0.6%	0.4%	0.4%	0.3%
	E2		26	20	32	46	12	9	11	5	11	7
			1.4%	1.1%	1.8%	2.5%	0.7%	0.5%	0.6%	0.3%	0.6%	0.4%
	W3		85	53	43	44	32	25	6	24	24	16
			2.9%	1.8%	1.5%	1.5%	1.1%	0.9%	0.2%	0.8%	0.8%	0.5%
	E4		38	46	65	32	20	22	3	6	10	22
			1.7%	2.1%	2.9%	1.4%	0.9%	1.0%	0.1%	0.3%	0.5%	1.0%
	E5		34	29	6	29	10	4	14	7	8	3
			3.2%	2.7%	0.6%	2.7%	0.9%	0.4%	1.3%	0.7%	0.7%	0.3%
	E6		19	27	34	23	11	17	6	13	12	17
			1.3%	1.9%	2.3%	1.6%	0.8%	1.2%	0.4%	0.9%	0.8%	1.2%
	S7		43	51	24	14	14	8	18	19	18	17
			2.3%	2.7%	1.3%	0.7%	0.7%	0.4%	0.9%	1.0%	0.9%	0.9%
	S8		46	69	32	20	24	14	52	16	18	22
		1.9%	2.8%	1.3%	0.8%	1.0%	0.6%	2.1%	0.7%	0.7%	0.9%	
E9		25	72	37	18	14	8	6	4	12	24	
		1.6%	4.7%	2.4%	1.2%	0.9%	0.5%	0.4%	0.3%	0.8%	1.6%	
W10		47	46	37	17	16	21	22	28	14	17	
		1.7%	1.7%	1.3%	0.6%	0.6%	0.8%	0.8%	1.0%	0.5%	0.6%	
E11		41	48	48	20	12	11	12	3	6	5	
		2.6%	3.0%	3.0%	1.2%	0.7%	0.7%	0.7%	0.2%	0.4%	0.3%	
S12		81	71	49	20	16	10	24	8	28	0	
		3.8%	3.3%	2.3%	0.9%	0.7%	0.5%	1.1%	0.4%	1.3%	0.0%	
S13		38	10	24	19	22	38	19	9	7	12	
		2.7%	0.7%	1.7%	1.4%	1.6%	2.7%	1.4%	0.6%	0.5%	0.9%	
NI 14		103	25	47	26	15	15	10	49	5	10	
		3.7%	0.9%	1.7%	0.9%	0.5%	0.5%	0.4%	1.8%	0.2%	0.4%	
Total		727	637	520	360	239	221	218	202	183	180	
		2.5%	2.2%	1.8%	1.3%	0.8%	0.8%	0.8%	0.7%	0.6%	0.6%	

Frequency of the codes applied
% of total interview words from transcript

Table 12- Quantitative analysis

The subsequent sections will delve into these key shared themes in further detail.

4.1.2 Staff

A prevalent theme emerging from interviews conducted across various advocacy organisations is the imperative of being responsive and creative in the management of staff within the organisational framework. Given the pivotal role of advocates in delivering advocacy services and their direct interactions with service users, it is evident that individuals constitute a crucial component of organisational development in this sector.

“For the good of the organisation, the good of the staff, the good of the people we support, innovation is critical.” (Interview 1, 2023).

Advocacy cases often present challenging and intricate situations, particularly when dealing with distressed service users and engaging in difficult conversations. One reoccurring observation from these interviews is the generally low compensation provided to advocates.

“So it is almost it is a passion approach rather than in it for the money type thing, because it does not it does not really pay well”(Interview 5, 2023),

Although this is not universal –

“We pay our team really well”(Interview 14, 2024).

This economic reality necessitates the exploration of alternative strategies for staff recruitment, retention, and motivation.

Furthermore, the role of advocates is characterised by an inherent power imbalance, as they represent the voice of service users in interactions with highly qualified and esteemed individuals such as surgeons, financial decision-makers, and other high-status professionals

“You know, the vicarious trauma that they face the fact that they're on, you know, a little over grand, and they're expected to challenge consulted psychiatrists that are on grand a day (Interview 5, 2023).

In recognition of this dynamic, interviewees emphasised the paramount importance of equipping advocates with the requisite skills, knowledge, and behaviours to effectively

navigate these interactions. Enhancing the efficacy and efficiency of advocates in their role is acknowledged as a top priority within advocacy organisations.

The research highlights the critical nature of responsive and creative staff management in advocacy organisations. The findings around these key areas will be reported below.

4.1.3 Flexible working locations

The nature of advocacy work imposes unique demands on organisations, requiring staff members to frequently traverse considerable distances to engage with their user base. These geographical challenges often entail covering expansive areas where users are dispersed across wide territories. It was a drain on resources for the organisations as these couldn't be invoiced and reduced the effective case load an advocate could manage.

“And that would be quite that would help in kind of on on you know well on an ongoing basis, but one of the biggest challenges is that the hourly rate is not fit for purpose and you can't charge, you can't log your travel time.”(Interview 14, 2024)

Historically, prior to the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic, it was commonplace for most of these organisations to maintain fixed office spaces, from which their staff members diligently carried out their daily operations.

“We were based in in one office in one area of Edinburgh” (Interview 13, 2024)

However, the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic and the ensuing lockdowns prompted a mixed response within the advocacy sector. As the world grappled with the pandemic's unprecedented challenges, organisations were compelled to adapt swiftly to ensure the continuity of their essential services. While certain aspects of their work seamlessly transitioned to online platforms, certain areas, due to their classification as key workers, received exemptions from the lockdown measures and continued to operate in person. Significantly, the impact of COVID-19 and the associated public health rules varied markedly across regions, necessitating that each organisation formulate its own adaptive strategies to navigate the evolving circumstances.

“Because I think the other thing about the post COVID world is that although we've moved back to being partly in the office, we operate a hybrid model.” (Interview 11, 2023)

“So then when we came out of lockdown, we actually did not have an office.”(Interview 13, 2024)

After the peak of the pandemic, a substantial number of these advocacy organisations embarked on a comprehensive review of their operational locations, including their physical office spaces. The primary aim of this review process was to redefine and optimize their working paradigms considering the lessons learned during the crisis. This introspective examination yielded a significant transformation in the work arrangements offered to their staff members.

“So we realized actually a lot of advocacy time was being taken upon that on things like that and then there was no advocate back in the office, for instance.” (Interview 3, 2023)

One of the key changes introduced was the concept of hybrid working, wherein trained advocates were afforded the opportunity to maintain a physical presence in the office during the workweek. Organisations felt they needed to identify creative ways to address this problem.

“Just kind of using our time more efficiently, not travel time. All that kind of thing.”(Interview 4, 2023)

“And they do some homeworking and, but they also appreciate the opportunity to come in and work together in the office.”(Interview 9, 2023)

This arrangement allowed them to effectively handle calls into the service while still being able to engage in face-to-face interactions with colleagues. The hybrid model not only ensured the efficient delivery of services but also fostered vital interpersonal connections among team members, mitigating the potential isolation that can be associated with remote work.

“Being more flexible in terms of working, you know, hybrid working became a thing we we caused the office at hours notice, you know wouldn't be.”(Interview 7, 2023)

“We also are not predominantly office based, although we everyone has an office day or duty day. We encourage people to be asked in the community as much as possible. But this level of flexibility is that there is a hope work from home offer as well.”(Interview 6, 2023)

“Actually, you know, we've had people who've been suicidal and everything else, and the advocacy cases or challenging, demanding, draining in another sense, if you're doing that constantly at home, there is not actually a break from it, that it is only that was, you know, individuals well, as when they come into the office and there's once, twice a week or whatever, they do bounce off one another, do not they?”(Interview 9, 2023)

In addition to hybrid work arrangements, all the organisations within the advocacy sector embraced the concept of remote work, enabling their staff members to work from the comfort of their homes for a substantial portion of their schedules.

“They've been recruited either during or post pandemic, and you know they've only ever known remote working, but there's still a handful of us oldies left that remembers when we all sat in an office.”(Interview 10, 2023)

“We have offices everywhere, but most people are home based and out in the field.”(Interview 14, 2024)

This strategic shift aligned closely with the overarching goal of optimizing travel time for staff, thereby minimizing the need for them to commute to a fixed location at the beginning and end of each workday. Such a change in work arrangements was viewed to enhance overall productivity, build trust among staff members, and facilitate a more adaptable work ethos.

“We still got an office, but what we realized was that we were far more productive actually working from home because we're covering the whole of North Wales and north.” (Interview 10, 2023)

Furthermore, the newfound location flexibility extended to employees residing abroad, who were enabled to retain their roles within the organisations while contributing remotely. This innovative approach not only retained valuable talent but also diversified the perspectives and experiences within these organisations. Moreover, the organisations extended their

recruitment reach to encompass prospective staff members further afield including Europe, further diversifying their workforce, and tapping into a broader talent pool.

“So we've got two NHS complaints contracts and they're both virtual... lives in the south of Spain and in Finland” (Interview 2, 2023)

In the subsequent sections, these profound shifts in organisational location strategies and work arrangements will be explored in greater detail. The implications and outcomes of these changes within the advocacy sector, along with the broader societal impacts, will be comprehensively examined.

4.1.4 Flexible Time

A recurrent theme that surfaced within the research conducted across various advocacy organisations revolved around the empowerment of staff members to exercise flexibility not only in terms of their work locations but also their working hours. This theme encapsulates a multifaceted approach to fostering a conducive work environment that accommodates the diverse needs of staff members, while simultaneously addressing the demands of their professional roles.

“I'm happy to be flexible around. Start finish times, and that's what that works quite well as well for people to use a service, because not everyone is there. So, we can be flexible in that way. So it is a bit of a win win” (Interview 6, 2023)

Central to this theme was the recognition of the intricate balance required by staff members between their professional responsibilities and personal life commitments. It was observed that factors such as medical appointments, the need to collect children from school, and other life administrative tasks assumed significant importance in the daily lives of staff.

“The other day he said I'm gonna if it is alright with you I've got to take a couple of hours out. I'm having a really rough time it is the anniversary of my overdose and stuff like that. I'm like, sure, it is fine. Just go. X will say I've got to go pick the kids up. Okay, fine, see you in a bit. Do you know what I mean? So we appreciate the fact that everyone has a life outside of work and the culture is very much like that.” (Interview 2, 2023)

As such, organisations acknowledged the pivotal role played by flexible working hours in alleviating the challenges associated with managing these multifarious commitments within the confines of the working week.

Most organisations featured in the study adopted a flexible approach to working hours, permitting staff members to exercise discretion in choosing their work hours throughout the week. While a semblance of core hours existed in many cases, typically designated for activities involving direct interaction with service users, tasks such as administrative work or the documentation of case notes were considered non-time critical. Consequently, staff members were afforded the autonomy to schedule these activities at times that best suited their individual circumstances.

“We work very closely as the team in the way. We're very flexible. My approach is family first work second, but do not let the clash.”(Interview 6, 2023)

Time management, integral to the broader theme of flexibility, was identified as a cornerstone of trust-building within organisations. It was acknowledged that the autonomy granted to staff members in managing their work hours instilled a sense of responsibility and trust, serving as a testament to the organisation's faith in their capacity to meet their professional obligations. Additionally, this approach was perceived as a potent tool for recruitment and staff retention, as it underscored the organisation's commitment to facilitating a harmonious work-life equilibrium.

“But again, the way that we have a very low attrition rate. Our attrition rate is about 5 % turnover of staff because we treat them well, we train them well and offer opportunities such as being flexible with time.”(Interview 2, 2023)

“Because I've just been recruiting new staff and I've had a bit of a gap. Advocacy is a passion project so we need to use things like flexi time to make the job attractive, no one is getting rich!”(Interview 5, 2023)

It is worth noting that the job roles within advocacy organisations could be inherently stressful, often involving complex and emotionally taxing cases. In this context, the latitude offered by personalized diary management played a vital role in promoting staff well-being. Staff members could take much-needed breaks or allocate time to relax and recharge when dealing with particularly challenging cases, thus mitigating the adverse effects of prolonged stress and burnout.

I know there's a lot of trust that goes into to how we work. But obviously we've got the guidelines there and obviously, that's monitored through supervision. That's done every to weeks. That's a regular thing in the diary. (Interview 6, 2023)

“We have a policy of coffee and cake to counselling. So if you've had a rough day, we will send you a cake from a company called Sponge. They're amazing and I just like saying the word. But we also provide everyone with Bennington health care and we also have counselling, so no questions asked. If you need counselling, you receive counselling and we pay for it.”(Interview 2, 2023)

“It can be quite lonely, especially now everybody's working from home. We speak to staff all day, but they do not speak to each other. They speak to us, but we could be on, we could be on a call practically every 20 minutes so we end up then having black humour. Please do not get me wrong, it is not discriminative or anything like that, but we'll end up having that black humour or we'll go to the office and we'll have a tea party.”(Interview 10, 2023)

In summary, the theme of staff empowerment through flexible time and location management emerges as a salient feature within advocacy organisations. It encapsulates a comprehensive strategy aimed at balancing the demands of professional roles with the multifarious commitments of personal life, while also fostering trust, enhancing recruitment prospects, and bolstering staff well-being in the challenging world of advocacy.

4.1.5 Training and development

Within the realm of statutory advocacy, certain roles in some countries necessitate formal training, such as those associated with Independent Mental Capacity Advocates (IMCAs) and Independent Mental Health Advocates (IMHAs). Other countries do not have such strict training regimes, although it is widely acknowledged that advocacy is a skilled role.

“We trained everybody. Everyone was on point.”(Interview 2, 2023)

“When it is the legislation, is very clear about what it has to do, and and you have to be qualified” (Interview 8, 2023)

This training creates a point of commonality among the various organisations operating within this sector. However, beyond the realm of mandatory training, the prevailing ethos among these organisations is a profound commitment to the ongoing professional development of their staff. It is seen as a mechanism for recruitment and retention of advocates.

“My main issue at the moment for staff will be staff development and because they've stuck by us through a lot and it is a hard job for them to do so and really like to be able to, we can never really give them the pay rise that they deserve, you know, because we never get an interest in funding.” (Interview 13, 2024)

This commitment underscores the sector's evolution away from its volunteer-driven, unqualified roots toward a more professionalized and skilled workforce.

In the context of Wales, advocacy service providers have established collaborative mechanisms to share training and development programs across different regions. This collaborative approach not only allows staff members from one organisation to access training opportunities provided by another but also serves to reduce the cost per participant for each program. Furthermore, it mitigates the risk of duplication, ensuring that resources are optimally utilized in the pursuit of staff development initiatives.

“So we've got a really good, combined training network type thing going on in Wales. So, for instance, next week, delivering a piece of training about going back to the basics of the advocacy charter with another one of the chief officers and advocates from another statutory org.”(Interview 3, 2023)

“We've done a lot of where we offer each other each other's training. We have been involved in both drawing in hope into some of our training so that they can project that out across Wales and say look we are delivering this training, and it is open to anyone from partners.”(Interview 10, 2023)

In Scotland, the Scottish Independent Advocacy Alliance (SIAA) plays a pivotal role in the development and delivery of training programs. Collaborating with its member organisations, the SIAA offers a diverse range of development opportunities that cater to the multifaceted requirements of advocacy professionals within the region. This collaborative effort not only bolsters the accessibility of training but also ensures that it aligns with the unique demands of the Scottish context.

“We're founding members of the Scottish Independent Advocacy Alliance. It offers training and a support network, I am on the board.” (Interview 8, 2023)

“You know, we are members of the Scottish Independent Advocacy Alliance. We like to get involved in their training and development opportunities, it is good for the staff.” (Interview 7, 2023)

“It is a couple of hours to get to Edinburgh, Glasgow and so historically when they did training things it was often in person and organisations like ourselves probably wouldn't have bothered going. But again, COVID kind of allowed that online platform and they are developing the training arm of the alliance.” (Interview 12, 2023)

In certain instances, organisations take their commitment to staff development a step further by offering accredited training. This accreditation can be achieved through the development of in-house qualifications or through partnerships with universities offering accredited courses. These accredited training programs not only elevate the skill sets of staff members but also confer formal recognition of their expertise, enhancing their professional standing within the sector.

“I wrote an RPR qualification by the way because I'm qualified to do that. So I wrote it and it was with NCFE. So we were doing that. I'm really hot on training and development. I used to lecture at the University of Surrey as well. And I've got my set ed and all of those kinds of things. So I'm kind of a bit niche myself. So I can write qualifications, training, and stuff like that, get it all CPD accredited and so on.”(Interview 2, 2023)

“As I was saying in accredited qualification, that Professional Practice award, which we and with put staff through after the been here for months, I think I think the minimum experience is 6 months and then they can start working through that.”(Interview 7, 2023)

For organisations involved in volunteer-led advocacy initiatives in the community or similar projects, training and development assume a dual role. Firstly, it serves as a mechanism to enhance the value that volunteers bring to the communities they serve. This equips volunteers with the knowledge and skills required to make a meaningful impact on behalf of the people they advocate for. Secondly, it empowers volunteers by offering opportunities to develop their skills and expertise, potentially paving the way for their transition into paid advocacy roles as they accumulate experience and proficiency in the field.

“Now we need to include a level of volunteers in our tenders to win the contract, well we have had to offer training so that we can actually get people to turn up. It is a win win, as it does help increase the volunteer skills.”(Interview 8, 2023)

“We have a team leader and we have a volunteer coordinator who ensure that we offer training and development. These guys are giving up their time, so we want to help them learn new things and be better in their role. “(Interview 13, 2024)

In summation, training and development constitute a critical domain that is universally recognized as highly important by all participants in the statutory advocacy sector. It not only underpins the professionalism and expertise of staff members but also plays a pivotal role in advancing the overall quality of advocacy services provided to vulnerable individuals. Moreover, it serves as a pathway for individuals, whether they be professional staff or dedicated volunteers, to continually enhance their skills, thus contributing to the continued growth and efficacy of the sector.

In conclusion, the commitment to training and development is emblematic of the statutory advocacy sector's dedication to maintaining high standards of service and professionalism, while also fostering the growth and progression of its dedicated workforce.

4.2 Organisation

The research underscores the prominence of organisational development as a recurring theme within advocacy providers. While creative strategies for staff and volunteers are indeed integral to their operations, the research highlights the shared commitment to organisational innovation among providers.

For respondents, the organisational culture serves as a dynamic arena for adaptation and change, even in the context of delivering requisite advocacy services. The case studies reveal that creative utilisation of elements such as meetings, advocate support mechanisms, and the internal lexicon have emerged as innovative means to amplify the impact of advocates.

“I think we have a culture where people are able to talk to us and I hate the cliché of open door policy, but I think people know they can come and bring me ideas and talk to me.”(Interview 1, 2023)

Furthermore, the sector exhibits a diverse array of management styles and structural configurations. Yet, beneath this diversity lies a unifying thread in the form of a foundational philosophy that underpins each organisation's chosen approach. Recognising the distinct

socio-geographical challenges in which each organisation operates, the pursuit of a one-size-fits-all solution is rendered untenable. Instead, organisations find common ground through shared philosophical ideas while accommodating unique contextual variables.

These management styles are inherently intertwined with the organisations' vision and mission. The socio-economic and geographic idiosyncrasies inherent to each provider preclude the adoption of identical approaches. Nonetheless, the study seeks to elucidate the commonalities that thread through these distinct contexts.

Central to the core of advocacy providers lies the relationships forged with service users. These intricate and delicate relationships are fundamental to the success of providers. The study delves into the shared approaches that underpin these pivotal relationships, as explored in the subsequent findings section.

In addition to the enhanced empowerment of staff achieved through flexible working hours and locations, technology has assumed a pivotal role in bolstering and shaping the organisational response. This encompasses the development of comprehensive databases, the introduction of individual devices, and the harnessing of internal peer communities for mutual support and professional growth.

4.3 Culture

For advocacy providers, each organisation participating in the research expressed a profound sense of pride in their distinctive identity. These identities often find their roots in a community-focused approach, serving as a fundamental method to nurture creativity. This emphasis on community-centricity allows for the celebration of a diverse range of cultural identities, underscoring the historical development of the advocacy sector.

Beyond this diversity, some common themes came to the fore during the research. Among these, the significance of rituals and routines emerged as a central component in the operations of most organisations participating in the interviews. These rituals and routines manifested in various forms, encompassing daily morning huddles, weekly team discussions, and the establishment of steadfast peer support networks for staff. While the specifics of these practices were unique to each organisation, they converged upon a shared vision of cultivating a culture that actively bolsters and supports staff members in their roles.

“We have Getting It Right Days. We have a couple of years where people who use our services are encouraged to come and tell us what works and what does not work. Also, there's a number of staff who—so we also then have a fortnightly management team meeting, and I expect managers to bring stuff from supervision to say, actually, this works, this does not work.”(Interview 1, 2023)

Staff work hard, but I need to keep an eye on the mental health and organisational need. We have weekly multidisciplinary team meetings where we can see what everyone is up to. (Interview 3, 2023)

In acknowledging the diverse composition of their staff, some providers displayed a heightened awareness of the presence of neurodiverse team members. In response, these organisations embarked on a deliberate journey to cultivate a culture that was not only accommodating but also deeply appreciative of neurodiversity. This approach resulted in an inclusive and supportive environment that catered to the unique needs and strengths of every team member.

“So someone came up with the idea of, you know, if people are busy, how how would they show that they're busy and someone came up with the idea of, like, we did not spoons and and if you wouldn't spoon is up, that means you're not to be interrupted.”(Interview 12, 2023)

“It was our 10th anniversary last year and actually one of the things we found is 30% of our workforce are people who would identify as having learning disabilities or autism or mental health issues and I'm very proud of us doing that because I think if we can't talk the talk, then who can?”(Interview 11, 2023)

“So we have a managers meeting every Monday and not only talk about whats happening, but we also chat about new ideas, especially the ones x comes up with.”(Interview 10, 2023)

“We have monthly team meeting and I suppose I like to think that the way it is led is just sort of very open. This encourages chat and ideas.”(Interview 11, 2023)

A common theme across advocacy providers was the steadfast commitment to delivering integrated services throughout their organisations. This commitment was born from a recognition of the potential drawbacks of siloed working approaches, which could inadvertently compromise the quality of services provided to users. To address this, organisations implemented clear and formal organisational structures designed to foster the

development of multiskilled advocates and employees, capable of seamlessly navigating the multifaceted needs of service users.

“You know we have had people multi skilled for for a few years now, so that's helped with that kind of fluidity of work.”(Interview 4, 2023)

“More multi skilled. That's that's our goal. And we've got people still working towards in some in some areas. But the idea is that they are all multi skilled. This allows for better services and helps the way people think beyond a silo” (Interview 6, 2023)

Facilitating decentralised and localised power structures represented another vital facet of the integrated approach adopted by advocacy providers. Empowering staff members, as discussed earlier, played a pivotal role in enabling this decentralisation. By delegating decision-making and initiatives to local levels, organisations sought to cultivate a sense of ownership and accountability among their staff members, thereby strengthening their commitment to the organisation's mission.

“I think giving them the stuff, the autonomy to manage their own work schedules and everything else does encourage that sort of creativity and I think they examples of good practice or where something has worked well”(Interview 9, 2023)

“So we have different because we have different projects and before we did not have as many projects, we now have you know meetings for all the different projects and there's a managers meeting, there's a whole team meeting and it seemed like it was kind of repetitive. We let managers choose where they would like to attend, rather than telling them.” (Interview 12, 2023)

Additionally, the research underscored the paramount importance of branding, identity, and the imperative for advocacy providers to establish and maintain their independent organisational credentials. Organisations articulated the necessity of signalling their independence from other official bodies, such as the NHS, Care Homes, and the legal system. This endeavour extended to ensuring that meeting spaces were not subject to external control, and when such control was unavoidable, creating secure spaces for discussions that safeguarded the interests of service users.

“We make sure we are seen as different, separate from NHS and councils. We can’t take offices in their buildings and we are very clear that we are there for the client” (Interview 11, 2023)

“We doing the community centre locations because there were a couple of buildings that we could have used and it is not there wouldn't have been an issue in terms of that, but it is more the perception from people you know . There was a few, there's a few big buildings in in Edinburgh that have like the social work department and the Council tax offices and we could have got rooms there. You need that distance, the perception that we are different.”(Interview 13, 2024)

The findings highlight the key commonalities of culture across the providers that took part in the research.

4.3.1 User Centred

Advocacy providers, driven by a deep commitment to empowering and representing individuals facing challenges, unequivocally position the user at the epicentre of their work. This dedication to prioritising the needs, rights, and voices of service users is not just a set of words but has become a key common principle across the providers taking part in the research.

“We work to adapt the pure advocacy which is issue-based, fighting for the rights of an individual, working alongside them and so on and so forth, it is the heart of what we do.” (Interview 2, 2023)

At the very core of this commitment lies the recognition that advocacy is, fundamentally, about giving voice of those who might otherwise be silenced or overlooked. This can take the form of human rights or social model of advocacy, but both aim to reach the same outcome. Advocacy providers are acutely aware that their work is not an exercise in imposition or direction; rather, it is an embodiment of the principle of allowing users to have their views heard. This entails respecting the autonomy and choices of service users, even if those choices diverge from what others might consider ideal.

“Yeah, people's rights are protected and that's critical, absolutely critical. But again, back to have they had a voice? Is their life better because of our intervention?”(Interview 1, 2023)

“We've had people, one young man who had a son and he's got fetal alcohol syndrome. We've helped, we've really fought hard for his voice to be heard, for him to go into fully funded alcohol rehab, right? We gave him his voice back.”(Interview 2, 2023)

“My deputy's husband works for an arts organisation. So she's really she's really wanting to do a lot of art stuff. So I mean again, that's another area looking at is, you know. Because advocacy and art do go together quite, quite well, you know. So you can. You can give people a voice through art.”(Interview 11, 2023)

One of the keyways advocacy providers place the user at the centre is through the process of informed consent. Prior to advocating on behalf of a service user, providers ensure that the individual comprehends their rights, the potential outcomes of their decisions, and the available alternatives. This transparency and respect for autonomy form the bedrock upon which advocacy relationships are built. Whilst this may not be possible in some cases, where capacity maybe lacking, the providers all demonstrated a preference for leading with an informed consent model.

“And I argue with local authorities and actually I'm arguing with the quality performance mark people at the moment as well. I know quite a lot about them as well, yeah. They're like, we've done our desktop assessment and they said, well, we need you to gain consent. I'm like, I'm sorry, what? Consent from who? From the people that you're doing IMCA for, we need you to gain their consent. I said, shall we take that back a few steps? Shall we? Shall we?”(Interview 2, 2023)

“A referral I had beginning of the year, there was somebody with hip hip replacement and referral came in in the morning. I phoned about the referral and they've gone down, but she's only gone for the operation. I asked why, they said they had a cancellation so decided to go ahead. But they did not get consent someone that lacks capacity you have given an operation such as a hip replacement. That's not legal or right.”(Interview 10, 2023)

The concept of 'person-centred care' is an integral part of advocacy provision from the interviews. This approach tailors advocacy services to the unique circumstances and preferences of everyone. It acknowledges that there is no one-size-fits-all solution, and that effective advocacy necessitates a nuanced understanding of the service user's distinct needs and aspirations.

“It is very our approach to advocacy is based on a human rights based framework and you know, and it is around the voice of the person.” (Interview 2, 2023)

“so it may be that somebody's got a very particular case that as extremely complicated or has some unique aspects of it, often there is no such thing as normal. Everyone is unique and we must treat them that way.”(Interview 7, 2023)

Moreover, advocacy providers adopt a holistic approach that recognises the multifaceted needs of service users. These needs span a wide spectrum, encompassing not only the immediate issue at hand but also the broader context in which the individual resides. This approach acknowledges that the challenges faced by service users are often interconnected, and addressing one issue may require consideration of others, the so called Wicked Problems. Addressing this, whilst beyond the strict remit of statutory advocacy, played a key role in a majority of providers. This was addressed through concepts such as citizen advocacy, volunteer led approach and also creating self-advocacy toolkits.

“Big providers do A sort of one. Size fits all approach to everything. It ends up providing services in exactly the same way as statutory services - long, long waiting lists. Our innovation is about the individual focus, our USP.” (Interview 3, 2023)

“There's the statutory advocacy strand and we now do all statutory advocacy. So, IMCA, RPR, Care Act, NHS complaints and now IMHA, which is relatively new for us, the IMHA bit. And we do very little commissioned community advocacy because nobody's commissioning it anymore. That's been chopped and again that's no surprise and it is not going to get any better. And almost certainly I will break down in floods of tears a minute when we talk about commissioning but will try to keep my powder dry. The other part of the organisation is our group work, so that is groups for, so very much self-advocacy, peer advocacy, so we work with people with learning disabilities, people with autism, we have a really interesting project in (our county) where we're working with people with autism who have a significant mental health issue.”(Interview 1, 2023)

“We also currently receive other funding through an organisation called support in the right direction, which again comes from the Scottish Government, which is specifically and relation to supporting people with self directed support, which is the kind of social chaos. It adds another element to our delivery model.” (Interview 7, 2023)

Furthermore, advocacy providers are resolute in their commitment to upholding the dignity and rights of service users. This entails challenging discrimination, stigmatization, and

marginalisation that service users may face. Advocacy interventions are designed to break down systemic barriers that obstruct the full exercise of rights and participation in decision-making processes.

“I think the other thing is, you know this this before I forget in the city, we do have, umm, quite high level of diversity and community groups. So around about 40 % of the population would be particularly South Asian. The communities, and again, sometimes there's a language barrier. Sometimes there's actually, perhaps not engaging with other services as well, so I think that's that's another part of it really. That makes our job much harder.”(Interview 9, 2023)

Advocacy providers frequently engage in capacity-building initiatives aimed at equipping service users with the skills and knowledge required to advocate for themselves. This empowerment is not just a means to an end; it is an intrinsic aspect of the advocacy process. By enhancing the self-advocacy skills of service users, providers enable them to navigate future challenges more effectively and independently. It also allows the organisation to extend their reach into communities and support groups that perhaps are unable to access traditional forms of advocacy.

“but we're already overwhelmed with referrals. So us providing them. An information pack is not what they were asking for they were asking for an advocate, so we at least need to give them the chance. And you know chances are that these person people have come to us because they have a mental health need or a learning disability, or something else that is preventing them progressing with that component on their own so additional barriers.”(Interview 4, 2023)

“And so we offered out some small grants to other third sector organisations. So there was. And I can't remember them off the top of my head. I'm sure it is on our website. But to those organisations. So I know. I think there was a charity said they focus on the trans community that you know, for whatever reason there's a there's a barrier for some people come into a kind of a generic advocacy organisation. So we're like, well, let's equip the organisations that are already meeting the needs of these people to deliver some advocacy. Let's train them.”(Interview 4, 2023)

Moreover, advocacy providers actively seek feedback from service users, via having persons with lived experience being part of their board or alternatively having a user group to create a positive feedback loop. This approach is underpinned by recognising that whilst lived

experiences are by their nature unique, the perspectives are invaluable in shaping the quality and effectiveness of services. This feedback loop allows for continuous improvement and ensures that advocacy remains responsive to evolving needs and priorities.

“We have started a conference that used to happen previously.... Coming out of COVID-19 we had to evolve. You know, it was trauma, informed practice and and it was great because I think X paid for the venue, we brought some cakes, Y brought something else and it was really just travel for those who wanted to attend.”(Interview 12, 2023)

“And, you know, for us, we innovated by taking on this project with people with mental health issues who are autistic. And that was a really big step for us. And it is not been a straightforward project. You know, we are now used almost as a crisis service by all the other services. But it is been really interesting to do that, and great, and has informed us. So I think just for the good of the organisation, the good of the staff, the good of the people we support, innovation is critical.”(Interview 1, 2023)

“So I saw my advocates really changing the way they worked with people. To try and make sure that you know I mean, this was small stuff in some ways for the individual. It is big, but it might have been the way in which they were able to seek views, communicate, manage remote meetings, to support the person to be involved the way that they were able to. You know those sorts of things. So we have a responsibility to share that in our organisation and to keep doing it.”(Interview 3, 2023)

This commitment manifests in a multitude of ways, from respecting informed consent to adopting a holistic approach and championing person-centred care. By empowering service users, and by ensuring that activities are user centred, this can allow the providers to deliver their shared vision of a more equitable and just society where the voices of all individuals are heard and valued.

4.3.2 Technology

The advent of the COVID-19 pandemic and the subsequent lockdown measures imposed a new set of challenges for advocacy providers, necessitating a swift adaptation to a changing landscape in their interactions with service users. Notably, the introduction of technology emerged as a common and pivotal theme that permeated the strategies of these organisations.

This shift was not only catalysed by the imperative to support other organisational changes, such as flexible working arrangements, but also by its identification as a mechanism for cost-saving through enhanced time efficiency.

In the post-COVID era, the utilization of technology, specifically laptops and increasingly tablets, has gained prominence by streamlining the administrative aspects of advocacy provision. Advocacy providers recognize the delicate balancing act required when dealing with sensitive user information. The challenge lies in capturing this information in a timely, secure, and effective manner, while simultaneously addressing the potential barriers introduced by technology. Notably, the use of laptops and similar devices has the unintended consequence of creating physical and emotional barriers between advocates and users, an issue that organisations are acutely aware of and try to actively address.

“So they advocacy partners, people that we work with, like for example, are consent forms are in evaluation tools, they're all loaded up onto their remarkable and the workers can take them out and the person can kind of fill them in and then they just got uploaded to our database.”(Interview 12, 2023)

At the heart of this technological transition is the introduction of bespoke databases, often repurposed Customer Relationship Management (CRM) systems, which have become integral to the operations of advocacy providers. These databases serve the dual purpose of creating synergies within organisations and offering a structured platform for the management of user data. Furthermore, they facilitate the generation of valuable management information, including data mining capabilities, that significantly reduces the burden of reporting to funders.

*“We introduced a new database. It helps everyone, but never again it was so stressful!”
(Interview 1, 2023)*

“I think that with the database we've partnered up with the database creator, the organisation that's creating the database, because we're constantly tweaking it and moving forward with it, but we're actually going to model that out and hopefully market it to advocacy organisations as well. So the workflow, the capturing information, the recording information, the diagram, so you can draw everything down from that and create nice wizzy reports and we've got an outcome star and all of those kind of things that are on the database. So but we partner with them about how to create it obviously but also then how we can develop it to bring it to market” (Interview 2, 2023)

“But it was a system that was developed for us and run about , I think, and it is based on a software called file Maker, which is a database software and initially it was on a server here in the office and computers were plugged in. We wireless, you know, when people would update their case notes here, but and before the pandemic, we decided to migrate it to the cloud, which was probably helpful because it wouldn't when the pandemic hit, it was a lot easier to get IT guy to set up remote access for it. “ (Interview 7, 2023)

This enhanced data infrastructure also affords advocacy providers with the added advantage of furnishing senior leadership teams with rich management information. This data-driven insight empowers these teams to discern emerging trends, allocate resources judiciously, and identify demographic groups that require advocacy support but may be underrepresented in current caseloads. The strategic utilization of this information fosters a more responsive and proactive approach to advocacy service delivery.

“I think I’m like another level removed. So maybe we’re smt having to do a bit more of like the politics kind of stuff. And and then this moves in and making sure that everyone’s okay. It can be like, well, you know, this is the data. These are the figures here in the bits we’re struggling with. We can make better decisions.”(Interview 4, 2023)

“Actually, is there something here? Is there something in this? Do we need to have a a more like deep dive into this again? Kind of yes, we’d look at the data quarterly, and we’ve got a bit of an idea in our mind about oh.that seems very different to the last quarter. Let’s have a bit more of a nosy at that, or we’ve turned down a lot of referrals.”(Interview 5, 2023)

“I mean so prescriptive. I’ve just been doing the reporting this morning and without exaggeration there’s something like 200 lines of data they want and there’s seven orgs doing that. Luckily having the system means we can just do it. “(Interview 1, 2023)

The adoption of laptops, tablets, and bespoke databases, while driven by the imperative of adapting to the challenges posed by the pandemic, has evolved into a transformative force that enhances the efficiency and effectiveness of advocacy work. Despite the potential barriers introduced by technology, advocacy providers remain committed to maintaining the integrity of their user-centric approach.

“And zoom enables that to happen relatively easily. We’re not dragging people into the office for the sake of it.”(Interview 4, 2023)

“you know, we have people that might be sitting on a bus for 60 minutes, if it is a quiet bus you then you could use your tablet and be typing some things on there and you know, I suppose it helps to streamline the process in that way and help people and manage their work. Rather than building up massive amounts of admin, neither do they need to put aside a day sitting at a computer.”(Interview 7, 2023)

The data infrastructure not only streamlines administrative processes but also equips senior leadership teams with the tools to make informed decisions, ultimately resulting in a more responsive and agile advocacy landscape, something that most providers are aware of.

4.4 Differences in the case studies

Through this research, there are a range of commonalities but also some clear differences in how providers approach advocacy. While the vision for advocacy remains constant, the strategies employed to achieve this goal exhibit some key differences across providers. This section of the chapter examines the findings that highlight the divergent approaches, shedding

light on key areas of differentiation encompassing funding mechanisms, planning strategies, partnership dynamics, and demand management.

The first thematic divergence centres on funding. Advocacy providers rely on a range of financial sources to sustain their essential services. The research identifies the differences of approach in accessing statutory funding, corporate backing, and grant-based support. These diverse funding mechanisms bear significant implications for the operational capacity and sustainability of advocacy providers. While the overarching goal of securing resources to facilitate their mission is a common thread, the strategies employed to navigate the financial landscape showcase considerable variation among providers.

Operational planning emerges as the second critical area of distinction among advocacy providers. An exploration of their approaches to planning illuminates a spectrum of methodologies. Providers embrace various strategies, both strategic and operational, to chart their course. The research closely examines the nuances of these planning processes, elucidating disparities in the scope, focus, and execution of planning efforts. These distinctions in planning methodologies reveal not only the idiosyncrasies within each organisation but also the strategic orientations that guide their actions.

Venturing beyond the organisational confines, the research looks at how providers use partnerships. These collaborative endeavours encompass engagements with fellow advocacy organisations, trade bodies, and entities related to their advocacy domain. This section examines the divergent approaches adopted by providers in cultivating and sustaining these vital partnerships. These differences in partnership strategies offer insights into the varying philosophies and network dynamics that underpin the advocacy landscape.

The final thematic element explored within this chapter revolves around demand management—an issue of importance for providers. The capacity to effectively manage increasing demand for services, often juxtaposed with the concept of waiting lists, assumes a critical role in shaping advocacy operations. While the overarching challenge of balancing service availability and demand is a shared concern, the strategies devised by providers to address this challenge reveal intriguing variations.

Each of these thematic area findings are explored in the relevant sections below, supported by pertinent quotes derived from the interviews conducted.

4.4.1 Funding

In the landscape of statutory advocacy, financial resourcing comes primarily from central government channels, funnelled through local authorities or health boards, contingent upon the specific regional requisites. The distribution of this funding is frequently distributed by the framework of a competitive tendering process, where each advocacy provider competes to secure contracts.

“Of course, you know these. I mean, there's a lot of providers out there, but everyone's trying to go for the same parts of money, so the competition is quite significant.”(Interview 6, 2023)

“Yeah, your colleagues across the border. If what you know the point that that contract comes up, that your competition and I'm sure you know advocacy providers do not think like that. But ultimately, if it is, you know we're an organisation that wants to continue existing. And to do that, we need, we need contracts. We need the work coming in.”(Interview 4, 2023)

Yet, the dynamics of statutory advocacy provision have undergone increasing challenges over the last five years. Escalating demands for advocacy services, coupled with escalating operational costs and the rigidity imposed by fixed-price tendering mechanisms, have compelled advocacy providers to exhibit a remarkable degree of adaptability in their pursuit of financial sustenance for their organisations. This chapter embarks on an exploration of the innovative strategies harnessed by advocacy providers to navigate the challenges around acquiring funding to deliver services.

“And actually the consortium model, and we're seeing more and more consortiums where they want to put everything together so it is not just advocacy, it is advice, information, guidance. And that's fine. We're a peripheral part of that. But what it does do, actually, increased costs. And the way commissioning is commissioned increases, costs not reduced,”(Interview 1, 2023)

“We have to keep banging our heads against the brick wall. and we meet a lot of brick walls, but now and again a little brick falls out, and you see a chink of light on the other side. But actually your advocates have got to be resilient enough to keep doing that for ever and ever and ever. Because that's the system we work within, is not it? It is wrong, but that's the system we work within. And that has been particularly difficult since Covid, with the cost of living crisis and with all of the downward pressure on budget that has been coming from central government, or whatever, wherever I do not want to get political,”(Interview 3, 2023)

“So it is a short, in theory. Short term, it is not quite obvious, and every time you go off every time you think you've got to a place of equilibrium. Usually it is commissioners that throw a spanner in the way or you have a cost of living prices, or something, or whatever it is, all you get, Covid, you know you get to a point where you think right, you have to respond.”(Interview 8, 2023)

One key approach employed by providers is diversification in their approach to sourcing funding. While central government funding remains foundational, organisations have ventured into harnessing supplementary streams of financial support. These alternative avenues may encompass corporate partnerships, philanthropic donations, or grants from private foundations. This diversification not only bolsters financial resilience but also fosters independence from singular funding sources, thereby enhancing organisational stability.

“Mirrors what's happened in England, really, where the contracts now, some of them are not even cost recovery. And you're expected even to find some funding elsewhere, or use volunteers to deliver it, which, when it is the legislation,”(Interview 8, 2023)

“Our plan for funding I think I need to rewrite it, because I think it needs to be more specific. So, for example. have we actually sort of said, how much we will raise through diversification. But that is the future target.”(Interview 11, 2023)

“We also currently receive other funding through an organisation called support in the right direction, which again comes from the Scottish Government, which is specifically and relation to supporting people with self directed support, which is the kind of social chaos.”(Interview 7, 2023)

Furthermore, advocacy providers have engaged in rigorous cost management practices. The imperative of optimizing resource allocation and operational efficiency has led to the implementation of leaner, more streamlined administrative processes. The ensuing cost savings are reinvested into service delivery, ensuring that resources are channelled to areas of paramount importance, ultimately benefiting service users.

“We had the remarkable because it translates your if you write neatly, it does not do it for me. You can translate it to text, so you're notes you know, rather than having to type up and say you can integrate all your documents. So actually when we looked at it, you know the amount of admin time that was saved versus the cost of the Remarkables was kind of a no brainer.” (Interview 12, 2023)

Moreover, collaborations and partnerships have emerged as a strategic cornerstone in securing additional funding. Advocacy providers explore synergistic alliances with other organisations operating within related domains, harnessing collective influence to attract funding opportunities that transcend individual capacities.

“So we took on a training addiction worker through the Scottish drugs Forum a few years ago. and it was absolutely great. So we managed to get funding from the local alcohol and drug partnership.”(Interview 8, 2023)

The subsequent sections delve into the nuances of these diverse approaches to financial sustainability, offering insights into the multifaceted strategies that advocacy providers employ to navigate the complex terrain of securing funding in the era of increasing demand and fiscal constraints.

4.4.2 Statutory

Within the cohort of providers, there exists a range of practices when it comes to engaging in statutory advocacy tendering. The participants selected for interviews were all bound by a common criterion: involvement in some form of statutory advocacy and the subsequent acquisition of funding through this avenue.

The strategies deployed by advocacy providers in their pursuit of statutory advocacy funding differ, underscoring the diversity within this professional domain. Among the respondents, three distinct approaches to statutory advocacy funding were discerned, each reflecting a unique stance in navigating the intricacies of tendering for contracts.

Firstly, some advocacy providers adopt a highly targeted approach, directing their resources and efforts towards securing contracts in a deliberate and calculated manner. These organisations meticulously identify specific contracts that align with their mission and operational capabilities. Building robust relationships with commissioners and fellow providers becomes a pivotal element of their strategy. The goal is clear: to optimize the likelihood of success in securing the identified contracts. Failure to do so could entail the risk of organisational dissolution or integration into another advocacy entity. This approach hinges on precision and strategic alignment.

“The other thing we have as well is commissioners saying, if we return % of the budget, they they will ensure early payment of invoices. And that for me is despicable. They have a duty to pay us on time. So of course, you know, to say, well, if you give us % back, we'll pay you early, two weeks early. Actually, you just paid us on time, we wouldn't need to. So it is what we do. And again, they mark you on it. So you get marked on whether you're going to accept the performance bond or not. So it was something like a % mark if you accepted it. So of course, what we did in one of our contracts is we said, yes, of course, we'll knock % off, but we just whacked it somewhere else in the budget” (Interview 1, 2023)

In contrast, a second cohort of providers embraces an opportunistic stance, casting a wide net by tendering for a multitude of opportunities that fall within their geographical and mission purview. This expansive approach aims to diffuse fixed operational costs across a greater number of tenders, thereby achieving economies of scale. By engaging with a broader range of contracts, these providers seek to mitigate the vulnerability associated with relying on a single funding source. Moreover, it mitigates the potential challenges that may arise from simultaneously partnering with multiple organisations within the same geographic area.

“For instance, in X we have a specific demand for support and adults with problematic alcohol and drug use. This gives us an opportunity to secure funding from a different pot.”(Interview 7, 2023)

“I mean there there's other but resources available within Scotland or something called CORRA funding, which potentially could be a possibility for us in the future if that area sort of alcohol and drugs. Or family related things was to increase, money for that can mean we can go beyond the the the the sort of limitations of our our current resources, so we might be able to apply for some funding through that.”(Interview 8, 2023)

A third, more focused approach is adopted by certain advocacy providers. These organisations elect to offer a limited spectrum of services, such as only offering spot purchases or appropriate adults in certain areas. This strategy translates into a concentrated emphasis on specific areas of advocacy, rather than pursuing a broad portfolio of contracts. By limiting exposure to long-term contracts, these organisations retain a heightened degree of flexibility and responsiveness in adapting to evolving funding opportunities. This approach prioritizes agility and adaptability over extensive service coverage.

“We will never go for a contract that is one that we can't get or one that we do not want because the funding, it is such a race to the bottom that there's just nothing there. We're not interested in like that organisation that I referenced, they had five contracts. They went from two right up to five and they lost three of them in the space of six months. So they pretty much had to make nearly all their staff redundant. And so we're really clear that we've got like our main bread and butter is the spot purchase work that we do.”(Interview 2, 2023)

“If we focus too much on the minute and kind of lose sight of where we can hope to be , then we may end up losing it to have big organisation that just comes in and sweeps all our contracts up. We need to stick to stat community based advocacy”(Interview 7, 2023)

4.4.3 Grants

In addition to statutory funding, most advocacy providers actively seek financial support from alternative sources, with grants emerging as a significant component of this endeavour. The acquisition of grants serves a dual purpose: to attain economies of scale and to expand the range of services offered, thereby augmenting the organisation's overall impact.

Among the interviewees, a subset of advocacy providers demonstrates a proactive stance in seeking grants that align with their mission and advocacy-related objectives. These grants

span a spectrum, encompassing both one-off test grants, which are strategically channelled into specific areas of advocacy such as addressing alcohol-related issues, and ongoing financial support extended by various providers. For these organisations, grant funding serves to bridge the financial gap left by the challenges surrounding statutory funding.

“But also we've been able to be quite innovative in the way that we access call funding from grant funders to be able to support that, to reduce the amount of central cost contributions. Now that in itself has been driven by necessity because actually, when it comes to it, you statutory funders, your local authorities, your health boards, whatever they're called in England and Scotland was health boards and local authorities here do not recognise the true costs.”(Interview 3, 2023)

By diversifying their funding streams through grants, advocacy providers unlock the potential to share central costs across a gamut of services. This strategic approach empowers organisations to achieve financial equilibrium, particularly in the face of fluctuating statutory funding. Moreover, the non-repayable nature of grants offers a distinct advantage. It enables organisations to broaden the scope of their advocacy services, including preventive interventions aimed at averting mental health crises. This expansion of services is viewed as a logical and pragmatic approach, given the funding's non-repayable nature.

“I suppose we have the benefit of being in the position that we are, because we see things for both sides where the money is, where the money is not, and where the need is. So we often put things to, you know those things together. And so then we would go and approach independent grants. That's very varied. Of course, you know these. I mean, there's a lot of providers out there, but everyone's trying to go for the same parts of money.”(Interview 6, 2023)

For example, turning point with other last August project where we were bringing awareness of substance misuse, we've got some lottery funding to do, some sort of more intense casework with people and be friending. We also have paid for services as well, which that varies from day care, where people are taken to a location or an activity centre, they spend some time there and they have meals and transport home. All of this helps. (Interview 9, 2023)

However, an alternative perspective on grant funding introduces a note of caution. Some interviewees contend that the nature of restricted, short-term grant funding presents its own set of challenges. They raise concerns about the administrative burden associated with such

funding, including the need to segregate grant monies in financial records and reports, as well as the imposition of stringent reporting requirements. Additionally, the prescriptive nature of some grants, specifying how the funds should be utilized, is perceived as potentially outweighing the benefits.

“So this is the very conversation that I have with them, you know, say we need more funds in because we're struggling with capacity and led to the cost, then you know our overheads are now more than the uplifts that we get and all the rest of it. And it is like, well, why do not you apply for this pot of funding? That pot of funding from this trust or that grant. But it is because it is statutory work - It a lot of these grants won't entertain that, even though it is the same people.”(Interview 12, 2023)

“We've got what we call an advocacy network. And I've been at lead on that. But we have all the sector organisations get together. I think it is like once a quarter, because we know that there are other groups that are delivering like advocacy advocacy just via another name. We get funding and so we offered out some small grants to other third sector organisations.”(Interview 4, 2023)

Participants also underscore the tendency of grants to serve as vehicles for testing projects, sometimes irrespective of the project's successful outcomes. For instance, a project designed to support a particular segment of the community may secure funding for a limited duration, often 12 months. While the project may demonstrate success within the specified timeframe, the nature of grant funding restricts its use exclusively for testing purposes. Consequently, even if the project meets its objectives, there is typically no avenue for continued funding, resulting in project termination at the end of the grant period. This phenomenon perpetuates a short-term outlook, which some advocacy organisations find challenging to reconcile with their long-term objectives.

“And then, unfortunately, most Grant providers do not keep the same thing going. They're looking to suddenly now find this magic bullet that fixes stuff in a year. Even if shows success, the funding gets cut.” (Interview 6, 2023)

But in the same respect they're very quick to fund a pilot project, not as quick to look at the evidence from that pilot, and then make a permanent project sleep. When I worked at a prison it was almost a revolving door with 12 month pilots different organisations coming in with money, gather the data, and then they're gone. So we know what works.(Interview 8, 2023)

Consequently, advocacy providers exhibit divergent perspectives on the pursuit of grant funding. While some actively harness grants to extend their services and bolster their financial resilience, others have reservations regarding the administrative complexities, restricted nature, and short-termism associated with such funding. This dichotomy in approach underscores the multitude of considerations that advocacy providers navigate as they resource their own organisations.

4.4.4 Corporate

Throughout the research, it became evident that select advocacy providers have actively pursued diversification of their funding streams through the exploration of corporate donations. This innovative approach seeks to tap into potential sources of both financial resources and expertise, which can, in turn, be leveraged for the advancement and expansion of advocacy organisations.

Interviewees revealed that their endeavours in this regard may have involved collaboration with external consultants, tasked with identifying suitable corporate partners capable of contributing to the organisation's mission.

“There are various schemes you can sign up to as a charity. There's one I know there's one called PilotLighters. Pilot Light is something that's called where you know it. Your partner is I do not know. Some guru from the private sector will come, and this is what I think I think happens anyway, will come, and you know support your charity in some way or another, whether it is your com, you know. Somebody might come in and offer their skills with comms.”(Interview 11, 2023)

The primary objective was to establish mutually beneficial relationships wherein the advocacy provider could align with a company's Environmental, Social, and Governance

(ESG) policy. This alignment could manifest in various ways, including financial contributions, support in areas such as marketing, or active participation in volunteer programs integrated into the company's strategic agenda.

“And you know the message from the corporates. I can't remember which one. It was one of the big banks or something with that, you know. Do not. Do not come to us just expecting a cheque, you know, cause you won't get it. You've got me? It is about building the relationship, and that can take a long time. So I'm so very aware of that. So like with Amex, for instance, what was the way I went in was, what can we offer you? You know. And that was a lot. What can offer them is about supporting them to improve their diversity. You know where we're an organisation in the city that supports people that are not represented or as well represented as they should be. So we can offer you training. That's sort of led by learning, disability, awareness, training, or easy read, making an information accessible.”(Interview 11, 2023)

By fostering enduring partnerships with corporate entities, advocacy providers not only gained access to valuable resources but also enjoyed secondary advantages, including enhanced organisational legitimacy and heightened awareness of the advocacy sector.

“We recently had a meeting with, I'm never quite sure what to call them without sounding rude. Corporate investors, I think they could call themselves. And we were talking about who we were. We're x million a year, staff. I asked them who they were, and they were £x billion a year. And one of my passions is cricket. And the guy who owned it was actually owned one of the Indian IPL franchises. And I was thinking, oh, it is not even the same universe, that'll even the same world or continent. So, but I think it was really good for us to learn to be more efficient and more focused because the reality is we have to diversify because if we solely rely on local authorities, we are really in trouble”(Interview 1, 2023)

Conversely, an alternative approach to securing corporate funding involved the development and provision of specialized training and development services, which could be offered to relevant companies in exchange for financial support. This strategy transformed the advocacy provider into a social enterprise, accompanied by the attendant complexities associated with such a business model.

“So the service is in which we can provide income, have to subsidize our advocacy services, which do not, which are not financially viable at all. Sometimes we sell unemployment services to corporate social responsibility, you know, so yeah. So we can get returns on that. So it is effectively having to fundraise or generating income in areas that can attract that additional money.” (Interview 14, 2024)

However, this approach was distinguished by its ability to generate unrestricted corporate funding, potentially lead to longer-term contractual arrangements, and avoid the additional burdens often associated with funder-specific reporting requirements.

“So we have to grow unrestricted income, from services that we provide that you can, you know, you know yourself in terms of like when you're doing services provision even within like a not for profit organisation, it is possible to generate some level of income from service provision. Working with businesses gives us our freedom.” (Interview 14, 2024)

In the pursuit of corporate donations, advocacy providers embarked on diverse trajectories, reflecting the multifaceted strategies employed to diversify funding sources. These approaches illuminate the nuanced decision-making processes that advocacy organisations navigate as they seek to secure financial support and cultivate partnerships within the corporate landscape.

4.5 Planning

A recurrent theme that highlighted variations among advocacy providers was their approaches to organisational planning. Both strategic and operational planning within these organisations revealed a spectrum of methodologies, often influenced by socio-economic factors and inherent management structures.

Strategic planning, a subject of vigorous debate within the sector, exhibited diverse perspectives among advocacy providers. The research unveiled an array of approaches to this facet, each reflective of the provider's unique ethos and situational considerations. Some organisations placed significant emphasis on long-term strategic planning, recognizing its importance in navigating the complex advocacy landscape. In contrast, others contended that the nature of the sector, coupled with its contemporary challenges, rendered long-term strategic planning a less essential pursuit.

“So, um, generally I did create my five year plan, but because I’m a patient, I like to get it done as quickly as possible, but that’s just my personality, right. And so I do I’m thinking about yeah how long am I going to be in the business and what this organisation will look like in the future.” (Interview 5, 2023)

“Would love to have a strategic plan, but in this region the government has stopped functioning. Mental health challenges are the biggest cause of disability here in this region, But that funding that we had that was to anchor all of this is now gone because the civil servant just decided one day was not going to fund it anymore. There are no politicians in power to discuss it with, so why plan?.” (Interview 14, 2024)

“I would wish for financial security, so it is that would be the main thing because if you’ve got financial security, you can you could put a plan in place, you could make proper plans for big projects and know that you’re going to continue to be able to fund them. At the moment plans are a good idea, but do not fit into our world.” (Interview 13, 2024)

Operational planning, on the other hand, emerged as a commonality among all advocacy providers, regardless of their individual nuances. While every organisation maintained some form of operational plan, distinctions arose in the design, development, and execution of these plans within the respective providers. A dichotomy in management approaches was evident, characterized by the juxtaposition of top-down, management-led methodologies against more holistic, bottom-up ideologies.

“And you know, sometimes you are required to fight fires, and that does not have to be negative. That just is the way it is. But yeah, we have been pushing to really try and avoid that as much as possible. You know everything is to the to a greater or lesser extent planned. and even if the plants fall apart, at least we had plans in the first place.” (Interview 4, 2023)

“We do spend time on it, but things change fast, it is not necessarily planning for the future, it is planning of attack of how we are now.” (Interview 10, 2023)

Some providers adhered to a hierarchical model, whereby leadership spearheaded the operational planning process. In contrast, others advocated for a grassroots approach, contending that advocates possessed a more intimate awareness of the day-to-day challenges encountered by service users. The divergence between these contrasting concepts will be subject to deeper exploration in subsequent sections.

“The plan is informed by what I see is being delivered to the service, and also what the ops plan is. We develop these through through those conversations with the staff delivering the service. They need to be involved.”(Interview 6, 2023)

“We know we have only 15 beds that we look after in the ward, so planning is easy for that. I can just do that going forward, challenge is only how often staff send patient’s home. It is a simple job though.” (Interview 9, 2023)

In essence, the landscape of organisational planning within advocacy providers is multifaceted, reflecting a blend of strategic perspectives and operational methodologies. These distinctive approaches underscore the nuanced decision-making processes that organisations employ as they grapple with the complexities of planning and adapting to the ever-evolving advocacy sector.

4.6 Partnerships

Advocacy providers, deeply embedded within the health and social care sectors of their respective regions, operate within a complex web of services and legislative frameworks. In the pursuit of their mission, these organisations often find themselves engaging in partnerships with various stakeholders.

As previously noted, providers that secure statutory funding frequently do so through competitive tendering processes, often characterized by a shift away from a single-provider model toward collaborative partnerships. This shift aims to mitigate risks within the sector and enhance the quality of advocacy services.

“Tenders can often be in a consortium, so we either need to work in partnership with the ones that I think are going to be incoming or else we're just not going to survive” (Interview 2, 2023)

The study has illuminated a noteworthy divergence in the approaches adopted by advocacy providers when it comes to forming and managing these partnerships. While some providers actively cultivate relationships with related organisations, even those in direct competition during tendering processes, others grapple with the inherent challenges of navigating conflicts of interest in such contexts.

“We try to work nicely with other orgs. We're in a couple of partnerships with other orgs. One or two of them are really good. We're also in a seven-organisation consortium that, clearly, when Dante was doing his levels of hell, he forgot charity consortiums as part of it, because I could weep quite often. We can't even decide if we want tea or coffee, let alone how we're going to provide . million pounds worth of services.”(Interview 1, 2023)

“Within Wales, the All Wales Advocacy Network Partnerships and training within that. So we have been involved in both drawing in hope into some of our training so that they can project that out across Wales and say, Look, advocacy. We're able to offer that out across Wales, and then everybody gets chance to do that. Now that was not happening before Covid, because everybody insisted their training had to be face to face in an office in the middle of nowhere, somewhere, whereas now we can have a mixture of that count where we can choose some stuff that needs to be face to face.It works well.”(Interview 3, 2023)

“However, we've grown, so we formed a working partnership with three other organisations at the beginning of, well, I think it is 2009 and we're successful in gaining the the 1st IMCA contract for the whole of x in partnership with with other services in 2010. But since then we have broken away from that partnership intended for the IMCA contract to bid for the whole of x on our own and being successful.”(Interview 10, 2023)

“So we're we're in a we're in a partnership with X, they are the lead in the partnership, so they they do the statutory advocacy. They do the IMCA and the bulk of the Care Act advocacy across Y, and also in Z, but we pick up some of the Care Act advocacy in in Z. They do keep most for themselves though.” (Interview 11, 2023)

Advocacy providers also maintain affiliations with trade bodies and representative organisations. However, the extent and nature of engagement with these entities varies among interviewees. Some providers perceive significant benefits in the form of policy development, resource sharing, and training opportunities through their participation in trade bodies. Conversely, others harbour reservations, perceiving these organisations as primarily serving the interests of larger members rather than levelling the playing field within the sector. Such perceptions influence the degree of active involvement exhibited by organisations in these collectives.

“You know, we are members of the Scottish Independent Advocacy Alliance. We follow their sort of principles and standards and code of best practice. And we feel quite strongly about that.”(Interview 7, 2023)

“And in fact, I was thinking of, you're probably aware of the advocacy leaders group that is a kind of a rough conglomerate of leaders of advocacy across the country. I'll just be really honest with you, Will, actually there's no point in otherwise. The problem with that is it is actually led by an organisation who want to do some really good work but are quite predatory and continually take over contracts of the smaller groups of the people in that group and that is a really uncomfortable fix.”(Interview 1, 2023)

“Is the huge difference between working in Cardiff, where everything's within a very small metropolitan area and working across what is a third of Wales in West Wales and how about what that means for people, the struggles they have, and all that sort of thing. So that collaborative side as got a lot to do with it. And it is also meant that from the management point of view as well, we've come together as a group of of advocacy organisations across Wales to be able to then en masse do certain things like dragging the Mental health Review Back Tribunal back to face to face tribunals for people when they did not want to, after Covid and going to the Health Minister and the local authorities around funding and in setting out what some of the crises are for advocacy organisations be able to continue to provide what is a really good service”.(Interview 3, 2023)

“Like an advocacy leader's forum, it is very predatory.They started to work together and they did over Covid, but then they put a spreadsheet together where everyone could upload their data, and so everyone could have access to it. And then people objected because X and Y said they did not have any data to upload, but took everyone else's. And they just like, basically, you know, why would you work with your enemy? It is cause they're, you know, they're financially drive.”(Interview 8, 2023)

Beyond the realm of advocacy, some organisations underscore the importance of forging robust relationships with other local entities operating within the same communities. The strength of these inter-organisational bonds serves as a catalyst for optimizing resources, facilitating seamless referrals, and enhancing the resilience of local communities. However, an opposing viewpoint posits that investing resources in relationship-building diverts attention from core advocacy activities and may not yield commensurate benefits.

“We've got lots of partnerships in the local area. Real robust solid network of services, you know, carers, carers, networks local voluntary sector. Services. I sit in the local B panel, and that's about local charities. So you know, it ranges from food banks to B : religious organisations through to general support. You name it where where we're linked. So, yeah, well, we discuss all sort of local area issues. We share ideas as well. You know, these, we all have access. We can work together and work in partnership to access some funding parts as well. So we've got a really good understanding of each other's strengths.”(Interview 6, 2023)

“We've got a really good relationship with a lot of the the different services and areas within the local authority and the local Nhs Health Board. So those really good relationships, you know, we've got a seat at the table. Adult Protection Committee and the Child Protection Committee cases.”(Interview 8, 2023)

4.6.1 Conclusion

This chapter has provided an examination of how organisations offering statutory advocacy services have utilized creativity to address operational challenges and foster innovation. Despite the regulatory constraints imposed by underlying legislation, advocacy providers have demonstrated a remarkable capacity for creative problem-solving and adaptation. Through interviews with key stakeholders, we have gained valuable insights into the diverse array of creative responses employed by organisations to navigate resource limitations, evolving user needs, and external pressures.

The analysis has highlighted both the shared and divergent aspects of creativity within the advocacy sector. While certain creative strategies may be universally embraced across organisations, others are tailored to the unique contexts and challenges faced by individual providers. From leveraging technology to streamlining administrative processes to developing novel advocacy models, organisations have demonstrated a commitment to exploring innovative solutions that enhance service delivery and meet the evolving needs of their users.

This chapter underscores the importance of fostering a culture of innovation within advocacy organisations. By creating environments where creativity is encouraged, experimentation is embraced, and knowledge-sharing is facilitated, organisations can enhance their adaptive capacity and resilience in the face of complex challenges. The next chapter will undertake an analysis of these findings in relation to key theoretical concepts.

Chapter 5: DISCUSSION

5.1 Overview of Key Findings

The research findings reveal a rich tapestry of creative responses among the organisations involved, showcasing diverse strategies to tackle sector challenges. The key shared output of the case studies was that creative organisations maximised their resources to meet the needs of their clients. Every statutory advocacy provider demonstrated evidence of adopting creative techniques to develop ideas, leading to innovation within their organisation.

According to scholarly sources, innovation drivers in the sector are divided into external and internal forces. External factors such as political influences, funding models, and metrics like Social Return on Investment (SROI) can drive organisations to innovate. In contrast, internal drivers might include ambitions for organisational growth, enhanced operational efficiency, and the necessity to satisfy increasing client demands, each promoting different innovation strategies. However, the research indicated that such a binary classification of innovation drivers does not reflect reality. Instead, internal and external factors intermingle, contributing to a continual impetus for innovation. Funding models are often connected with SROI and organisational expansion, while efficiency goals are leveraged as political instruments, further stimulated by increasing competition in the sector.

The response to these blended innovation drivers is broadly positive, with a vibrant and dynamic approach to supporting and developing creativity and ideas in the statutory advocacy providers. These different approaches highlight a range of innovative strategies, including the adoption of flexible work patterns to accommodate evolving needs, the cultivation of a dynamic and creative organisational culture, and the strategic use of training and development as pivotal tools for organisational enhancement. Examples of creativity in each area include using chocolates to drive awareness, supporting a neurodiverse workforce, and utilising ideas from adjacent fields through advocacy clinics.

While existing SI models focus on structured ideation stages with specific processes, this research highlights the importance of culture and practice in fostering innovation, elements often missing from existing frameworks. Although the literature provides a clear framework for managing innovation, the actual practices reported in the research were more complex. Interviewees shared that they did not follow prescribed SI methodologies; instead, they adopted a more spontaneous and responsive approach to innovation, especially ideation.

These methods emphasised culture and practice within the organisations rather than strict processes.

Therefore, to bridge this gap and allow analytical discussion around the research, the Shepherd Ideation Model (SIM) has been developed to recognise the need for culture and practice to be incorporated into SI frameworks. It builds on the work from Van Dijk and Van Den Ende (2002)

The development of the Shepherd Ideation Model (SIM) emerged from a research journey grounded in three key academic approaches, which together provided a distinctive perspective on creativity within the statutory advocacy sector and formed the conceptual backbone of the thesis. The study was initially informed by the social innovation model proposed by Murray et al. (2010), which offered a structured framework tailored to the needs of third sector organisations (TSOs). This framework provided a foundation for understanding how organisations approach innovation systematically.

This theoretical base was further enriched through the integration of perspectives from Van Dijk and Van Den Ende (2002) and Amabile (1996). Both approaches emphasised the utilisation of creativity and its transformation into actionable ideas, which were critical for examining the ideation stage within the social innovation model. These combined frameworks were instrumental in guiding the analysis and interpreting how creativity was fostered and harnessed by statutory advocacy providers. By uncovering the interconnection between culture, practice, and creativity, the research extended beyond traditional SI models, ultimately informing the creation of SIM as a framework that better reflects the dynamic and practice-driven nature of innovation in this sector.

5.2 Shepherd Ideation Model

The Shepherd Ideation Model (SIM) builds on existing innovation models, as discussed in the literature review, by introducing key elements that were previously overlooked. While traditional models focus on a structured ideation stage with specific processes, this research has revealed the critical roles of culture and practice in fostering innovation, elements absent in many existing frameworks.

The model reflects the shared experiences of idea generation with the SA providers that took part in the research. Focused on Culture and Practice, this model offers insight in ‘how to’ rather than ‘what to do’ in the ideation stage. It adopts a nonlinear approach, emphasising

two main aspects of ideation: Creative Unlocking and Idea Landing. The model has been developed to capture the reality that both elements are vital to successful ideation, then presented in a symbiotic shape that demonstrates the interconnectedness.

The model is versatile, fitting seamlessly with the social innovation models previously discussed, and serves as a complementary tool to enhance cultural and practical aspects of ideation. The figure below combines and simplifies social innovation models, demonstrating where the SIM can be used as a complementary tool for organisations.

Figure 8 Shepherd Ideation Model

These two elements will be explored with support from the research, setting out how this addressed the gap.

Before detailed exploration of these elements, it is important to see how the SIM works within the current frameworks of SI. Distilling the previously discussed SI models, there are broadly three phases, outlined below

Figure 9 Simplified Social Innovation Processes

Each of the existing models has stage or stages that address the issue, suggest way to carry out idea generation and then propose a mechanism to launch the innovation. All these approaches focus on developing an innovation process, which proposes a best practice definition of SI.

The literature suggests that creativity and ideas are the keys to the whole process, which is often located in the idea generation stages. The models propose tools that help with idea generation, such as brainstorming or SCAMPER, but fail to address the wider organisational context that the research shows is key to successful ideation.

The SIM addresses this gap by being complimentary to the SI models, adding some more contextual understanding around the culture and practices which can support ideation. The fit between the models can be seen below.

Figure 10 Simplified SI Process with SIM added

SIM has been developed to bridge the gap and reflect the current ideation practice in SA providers in the UK. It offers the opportunity for organisations using ideation as a process, to additionally explore other key elements that can support the creation of ideas.

Creative Unlocking, the first element of the model, acknowledges that all interviewed organisations had cultivated a culture that supports and encourages nonlinear thinking, which is crucial in the early stages of innovation. This is facilitated by fostering divergent thinking within the organisational culture, creating spaces where employees can freely explore new ways to address challenges, thereby valuing and nurturing creativity.

The second element, Idea Landing, is where creativity is transformed into actionable ideas within the organisation. This phase marks the transition from divergent to convergent thinking, where ideas are refined and integrated into the organisation's framework. Both elements of the SIM, are evident in the organisations studied, often subtly supported by the leadership within these providers. Leadership plays a crucial role in fostering an environment where creativity can flourish, and innovative ideas can take root. In these organisations, leaders actively encourage a culture of openness and experimentation, which is essential for Creative Unlocking and Idea Landing. They provide the resources and support needed for

staff to engage in divergent thinking, challenge conventional approaches, and propose novel solutions.

The model's flexibility allows it to be applied to a range of organisations, as it suggests ways to enable the exploration of activities within each segment without a rigid, predefined pathway. This adaptability ensures that the application of the model remains practical and relevant across different organisational contexts.

Both elements of the SIM will be discussed in detail, with supporting examples from the SA providers that took part in the research.

5.3 Creative Unlocking through Culture

Figure 11 Creative Locking Element of the Shepherd Ideation Model

The first element to be addressed is unlocking creativity through the development of organisational culture. The research revealed that organisations actively foster a culture that encourages the free expression of innovative ideas and the exploration of new possibilities. Organisational values include open communication, the belief that everyone can contribute, and minimising the fear of failure. By creating an environment where individuals and teams can think freely and divergently, providers can generate unique solutions and drive advancements. Leadership plays a crucial role in promoting and modelling this open, creative culture. This approach not only ignites creativity but also sustains it, making it essential for fostering innovation and maintaining competitiveness within any organisation.

Examples of statutory advocacy (SA) providers unlocking their creativity include creating an organisational culture that is diverse, offers a supportive environment, promotes risk-taking,

and is led by leaders who value creativity, thereby creating a fertile ground for innovation. These elements will be discussed below, revealing how providers have developed a culture that unlocks creativity within their organisations.

5.3.1 Diversity

Diversity has long been promoted as a mechanism for increasing creativity in an organisational context (Csikszentmihalyi, 1988), highlighting that teams that encompass this key attribute can boost outputs (Kurtzberg and Amabile, 2001). The research highlights that providers within the statutory advocacy sector reflect this ideology, showcasing the critical role of diversity in promoting creativity in organisational contexts. This diversity demonstrates an organisational awareness of creativity that can be unlocked to help drive innovation success.

5.3.2 Neurodiverse organisations

This concept is echoed in the findings of the current study, where interviewed providers frequently pointed out the diverse origins of their staff. Some organisations deliberately recruited individuals from a broad spectrum of experiences and backgrounds, acknowledging the significant contribution that diverse viewpoints and experiences make to fostering creativity and innovation. Whilst others felt that the nature of the role, level of pay and the flexibility of the organisations offered a more inclusive workplace than a private sector employer.

By welcoming a workforce with varied backgrounds, these providers lay the groundwork for a rich exchange of ideas, leading to the development of innovative solutions for intricate problems (Vasquez et al., 2021).

Additionally, a diverse staff enhances the organization's ability to adapt and remain resilient amidst changing circumstances. This thesis emphasizes the pivotal role diversity plays in fuelling creativity and innovation in businesses, underlining its importance in ensuring organisational success and maintaining a competitive edge in today's rapidly evolving and complex commercial landscape (Østergaard et al., 2011).

The recognition and inclusion of neurodiversity within organisations play a pivotal role in the development of creative ideas. Neurodiverse individuals, characterized by conditions such as autism spectrum disorder (ASD) and attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD)(Vasquez et al., 2021), bring unique perspectives and cognitive approaches that are invaluable in the creative process. Creativity can require divergent and then convergent

thinking, to develop lateral problem solving (De Bono, 1990). Two of the organisations felt that having a diverse workforce could be a ‘special power’(Interview 1, 2023) and gave them a ‘unique’(Interview 12, 2023) way to develop the organisations.

These unique perspectives stem from the different ways neurodiverse individuals process information and respond to their environments. For instance, someone with ASD might have an exceptional ability to focus intensely on details, leading to deeper insights or innovative solutions that others might overlook. Developing a workforce that naturally has different ways of approaching problems (Axbey et al., 2023) may drive creativity and in turn help the diversity to be an active contributor to the success of the provider (Herring, 2009). Similarly, an individual with ADHD may exhibit lateral thinking and rapid idea generation, traits that are crucial for brainstorming sessions and creative ideation (White, 2020).

This means that for statutory providers that offer workplaces that embraces neurodiversity, the conventional approach to problem-solving is enriched. Neurodiverse employees may contribute to a more varied set of ideas and solutions, breaking away from traditional or linear thinking patterns (Vance et al., 2008). This diversity in thought and approach is a key driver of innovation, enabling organisations to tackle challenges from different angles and come up with more creative, comprehensive solutions (Østergaard et al., 2011).

Beyond employees, over 40% of the organisations had user groups or people with lived experience as part of their wider creative ecosystems. This included volunteers that provided community advocacy, trustees of the organisation and project groups that all played active roles in the organisations. The voices of these member of the advocacy community were highly valued by providers, as they were helpful to “point out what we do not know” (Interview 5, 2023) as well as making sure the organisations were “supportive” rather than “dictatorial”(Interview 1, 2023).

Moreover, the presence of neurodiverse individuals was seen as a mechanism to drive a culture of “openness and flexibility” (Interview 10, 2023). It was highlighted that teams needed to become more adept at considering and integrating diverse viewpoints, fostering an environment where unconventional ideas are valued and explored, again creating a “unique authentic provision” (Interview 8, 2023) that was located in a “community centred” mindset. This not only enhances the creative process but also strengthens the organisation’s overall capacity for adaptation and innovation (Amabile, 1996), building a culture of creativity within the organisation.

Whilst a neurodiverse organisation is a key to the creativity demonstrated by the statutory providers, it is important to highlight that this factor needed to be nurtured. Without having a strong voice ensuring the views were integrated, it can result in a reduction of creativity (Hawlina et al., 2019). Therefore, another key discussion point in diversity was that of the leadership backgrounds of the interviewees.

5.3.3 Leadership Backgrounds

In relation to the development of creative ideas, the interview participants in this study came from a wide array of professional fields, including social work, performing arts, and academia (Interview 1, 2023, Interview 2, 2023, Interview 7, 2023, Interview 9, 2023, Interview 11, 2023, Interview 13, 2024, Interview 14, 2024). This diverse mix of backgrounds among the interviewees significantly enhanced the range and depth of perspectives obtained during the research (Herring, 2009). It also plays a crucial role for unlocking creativity in organisations as it ensures that there is a deep level of diversity from the top down (Wang et al., 2019).

The distinct expertise and knowledge that each participant brought from their respective fields greatly enriched the dialogue and facilitated a multifaceted examination of the topic at hand (Østergaard et al., 2011). Many of the interviewees highlighted their nontraditional leadership backgrounds, (Interview 1, 2023, Interview 2, 2023, Interview 8, 2023, Interview 10, 2023, Interview 12, 2023) as an important factor particularly pertinent to areas like statutory advocacy and organisational creativity.

Interviewees remarked that sometimes their roles as ‘outsider’ leaders (Interview 1, 2023, Interview 8, 2023, Interview 12, 2023), allowed them to challenge norms especially in a sector that is dealing with a highly dynamic and complex set of competing demands. It highlights that there is not a single template of a leader in the statutory advocacy sector. The leadership roles often being achieved by ‘accident’ (Interview 8, 2023) or through a set of circumstances that leads to ‘suddenly being in charge of a multi-million pound charity’ (Interview 4, 2023).

Overall, a consistent theme was the ‘outsider leader’, developing a creative culture that allows staff to give a voice to those who needed to be heard. The leadership journey being seen as a positive mechanism to embrace different concepts, often coming from a creative background including drama and art (Interview 7, 2023, Interview 10, 2023, Interview 13, 2024).

Leveraging and amplifying this diversity can result in a multitude of backgrounds, experiences, and viewpoints. Teams characterized by diversity frequently offer a spectrum of perspectives, fostering the generation of novel and inventive solutions. By embracing a diverse array of backgrounds and perspectives, organisations can harness the collective creativity and ingenuity of their teams, ultimately driving innovation and fostering a culture of inclusivity and innovation.

Ultimately unlocking creativity within the organisations needs nurturing, through a supportive environment that encourage exploration.

5.3.4 Supportive Environment

A supportive environment is vital for the development of creative ideas as it fosters a safe space for intellectual risk-taking and the exploration of novel concepts (Edmondson, 1999), free from the fear of judgment or failure. This nurturing atmosphere creates an environment that can be classed as offering participative safety (Axtell et al., 2000) which can encourage individuals to express their unique perspectives and experiment with innovative solutions, thereby enriching the collective pool of creative thought within an organization.

In every interview conducted with various organisations, there was a unanimous agreement on the paramount importance of staff in fostering and sustaining a culture of creativity through information exchange (Amabile and Khaire, 2008), which is intrinsically connected to the success of the organization. This emphasis on creativity is not merely a theoretical concept; rather, it is recognized as a critical component that thrives in an atmosphere of psychological safety and support.

To cultivate such an environment, these organisations adopt a multi-faceted approach. A key element is the creation of a physically appealing and positive workspace (Interview 1, 2023, Interview 2, 2023, Interview 5, 2023, Interview 10, 2023) through open collaborative spaces (Dul et al., 2011). This aspect is not limited to aesthetics alone; it also encompasses the functional design of the space to stimulate creativity and comfort (Interview 1, 2023, Interview 10, 2023, Interview 12, 2023). An example of this is that for one organisation the act of removing barriers and ‘de-siloing’ (Interview 10, 2023) allowed for better idea sharing, which corresponds to the relevant research (Kallio et al., 2015, {Martens, 2011 #1849). This allowed for development of wider elements of culture including the establishment of spaces dedicated to peer discussions, which it was felt served as breeding grounds for creative ideas,

encouraging staff to engage in open and collaborative conversations (Interview 1, 2023, Interview 4, 2023, Interview 10, 2023).

Time was also identified as a key factor in unlocking creativity within the statutory organisations, with some interviewees stating that allocating specific time for creativity is essential (Interview 13, 2024, Interview 14, 2024). The implementation of this varied including designated "innovation days"(Interview 2, 2023) or by offering flexible working hours to pursue personal creative projects (Interview 1, 2023, Interview 10, 2023). Other organisations had a structured set of activities that were creative days by another name (Interview 9, 2023, Interview 12, 2023), which gave employees time away from business as usual tasks, and space to think which was seen as crucial for fostering a culture of innovation and creativity (Interview 2, 2023, Interview 9, 2023).

Beyond the physical space, many of the organisations adopted an 'open door' policy in management (Interview 1, 2023, Interview 4, 2023, Interview 8, 2023, Interview 10, 2023, Interview 13, 2024, Interview 14, 2024) aiming to foster a sense of accessibility and openness, encouraging employees to share ideas, concerns, and feedback without hesitation (Kremer et al., 2019). This policy is not just symbolic; it is a practical step towards building trust and breaking down hierarchical barriers that can stifle creativity (Interview 4, 2023, Interview 14, 2024). Furthermore, organisations recognize the need for employees to have dedicated time to ponder and strategize about future initiatives (Interview 1, 2023, Interview 2, 2023). This time allocation is crucial for nurturing forward-thinking and innovative ideas, which are essential for the long-term success and evolution of the organization(Linstead and Mullarkey, 2003).This demonstrates a purposeful approach to developing a creative culture inside the organisation, that can allow for long term organisation innovation ideas to be located, developed and launched.

By integrating these diverse yet interconnected strategies, organisations effectively develop a creativity capacity with a nurturing environment (Törnqvist, 2004), which is directly linked to their overall success and growth. A supportive environment cultivates a culture of trust and openness, where individuals feel valued and understood, thus reducing the apprehension associated with proposing unconventional or bold ideas (Kallio et al., 2015). Such an atmosphere diminishes the fear of negative consequences for failure, encouraging individuals to venture beyond their comfort zones and experiment with novel, potentially high-reward creative solutions (Axtell et al., 2000). This freedom to explore and take risks without undue

criticism or backlash is fundamental in pushing the boundaries of creativity (Törnqvist, 2004, Linstead and Mullarkey, 2003), leading to breakthrough ideas and innovations.

5.3.5 Creative Leadership

Developing a culture of creativity within an organization greatly benefits from leaders who exemplify innovative thinking and creative problem-solving in their own roles (Hughes et al., 2018). It has been recognised that creativity is an essential element of the leadership role (Sternberg, 2007), which can support organisations to be inspired to think divergently and embrace risk-taking (Anderson et al., 2014). This leadership approach is integral in establishing a workplace environment that values and stimulates creative thinking, which in turn allows for the organisation to be flexible and efficient (Attar and Abdul-Kareem, 2020)

All the interviewees were in leadership roles, with some openly acknowledging their creativity (Interview 1, 2023, Interview 4, 2023, Interview 8, 2023, Interview 10, 2023, Interview 12, 2023), whilst others could only identify it when reflecting on their past actions (Interview 2, 2023, Interview 3, 2023, Interview 7, 2023, Interview 14, 2024). A common theme recognised across the research was that all the leaders were receptive to ideas and willing to implement suggestions from others, as long as they were supportive of the organisational mission. One interviewee shared that “Creativity is about freedom within the strategy” (Interview 1, 2023), identifying that they were often the “keeper of the strategy” (Interview 1, 2023) therefore had a responsibility to gather creative ideas from “far and wide” (Interview 1, 2023).

This practice not only fosters a sense of collaboration but also empowers employees to contribute more actively to the company’s creative endeavours. The leadership role therefore must manage a range of tensions in the development of creativity (Hunter et al., 2011), including communication of the company's goals and objectives, yet leaving the space for innovation in the future (Smith and Tushman, 2005). The leadership styles adopted by interviewees included dictatorial top down management (Interview 2, 2023, Interview 8, 2023) at one end of the scale, through to a much more laissez-faire style in others (Interview 5, 2023, Interview 10, 2023, Interview 13, 2024, Interview 14, 2024). It is clear from the research that whilst the approaches may differ, all the organisations aimed to provide employees with the ability to experiment with different approaches and solutions, fostering a more dynamic and innovative work environment.

The organisations involved in the study showcased a variety of methods fostering and unlocking their creativity. However, it is important to note that creativity alone is not enough; without effective mechanisms to capture and implement these creative ideas, their potential impact may be lost. This reality underscores the need for the providers to successfully 'land' these ideas, ensuring they contribute positively to the organisations.

Distilling these findings and mapping them against the Unlocking Creativity, identifies some cultural strategies that organisations can adopt to support ideation.

Figure 12 Cultural Strategies to Support Creative Unlocking

Unlocking creativity is crucial, but it is not sufficient on its own. It must be supported by effective idea landing, where creative concepts are transformed into actionable plans. Idea landing involves refining and integrating these ideas into the organisation's framework, ensuring they are practical and aligned with strategic goals. Without this step, creative ideas risk remaining abstract and unrealised. Leadership plays a key role in this process by providing resources, feedback, and support to transition from divergent to convergent thinking. This ensures that innovative solutions are not only generated but also effectively implemented, driving meaningful organisational change.

5.4 The Practice of Landing ideas

Figure 13 Landing Ideas element from the Shepherd Ideation Model

The second element of the SIM, is recognising the significance of an organization's ability to effectively 'land' ideas, transforming creativity into tangible concepts to support innovation. This not only requires a creative environment, but also organisational support to achieve the balance between business as usual and innovation projects.

This can be as simple as how the organisational manager responds to the ideas presented through to taking action to ensure that mechanisms exist to capture the widest possible range of ideas. This section of the thesis is focused on analysing findings related to this critical phase. It will comprehensively explore approaches to organisational ideas and the vital role of creative feedback loops in refining and enhancing the developmental process of these ideas.

5.4.1 Organisational Idea Generation

The importance of giving organisational creativity a way to be developed into ideas, and then set down (Van Dijk and Van Den Ende, 2002) cannot be underestimated. As discussed previously the research demonstrated that some of the interviewees highlighted that they are responsible for ensuring that the creativity is turned into ideas that are aligned with the organisational strategy.

One common theme that came through the interviews was that of regular 'development' days for the organisations (Interview 1, 2023, Interview 4, 2023, Interview 8, 2023, Interview 13, 2024, Interview 14, 2024). These were often aligned to staff development (Interview 1, 2023, Interview 10, 2023), training (Interview 4, 2023) and information sharing activities (Interview 2, 2023), creating a space where ideas could be generated against clearly defined

problems. This highlights the organisational support put in place to foster creativity, it is not something that happens by chance.

For these organisations the ability to generate and land ideas against a clearly defined problem, whilst the teams were together created a positive solution driven environment. Ideas could be developed and modified ‘on the fly’ (Interview 4, 2023) utilising the ‘lived experiences of the staff’ (Interview 1, 2023), resulting in a quick workable solution. It was identified that this removed the barrier of ‘not invented here attitude’ (Interview 4, 2023) and allowed all the staff to feel like they had some ownership (Interview 12, 2023, Interview 14, 2024). This offers a centralised idea suggestion mechanism (Frese et al., 1999) that provides a formalised approach focused on a clearly defined group issue (Leach et al., 2006).

This communal approach to idea generation is highly attractive to the organisations, as the need for ‘being inclusive’ (Interview 1, 2023), ‘allowing for everyone’s voice to be heard’ (Interview 4, 2023) and ‘giving equal opportunities for staff and service users to help develop the services in future’ (Interview 9, 2023). This runs counter to research that has identified that group idea generation creates fewer (Larson Jr, 2013) and often weaker ideas than either individual or nominal brainstorming (Barki and Pinsonneault, 2001).

Whilst it was a common theme, not all research participants followed a centralised approach (Frese et al., 1999), with one organisation pursuing an individualistic idea generation approach. The issues would be identified through data analysis, highlighting any gaps or reoccurring issues, which would then be allocated to a key member of staff with experience of the area. This was stated as ‘the quickest and best’ way to get a solution without ‘causing huge disruption’ (Interview 3, 2023). This organisation felt that having a specialist in the field with experience offered the best method of idea generation, with the concepts then being appraised by the leadership team to ensure organisational alignment (Interview 3, 2023).

The collaborative organisational development mechanism used to land ideas was proactively supported by the cultures of providing feedback throughout the process.

5.4.2 Creating a feedback loop

The literature is quite clear that that collation of initial ideas was not sufficient to drive a level of quality that would be required for strong innovation, this could easily lead to wasted effort (Wooten and Ulrich, 2017). As previously discussed, statutory advocacy providers are under increasing pressure to be more effective and efficient due to ongoing underfunding in the

sector. Optimising the development of ideas is one mechanism of aiming to maximise the return on investment of time from staff.

Offering feedback can be a mechanism that allows for the development of self-efficacy (Tolli and Schmidt, 2008) within the staff at statutory advocacy providers, which can be seen as a ‘good way to increase motivation of the staff’ (Interview 4, 2023). It is also seen as a vital step in the process of creativity, with both a generative and evaluation element (Montag et al., 2012). This process of providing creative ideas significantly boosts staff motivation in advocacy providers (Interview 1, 2023, Interview 4, 2023). The interviewees highlighted that when colleagues see their ideas acknowledged and constructively reviewed through verbal feedback (Interview 1, 2023, Interview 12, 2023) it can help reward their contributions and efforts. This recognition not only enhances their commitment to driving innovation (Interview 4, 2023) but also bolsters their drive to continuously contribute valuable insights, as they have lived experience of the challenges (Interview 5, 2023), which directly benefits the organisations.

The evaluation process was predominantly conducted by the organisation's leader, ensuring a focused and high-level review of the ideas (Interview 4, 2023, Interview 10, 2023, Interview 11, 2023, Interview 13, 2024). However, for topics that were particularly specialized or had significant impact, the discussion was broadened to include a wider range of perspectives, bringing in additional expertise and viewpoints to inform the decision-making process (Interview 1, 2023, Interview 3, 2023).

The mechanisms of feedback varied amongst the providers, with some having a highly structured process (Interview 4, 2023, Interview 8, 2023, Interview 10, 2023, Interview 11, 2023) and others offering a much more informal approach (Interview 1, 2023, Interview 3, 2023, Interview 12, 2023, Interview 13, 2024, Interview 14, 2024).

The formalised process allowed for a set standard of ideas to be measured and benchmarked, both from the proposer and the evaluators. Ideas may have to be shared in a ‘one pager’ which is then measured against a set of key organisational priorities such as resource allocation and risk (Interview 4, 2023). The organisations that used this or similar processes believe that it allows for a streamlined process (Interview 10, 2023) and allows the person with the idea to have to undertake some initial development in an organisational context (Interview 11, 2023). Feedback would be based around the same categories creating a transparent and logical process for all participants (Interview 4, 2023). It was an early stage

of idea evaluation, with the feedback being based around the potential idea implementation (Basadur, 1995). The feedback process is another organisational element that offers support to creativity within the providers, giving opportunities for multiple voices to be heard as well as different opinions to be given respect throughout the process.

Implementing a standardized feedback process, categorized for clarity and transparency (Interview 11, 2023), allows participants to refine their ideas iteratively. This formalized approach ensures a consistent and clear framework for idea generation (Interview 4, 2023). However, it is recognized that this method might lead to oversimplification (Interview 10, 2023) or rejection of ideas that do not align with the organization's current capabilities (Interview 1, 2023), posing potential limitations to the breadth and innovation of the ideas generated.

In some instances, providers within statutory advocacy adopted a more relaxed, informal approach to feedback on creative ideas (Interview 1, 2023, Interview 3, 2023, Interview 12, 2023). This approach stemmed from the understanding that a stringent, formal process might inadvertently suppress creative expression and intimidate staff from offering ideas (Interview 1, 2023). Proposing new ideas can be a challenging and vulnerable experience; thus, a less formalized feedback system was seen as more encouraging and supportive.

Staff members usually invest a significant amount of time and thought into developing their ideas (Interview 1, 2023), making sure these ideas aptly address relevant problems from the start (Interview 3, 2023). This relates back to the concept that idea generation contains an element of metacognitive reasoning through the process, implicitly building in the skills and knowledge of the practitioner (Puente-Díaz et al., 2021). Therefore, the main objective of informal feedback in this context is to confirm that the broader impacts on the organisation are well-understood, which is a critical step before an idea can receive approval (Interview 1, 2023). The aim was for leaders to 'get out of the way' (Interview 3, 2023) of ideas being created by the organisation.

This informal method of feedback was found to be particularly effective in smaller organisations (Interview 3, 2023, Interview 14, 2024) that in such settings, rigid structures might be more hindering to the cultivation of a creative environment (Steele et al., 2018). Removing the barriers that formal feedback processes might present helped to create an atmosphere more open to spontaneous idea generation and sharing (Interview 1, 2023, Interview 13, 2024, Interview 14, 2024). This environment not only encourages staff to freely

express their ideas but also fosters a dynamic and agile approach to problem-solving (Interview 1, 2023).

For both feedback approaches, it was felt that having this step can significantly enhance the flow of creative ideas within an organisation (Interview 3, 2023, Interview 4, 2023). It establishes a more accessible and less intimidating space for the generation and exchange of ideas (Interview 1, 2023), encouraging staff to engage more actively in the creative process (Interview 3, 2023).

For the providers this feedback loop can be viewed as a crucial step for managing organisational risk (Cucuzzella, 2016). Providing this feedback at the idea's inception identifies potential legal, ethical, or practical issues (Sperandio et al., 2009), essential in a field where compliance with strict legal and ethical standards is paramount. This early identification ensures that innovative ideas are not just creative, but also align with advocacy sector regulations, organisational capabilities (Interview 3, 2023, Interview 10, 2023) therefore balancing inventiveness with compliance.

Feedback also ensures alignment of ideas with an organisation's strategic goals and legal context. Quick identification of misaligned ideas saves resources and keeps the innovation process on track (Interview 1, 2023), especially vital in statutory advocacy where the impact of solutions is significant. However, early feedback can lead to misunderstandings if ideas are still underdeveloped (Amabile, 1998). Feedback at this early stage might miss the idea's potential or intended direction (Cucuzzella, 2016), leading to potentially unhelpful critiques.

Moreover, while feedback guides the development of creativity, it can inadvertently hinder the iterative nature of idea generation (Amabile, 1998). Premature, overly critical feedback might stifle the evolutionary process essential for innovation, leading to the early discarding or alteration of ideas (Toubia, 2006). Therefore, balancing early critiques with the understanding that some ideas require time and exploration to mature is crucial for effective innovation.

By implementing a structured process for idea evaluation, coupled with constructive feedback and public recognition, organisations can create an environment that encourages continuous innovation (Amabile, 1996). This environment is particularly beneficial in the field of statutory advocacy, where creative and novel approaches are often required to address the unique challenges faced. It creates an organisational support system that enables creativity to

be nurtured, ensures that these ideas are carefully considered, thereby contributing to the organization's ongoing growth and adaptability in a constantly changing landscape.

The transition from creativity to actionable innovation necessitates some level of structured approach to executing ideas (Sperandio et al., 2009). Without any systematic method, creative efforts risk being unutilized and essentially wasted (Wooten and Ulrich, 2017). How SA provider land ideas vary, but all were clear that they had a mechanism to do so.

The results from the research demonstrate there are some shared best practices amongst the case studies from SA providers. Flexible structures to create space for ideation outputs, allocating resources to support landing ideas and offering mechanism that deliver continual feedback, feature across the providers. Therefore these have been incorporated into the model, to allow organisations to identify some key practices that can support idea landing.

Figure 14 Organisational Practices to Support Idea Landing

The efficacy of this stage can be seen through some of the organisational innovation shared as part of this research. Exploring some of the creativity, which became ideas and then launched into innovation, can highlight the value of these two key elements of SIM.

5.5 Innovation Launched

After converting their creative concepts into concrete ideas, each of the interviewed organisations had developed unique approaches to innovation. These strategies were rooted in three key themes, each critically contributing to the organisations' developmental progress. These thematic underpinnings not only guided their innovative practices but also significantly influenced their overall growth and evolution, highlighting the diverse ways in which creativity can be harnessed and channelled into practical and effective organisational advancements.

One of the key challenges around creativity and innovation is the allocation of organisational resources, with the risk of failure in innovation potentially meaning that this could be viewed as wasted resources. The interviewees were very clear about how their organisations invested these resources with two very clear pathways.

5.5.1 Innovation Resource

Allocating resources effectively plays a critical role in fostering a culture of innovation and progress within organisations, as highlighted by Klingebiel and Rammer (2014). The research involving various providers underscores that innovation is not just a component, but a cornerstone of organisational strategy (Interview 1, 2023). In fact, several providers indicated that the survival of their organisation hinged on successful innovation (Interview 3, 2023, Interview 10, 2023, Interview 12, 2023). This underscores the consensus among most providers that resource allocation towards innovation is not optional, but essential.

To ensure the success of innovation initiatives, adequate resourcing is key. This not only includes providing necessary funding but also the allocation of time and personnel dedicated to innovation projects (Duran et al., 2016). Such strategic distribution of resources extends beyond the initial phase of idea generation. It provides the innovation efforts with the essential tools and support needed to transition from conceptual ideas to successful, tangible outcomes (Uhlener et al., 2013). This methodology is instrumental in creating an environment conducive to the development and success of innovative ideas, ensuring that these initiatives have the optimal conditions to flourish.

The allocation of resources towards innovative projects in statutory advocacy was exemplified by one organisation that developed triage clinics for potential service users (Interview 5, 2023). Recognising that delays in providing advocacy support for simple

matters could escalate issues, making them more complex and time-consuming, the organisation implemented early intervention strategies. Not only did this approach meet the goal of promptly supporting users, but it also helped in reducing resource expenditure in the long run. The organisation tasked its team with devising a solution, allocating funds and time to develop a pilot project. This initiative resulted in the creation of an Advocacy Clinic – a mobile, drop-in service for those needing initial support (Interview 5, 2023).

Another provider saw an opportunity in increasing service awareness among other stakeholders, like nurses and medical professionals (Interview 10, 2023). They identified that certain groups, especially hospitalised individuals, were unaware of their legal rights to their services. The innovative solution involved distributing boxes of chocolates to nurses' stations, wrapped in the provider's branding, and accompanied by informational cards about their services. This idea sparked internal debate regarding resource allocation, but recognising the importance of innovation, the CEO approved the initiative. This approach aimed not just at raising awareness but also at fostering relationships with key stakeholders in the medical community.

Another instance of resource allocation for innovation in statutory advocacy is demonstrated using 'shelf bids', as practiced by a certain provider (Interview 1, 2023). This organisation set aside a day each quarter for its senior leadership team and other staff members to brainstorm potential bid ideas related to their services. These sessions resulted in the creation of brief bid proposals, which were then kept 'on the shelf' for future use. This strategy enabled the organisation to respond proactively when funding calls were announced by local authorities or other entities. The organisation had identified that frequently, towards the end of the financial year, there are available funding opportunities requiring swift applications. By having a repository of ready-to-use bid proposals, the provider positioned itself advantageously to tap into funding sources that required quick action. This innovative approach not only ensured a state of readiness but also enhanced their capability to secure funds that might otherwise be missed.

The examples underscore how the interviewed providers have placed a high value on innovation, allocating resources accordingly to support their innovative workstreams, aligning with the perspectives of Schlegelmilch et al. (2003). This approach is in line with the principles set out by Kim and Mauborgne (1999), who advocate for leveraging internal assets as a key driver of successful innovation, a strategy evidently embraced by statutory advocacy

providers. Given the constraints related to funding, time, and workload that these organisations often face, the deliberate choice to allocate resources to innovation speaks volumes. It highlights a clear recognition among the interviewees of the importance and value of innovation within their operational and strategic frameworks, which demonstrates the value of creative unlocking and landing ideas for the organisations.

In addition to dedicating resources to kickstart innovation, numerous providers recognised the significant impact of personal staff development on driving organisational change. This belief led to the establishment of comprehensive training and development opportunities accessible to all staff members. By investing in the growth and enhancement of their employees' skills and knowledge, these organisations are not just improving individual capabilities but also fostering a more dynamic, innovative, and adaptable workforce. This approach reflects an understanding that the development of staff is integral to the overall evolution and progress of the organisation, contributing to a culture where continual learning and improvement are key drivers of change and innovation.

5.5.2 Training and Development

Creating a culture of learning through training and other development opportunities allows statutory advocacy organisations to be more innovative in the future (Interview 1, 2023, Interview 3, 2023, Interview 8, 2023, Interview 10, 2023, Interview 12, 2023).

Bauernschuster et al. (2009) identifies a strong association between training and organisational innovation, an approach that is reflected in the statutory advocacy providers in the research. Resources spent on training were seen as a good investment that not only supported current operations but also allowed for organisational development which could support innovation.

The staff all had mandatory training relevant to their roles, but creating opportunities beyond this 'encouraged an openness of mind' (Interview 1, 2023), allowed them to 'speak to people beyond these four walls' (Interview 3, 2023) and 'could steal ideas from elsewhere' (Interview 12, 2023). This can be identified as a form of open innovation, creating knowledge flows across the organisational boundaries (Chesbrough, 2006)

Embracing a positive attitude towards training and development yielded numerous opportunities for innovation among providers. Exposure to diverse perspectives and approaches during these sessions significantly broadened the horizons of staff

members(Interview 10, 2023), thereby enhancing the human investment resource assets of the organisations (Schlegelmilch et al., 2003, Acemoglu, 1997).

The additional benefit was that staff equipped with the latest knowledge and skills were more readily identify emerging opportunities, adapt to new tools, and implement new approaches (Schlegelmilch et al., 2003). They could escape their current models and limitations, opening opportunities elsewhere (von Oetinger, 2004). Multiple organisations felt that this not only allowed the providers to respond effectively to change but also to lead in innovation, by being competitive and responding to user's needs (Interview 6, 2023, Interview 5, 2023, Interview 13, 2024).

One innovative approach by an organisation involved the development of a bespoke qualification, validated by a university (Interview 7, 2023). The primary goal of this initiative was to upskill their workforce and garner external recognition for their staff. Interestingly, while the primary aim was not directly linked to fostering innovation, an unexpected but valuable outcome emerged. As staff attended university sessions, they were exposed to a diverse array of ideas and perspectives through cross pollination discussions (Crockett, 2003).

This exposure led to the launch of at least five distinct innovations within the organisation. These ideas, as noted by the provider, 'would definitely not have seen the light of day' (Interview 7, 2023) without the enriching experience provided by the university environment. This underscores how educational partnerships and external learning opportunities can inadvertently serve as catalysts for innovation, broadening the horizons of staff and bringing fresh, transformative ideas into the organisation.

Further advantages of the training and development initiatives included upskilling that led to more proactive problem-solving among staff (Interview 1, 2023), along with enhanced flexibility (Interview 7, 2023). This upskilling meant that employees were better equipped with the tools and knowledge necessary to anticipate and address challenges efficiently and creatively (Interview 1, 2023). Moreover, the increased flexibility of the staff, a byproduct of their diverse training, allowed them to adapt to changing circumstances and requirements more readily (Interview 7, 2023). This adaptability is crucial in today's dynamic work environments, enabling organizations to respond swiftly to new opportunities and challenges, thereby maintaining a competitive edge and fostering a culture of continuous improvement and innovation.

A similar theme of innovation through training and development was observed among a group of providers in Wales (3, 2023). They established a learning network that allowed for the sharing of training and development opportunities across the group. This approach reduced the costs associated with conducting training, as sessions were open to a broader audience, and it provided staff with access to a wider range of development opportunities (Interview 10, 2023). The relationships formed during these training sessions created an environment where innovation became customary (Interview 3, 2023). The courses served as a melting pot for ideas among the statutory providers, fostering a 'safe space' (Interview 10, 2023) where the competitive dynamics often present in inter-organisational interactions were absent. The cross-pollination (Crockett, 2003) of ideas during network training sessions enabled the cultivation and launch of innovative concepts with reduced risk (Interview 3, 2023).

This collaborative atmosphere led to the emergence of new ideas that were subsequently adopted within their organisations. Innovations such as peer support networks, combined marketing initiatives, and the development of cooperative tendering processes were some of the tangible outcomes of this collaboration (Interview 3, 2023).

This approach to training and development was not just a theoretical exercise; it had tangible, identifiable benefits on the innovation process, as clearly noted by the interviewees. These benefits manifested in the form of enhanced creativity, improved problem-solving skills, and a more dynamic approach to innovation, aligning perfectly with the organisational goals and strategies (Interview 1, 2023, Interview 3, 2023, Interview 10, 2023, Interview 11, 2023, Interview 12, 2023, Interview 13, 2024).

These examples highlight how creating shared learning environments can facilitate not just individual development (Schlegelmilch et al., 2003) but also spark organisational innovation, demonstrating the value of collaborative learning and idea-sharing in the statutory advocacy sector.

5.6 Answering the Research Questions

The SIM model built on the answers to the research questions proposed at the beginning of the thesis. The first question asked, "What strategies and practices do providers in the Statutory Advocacy sector use to foster a culture of idea generation within their organisations?". The research found that providers adopt multiple strategies to nurture

creativity and innovation including promoting open communication and valuing every contribution, which helps minimise the fear of failure and encourages the free expression of innovative ideas. Examples of effective strategies included adopting flexible work patterns to accommodate evolving needs, cultivating a dynamic and inclusive organisational culture, and leveraging training and development to enhance creative capabilities.

The second research question asked, "What support systems and mechanisms enhance and sustain idea generation and innovative thinking in statutory advocacy organisations?". The research highlighted that freedom to explore and take risks is essential for fostering creativity and breakthrough ideas. Effective support systems included structured feedback processes and informal approaches that encouraged diverse perspectives. Leadership exemplified innovative thinking and creative problem-solving, which helped create a supportive environment. The research found that while structured processes provide consistency, the flexibility to include diverse viewpoints is equally important in sustaining innovative thinking.

The final research question asked, "How do statutory advocacy providers allocate and manage resources to support idea generation, and what factors influence their decisions in pursuing innovative projects?". The research revealed that resource allocation often involved identifying issues through data analysis and assigning them to key staff members with relevant experience. This ensured that innovative ideas were given the optimal conditions to succeed. The decision to pursue innovative projects was influenced by internal and external factors, including the need to address service gaps, enhance operational efficiency, and respond to political and funding pressures. Leadership support and strategic prioritisation were crucial in managing resources effectively to foster idea generation and sustain innovation within the organisations.

Overall, the research demonstrated that fostering a culture of creativity, supporting innovative thinking, and managing resources effectively are interconnected practices that drive innovation in statutory advocacy organisations.

5.7 Recommendations

In this section, I present recommendations based on the study's findings and identified limitations. These suggestions aim to enhance the effectiveness of statutory advocacy and provide guidance for future research, policy, and practice within the sector, ensuring a more

comprehensive and inclusive approach to addressing the diverse needs and challenges in this field.

5.7.1 Integrating the Shepherd Ideation Model

The first recommendation is to modify the current SI models to incorporate the SIM as part of their approach. This integration is crucial as the research identifies specific practices and cultural elements that significantly enhance the generation of innovative ideas. Traditional SI models often focus on structured processes and stages but may overlook fostering a supportive and creative organisational culture, which the SIM emphasises.

As previously discussed, the SIM fits symbiotically as part of the standard SI models currently suggested for the sector, as proposed in the figure below.

Figure 15 Simplified SI Process with SIM added

Incorporating the SIM within existing SI frameworks will allow organisations to build long-term capacity for innovation, particularly as they navigate ongoing sector challenges. The SIM offers a holistic approach to idea generation by addressing both cultural and practical aspects of innovation. It encourages open communication, values every contribution, and minimises the fear of failure, creating an environment where individuals and teams can think freely and divergently. This cultural shift is essential for generating unique solutions and driving advancements.

Adoption of the SIM offers numerous benefits, particularly in fostering innovation and enhancing creative processes. The SIM promotes a culture that encourages free expression of ideas and open communication, essential for fostering creativity. This shift minimises the fear of failure and encourages innovative thinking. By focusing on Creative Unlocking and Idea Landing, the model provides a structured yet adaptable framework to meet each organisation's unique needs. Moreover, the SIM's emphasis on leadership in promoting and modelling a creative culture ensures that innovation is not just sporadic but a sustained effort. Leaders play a pivotal role in fostering an environment that supports creativity, providing the necessary resources and backing to transition from divergent thinking to convergent, actionable ideas.

The SIM equips organisations with the resilience and adaptability required to thrive in a dynamic landscape. By embedding innovation within the organisational structure, the model ensures continuous and integral innovation capacity for SA providers who are facing a challenging operating environment.

5.7.2 Focus on Building Creative Partnerships

The next recommendation for statutory advocacy organisations is to actively engage in diverse and creative partnerships. This strategy is crucial in a sector where innovation and responsiveness to evolving needs are paramount. By expanding their collaboration network beyond traditional boundaries, organisations can access a wealth of knowledge, resources, and strategies that might otherwise remain untapped. Partnering with organisations in geographically similar areas or different sectors that are not in direct competition offers unique advantages. These collaborations allow for the sharing of best practices, pooling resources for greater impact, and potentially reaching a wider client base.

Such partnerships can foster the cross-pollination of ideas, leading to innovative solutions to common challenges faced in statutory advocacy. For example, collaborating with technology firms could result in the development of new digital tools for client advocacy, while partnerships with academic institutions might provide access to the latest research and methodologies. Additionally, these collaborations can enhance the sector's visibility and influence, enabling more effective advocacy for policy changes or increased funding.

Embracing diverse partnerships demonstrates a commitment to holistic service provision, addressing various facets of client needs that a single organisation might not fully cover. This approach benefits the organisations and their clients and contributes to building a more robust

and interconnected advocacy sector. By adapting to and meeting the complex needs of their beneficiaries, statutory advocacy organisations can ensure they remain resilient and effective in a challenging environment.

Engaging in diverse partnerships also aligns with the broader recommendation of incorporating the Shepherd Ideation Model into existing SI frameworks. These partnerships can facilitate better creative unlocking by exposing organisations to different perspectives and approaches, thereby enhancing their ability to generate and implement innovative ideas. The integration of diverse and creative partnerships supports the creation of a culture that encourages open communication, values every contribution, and minimises the fear of failure, all of which are essential for fostering creativity and sustaining innovation.

5.7.3 Embrace diversity

The third recommendation for statutory advocacy organisations is to broaden stakeholder engagement to include perspectives from users, volunteers, and external experts. This inclusive approach can significantly enhance organisational creativity and improve the landing of ideas within the organisation, directly supporting the SIM

The SIM emphasises two main aspects: Creative Unlocking and Idea Landing. Broadening stakeholder engagement aligns perfectly with these components. Engaging a diverse group of stakeholders provides access to a wide range of experiences and viewpoints. Users of advocacy services can offer direct insights into the effectiveness and impact of these services, highlighting areas for creative improvement. Volunteers and external experts bring different skills and perspectives, potentially leading to innovative solutions that internal staff might not have considered.

This diversity of thought is crucial for Creative Unlocking as it challenges organisational norms and introduces fresh ideas, preventing stagnation and groupthink. Collaborating with people from varied backgrounds combines unique experiences and knowledge, creating fertile ground for innovative ideas to flourish. For instance, insights from users with lived experience could inspire novel approaches to service delivery.

Broad stakeholder engagement facilitates a deeper understanding of the challenges and needs within the advocacy sector. This understanding is essential for developing creative solutions that are effective and resonate with the target audience. Moreover, by integrating a broader range of stakeholder perspectives, statutory advocacy organisations can foster a more creative

environment. This inclusivity drives innovation and ensures that developed solutions are comprehensive, user-centric, and aligned with the evolving needs of the sector.

Linking this approach to the SIM, broad stakeholder engagement helps refine and integrate creative concepts into actionable plans, essential for Idea Landing. By involving diverse perspectives early in the idea generation process, organisations can better align their innovations with practical needs and ensure smoother implementation. This ensures that ideas do not remain abstract but are effectively transformed into impactful, real-world solutions that benefit the organisation and its clients.

5.8 Limitations to research

In this section, I acknowledge the limitations of my research. Despite offering valuable insights into statutory advocacy providers, it is important to recognize the constraints of my approach. These limitations, including geographic focus and participant selection, as well as the exclusion of other key stakeholders, may impact the comprehensiveness and generalizability of my findings.

5.8.1 Size of organisation

This thesis has a notable limitation in that it focuses exclusively on smaller statutory advocacy providers. In England, there are three major statutory advocacy providers who are expanding their operations to other regions, including one that has secured a national contract for services throughout Scotland. Unfortunately, two of these larger providers declined to participate in the study, and the third did not respond to inquiries about the research.

This focus on smaller organisations may lead to a potential oversight of the unique insights and experiences that larger advocacy groups can offer. As a result, the study's findings might not entirely capture the diversity of the statutory advocacy sector. Acknowledging this limitation is important, as it underscores the necessity for future research to include a wider range of advocacy providers. Such inclusivity in future studies would provide a more holistic understanding of the sector's challenges and the various dynamics at play.

5.8.2 Sampling

The research methodology included convenience sampling, a decision that introduces a significant limitation. Out of over 60 organisations contacted, only 14 participated in interviews. Roughly half of these participants were reached through referrals from earlier interviewees, leading to further introductions within their networks.

This method, while potentially increasing participation rates, raises concerns about the research possibly representing a limited demographic or specific networks within the advocacy sector. Therefore, the study's findings might not fully encapsulate the diverse array of perspectives and experiences prevalent in the wider advocacy landscape. This limitation warrants a careful interpretation of the results and underscores the need for future research to employ more varied sampling methods. Such an approach in subsequent studies is essential to gain a more comprehensive and representative understanding of the complexities and variances in the advocacy sector.

5.8.3 National Samples

The research predominantly included interviews with organisations in England, despite aiming to cover experiences across the United Kingdom and Northern Ireland. This geographical concentration potentially biases the study's findings, especially considering the limited inclusion of Northern Ireland, where only one provider participated.

This imbalance in geographical representation means the study may not fully reflect the diversity and distinct characteristics of the advocacy sector across different regions. The findings should thus be interpreted with caution, acknowledging the limitations of generalizing these results to the entire UK and Northern Ireland. Additionally, variations in legislation across the countries could significantly affect the research outcomes. These legal differences might influence operational methods, resource distribution, and the wider framework within which statutory advocacy organisations operate, leading to differing perspectives and practices among providers.

For a more holistic view of the sector, future research should aim for a balanced representation from all regions. Doing so is crucial for capturing the full range of challenges and dynamics in statutory advocacy across the UK and Northern Ireland, offering insights into how regional legislative differences shape the sector.

5.8.4 Providers only

The study's focus on interviewing solely providers present a notable limitation by not incorporating the perspectives of other vital stakeholders, such as users and commissioners of statutory advocacy services. This approach may overlook critical aspects of the advocacy ecosystem, missing out on valuable insights into the experiences and needs of users who navigate these services and the perspectives of commissioners responsible for their funding and oversight.

By concentrating exclusively on providers, the research risks a narrower understanding of the efficacy, impact, and intricacies of advocacy provision. This could lead to conclusions that are potentially skewed or lack comprehensive insight into the full scope of the advocacy landscape. Integrating viewpoints from users and commissioners, perhaps through additional interviews or alternative data gathering techniques, could provide a more rounded understanding. This is particularly pertinent considering the importance of the commissioning process in funding these organisations.

To address these gaps, future studies should include these critical perspectives, broadening the scope to encompass a more complete picture of the statutory advocacy field. Such an inclusive approach would enrich the research, offering a deeper, more nuanced understanding of the various interactions and dynamics within the sector.

In summarizing the limitations of this study, it is important to note the geographical skew towards English providers, the exclusive focus on providers excluding users and commissioners, and the reliance on convenience sampling. These factors potentially limit the depth and breadth of understanding the diverse dynamics within the statutory advocacy sector.

Despite its limitations, this research holds significant value, particularly given the paucity of literature in the statutory advocacy sector. It illuminates the innovative practices and strategies advocacy providers employ to foster creativity and adaptability. The insights into the roles of organisational culture, leadership, and partnerships in driving innovation offer practical implications and fill a critical knowledge gap.

By setting out the limitations, the study also lays groundwork for more expansive future research. Overall, this research contributes to a deeper understanding of statutory advocacy, emphasizing the sector's complexity and the necessity for ongoing evolution and learning in this understudied area.

5.8.5 Access to data

The research for this thesis is limited to those currently providing a SA contract, which excludes the views of service users, commissioners, and potential providers who are not currently successful bidders. This may also exclude non-traditional or more voluntary organisations that may be providing SA in a less formal way. Additionally, there is a dearth of published data in the SA sector, which makes it challenging to assess its impact and advocate for adequate resources and support from commissioners (Mercer, 2019).

A good example is to examine the current knowledge around SA provision in England. The last published central government report into DoLS in Q2 2015/16 shows that over 40,000 applications were made by 123 local authorities (*Mental Capacity Act 2005, Deprivation of Liberty Safeguards (England) Annual Report 2015-16*, 2016), but it does not indicate how many of these applications required SA intervention, thus not reflecting the demand for SA by clients. In 2013, the department of health data showed that 12,381 eligible instructions were received for IMCA service in England (Bonnerjea, 2014), which highlights the numbers a decade ago. However, DoLS is only one part of the dataset needed to provide a clearer picture of the sector, as SA can be provided via IMCA (Mental Capacity Act 2005), IMHA (Mental Health Act 1983), and SCA (Care Act 2014), and each has subsets within them. Clients may receive Statutory Advocacy support (due to having a legal right), Non-Statutory Advocacy support (no legal right but funded by the relevant local authority), or self-advocacy support (capacity building for the client on a volunteer-led basis). Another variable is whether the client fits into a protected group, such as child services or the elderly, which creates further complications. Despite these complexities, there is currently no published dataset in England that provides a definitive answer to the extent to which individuals who are nationally entitled to advocacy services are receiving them.

Due to the limited availability of central government data, another option for researching the sector is to examine providers' reports. As the market is fragmented with numerous contracts, a sample was taken from the end-of-year annual reports published by Providers.

Table 13 End of Year Annual Reports for Statutory Advocacy Providers in England

Provider	Supported (people)	Area Covered	Year of Annual Report
Warwickshire Independent Advocacy Alliance	700	Warwickshire, Solihull, and Coventry	2022 (Alliance, 2023)
Advocacy Focus	5,336	Lancashire and Trafford	2022 (Advocacy Focus, 2022)
Solihull Action through Advocacy	597	Solihull	2022 (Advocacy., 2022)
Advonet Group	2,500	Leeds and Yorkshire	2022 (Advonet, 2022)

Pohwer	148,203	Central & East England, East Midlands, London, Southern England, Southwest England, West Midlands	2022 (POHWER, 2022)
Voiceability	22,585	Cambs, Cheshire, Hamps, Herts, Lancs, Lincs, London, Mancs, Mersey, Northants, Notts, S.Yorks, Shrops, Staffs, Suffolk, Surrey, Tyne & wear, W.Mids, W.Yorks, Warks.	2022 (Voiceability)

It is clear from this snapshot that the six providers supported a significant number of people in 2021/22. However, it is important to note that data collection in this sector can be challenging due to overlapping areas and a lack of centralised data. This process is replicated across the other countries which presents a limitation for this research as it may impact the ability to provide objective facts around the marketplace. However, by taking a qualitative approach, the research can provide valuable context to the idea generation process for providers operating in the SA sector.

The use of multiple qualitative case studies will allow a snapshot of the current approach to be captured but will lack the ability to create a generalised model that can be applied to other sectors or organisations. The nature of qualitative research will mean that the responses including the coding of interviews, will involve a degree of interpretation which can introduce bias into the findings. Steps will be taken to minimise this, using structured and systematic processes, but this won't be able to eliminate bias from the process.

The alternative would be to use a quantitative methodology, which can potentially offer a more objective result. This would be a challenge to use with multiple case studies, as it would miss some of the depth and links between the current ideation approach.

5.8.6 Time

The research is a cross-sectional approach rather than a longitudinal study. As set out in the background, the sector is undergoing change with the launch of LPS and recovery from Covid. By choosing a cross-sectional viewpoint the research may find that some of the recommendations addressed by the incoming legislation. The research will set out the current sector contexts so that the work can be placed in the appropriate time.

5.8.7 Sector Choice

This study focuses on only SA, a small subset of the wider social care sector. In choosing a small but focused study, the research may limit the replicability of the recommendations. The social care sector encompasses a large range of services, so a study that examines a wider remit may offer more practical impactful findings. The findings will consider this limitation and highlight links to other potentially relevant sectors to try and optimise the utility of the recommendations.

There is a paucity of sector wide literature, with a lack of available data even relating to the number of people in receipt of statutory advocacy support. By focusing on SA, this work can help bring its vital work to a new academic audience.

Chapter 6: CONCLUSION

The research aim, as outlined at the beginning, was to conduct “a critical examination of how providers in the Statutory Advocacy sector currently encourage, support, and resource creativity for organisational innovation.” This thesis has illuminated a sector under immense pressure, yet actively developing and delivering innovation through creativity and ideation.

6.1 Research Objectives Answered

The research objectives were

1. Explore how encouragement can help organizations in statutory advocacy to create a culture of creativity and innovation and identify effective methods to encourage innovation and sustain it in these organisations.
2. Identify the types of support that organisations in the statutory advocacy need to be more creative and innovative.
3. Investigate how statutory advocacy providers use their resources to support creativity and find out what factors influence their decisions on innovative projects.

The findings reveal that providers cultivate a highly creative culture, characterised by encouragement and positive feedback loops. This approach was consistently observed across all participating organisations, underscoring the vital role of a creative culture in fostering innovation.

A common theme in the interviews was the provision of ongoing support to transform creative thoughts into practical ideas. Methods ranged from designated “getting it wrong” days to informal brainstorming sessions with cake, demonstrating the strong link between supportive environments and successful innovation outcomes.

Statutory advocacy providers also displayed resourcefulness in maximising the resources allocated to creative development. Simple tools, such as wooden spoons, were often used to stimulate creativity. Ensuring the organisation's agility and responsiveness to user needs was central to resource allocation.

The focus on continuous improvement allowed employees to request resources for experimenting with new concepts, even within tight financial constraints. This resourcefulness led to innovative initiatives, such as raising brand awareness through

chocolate boxes—a cost-effective strategy that might have been overlooked if more funds were available.

This research has identified key elements of idea generation among SA providers, which have been distilled into the Shepherd Ideation Model, focusing on culture and practice for organisations.

6.2 Contribution

This research has added to the literature around creativity as it relates to idea generation and to the Statutory Advocacy sector by examining multiple case studies. The in-depth analysis of organisational experiences around idea generation has allowed for the identification of the similarities and differences in the idea generation approaches.

This study is unique, as the Statutory Advocacy sector has been largely overlooked in academic research, with a notable paucity of literature on creativity within this context. By addressing this gap, it offers a pioneering exploration of idea generation in a sector where such processes have not been systematically studied before.

The findings can serve as a practical guide for statutory advocacy organisations to enhance their creative practices and develop more effective, innovative solutions to challenges. Additionally, it provides a framework for these organisations to reflect on and refine their internal processes for fostering idea generation. Building on the previous models on SI (Murray et al., 2010, Beckman et al., 2020, Logue, 2019) the research has allowed development of the Shepherd Ideation Model.

Figure 16 The Shepherd Ideation Model

The development of a model which focused on the culture and practice surrounding idea generation, adds depth to the current process driven SI approaches. Although the research has focused on the SA sector, the fact that the elements are flexible may lead to the application in other third sector organisations who have similar challenges.

6.3 Implications for future research

This research has revealed several knowledge gaps, highlighting specific areas that warrant further investigation. There are four key areas where future studies could make significant contributions:

6.3.1 Expanding the geographical scope

One critical area for future research lies in broadening the geographical scope of studies. The current research primarily focuses on organisations in England, with limited representation from other regions of the UK, including Northern Ireland, Scotland, and Wales.

Expanding research to these areas is essential to capture the diverse experiences and practices in statutory advocacy across the UK. Different regions may have unique challenges and approaches due to varying legal frameworks, funding structures, and cultural contexts. Research that encompasses these variations will provide a more holistic view of the sector, offering insights into regional best practices, policy impacts, and specific needs of communities in different areas. Such studies would contribute significantly to a balanced and comprehensive understanding of statutory advocacy across the UK.

6.3.2 Diverse Stakeholder Perspectives

Future research should aim to include a wider range of stakeholders beyond advocacy providers. Incorporating the voices of service users, for example, can shed light on the direct impact and effectiveness of advocacy services from the beneficiary's perspective.

Understanding their experiences, needs, and the challenges they face in accessing and benefiting from advocacy services will provide invaluable insights for service improvement.

Additionally, engaging with commissioners and policymakers can offer a broader view of the sector's funding landscape, regulatory challenges, and the implications of policy decisions on service delivery. This holistic approach will ensure that research outcomes reflect the complex interplay of various forces shaping the statutory advocacy sector.

6.3.3 Longitudinal Studies

The advocacy sector is dynamic, with practices and challenges evolving in response to changes in legal frameworks, societal needs, and funding environments. Longitudinal research could provide valuable insights into these changes over time.

Such investigations would allow researchers to track the long-term effectiveness of advocacy strategies, the sustainability of funding models, and the impact of policy shifts. Longitudinal studies could also reveal trends and patterns in service demand, advocacy outcomes, and organisational development within the sector. This approach would offer a deeper understanding of the long-term impacts and effectiveness of statutory advocacy work.

6.3.4 Comparative Studies across sectors

Comparative research can offer critical insights into the statutory advocacy sector. Studies comparing different types of advocacy organisations, such as those focusing on varied advocacy areas like health, education, or social services, can highlight sector-specific challenges and innovative practices.

Additionally, comparing statutory and non-statutory advocacy organisations could reveal differences in approach, effectiveness, and challenges, providing a richer understanding of the advocacy landscape.

Comparative studies could also extend to comparing advocacy practices across different countries, offering a global perspective on best practices and innovative solutions in advocacy work. These four research areas present opportunities to enhance our understanding of the statutory advocacy sector, providing valuable insights that can inform policy, practice, and future research directions. These recommendations and opportunities for further research will allow the SIM to share the learnings from providers of SA.

The findings from the research are planned to be shared with the interviewees organisations as well as relevant trade bodies such as Scottish Independent Advocacy Alliance

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Chapter 8: APPENDICES

8.1 Appendix 1 - Semi Structured interview questions

57Topic	Main Question	Research Question
Background	Can you briefly explain what your organisation does?	Context
Change Drivers	How do you feel statutory advocacy has change for your organisation over the last 3 years?	
Challenges	What do you see as the 3 big challenges in the future for statutory advocacy for your organisation?	
Creativity	How much time do you think that the organisation spends thinking about the future challenges?	<i>Research Question 1 - Explore how encouragement can help organizations in statutory advocacy to create a culture of creativity and innovation and identify effective methods to encourage innovation and sustain it in these organisations.</i>
	Do you think that you encourage people in your organisation to be creative and come up with new ideas?	<i>Research Question 1 - Explore how encouragement can help organizations in statutory advocacy to create a culture of creativity and innovation and identify effective methods to encourage innovation and sustain it in these organisations.</i>
	What do you do when someone comes up with an idea that could develop into a new way or working or new service etc?	<i>Research Question 2 - Identify the types of support that organisations in the statutory advocacy need to be more creative and innovative.</i>
	How much resource do you allocate to developing the future organisations direction?	<i>Research Question 3 - Investigate how statutory advocacy providers use their resources to support</i>
Wishes	If you had a magic wand and could be granted 3 wishes that would improve statutory advocacy – what would they be?	Development of themes

8.2 Appendix 2 – Sample Coding

Quoted Research Interview	Codes
<p>Yeah, it's a very good question. And it's a bit ad hoc. I mean, we have three, what we call three team days a year. So the whole organisation comes together. We, I think we've now had two since COVID in person. Basically, we find an inappropriately small church hall and hire it for the day and try and jam us all in and then we provide mediocre sandwiches. That's basically our modus operandi. So it brings the whole organization together. And then we always do, I do an update. We do a piece of training. It might be around safeguarding. It might be around kind of working with people with mental health issues or working with people with acquired brain injuries we had recently. And then we say to people, then we get people into small groups and say, okay, what's good? What doesn't work? So that kind of feeds in. And there's something about just taking time talking to people. And we should do more of that, about me getting off my backside and going to team meetings rather than rowing with commissioners. There's that mechanism for feeding in. We have Getting It Right Days. We have a couple of years where people who use our services are encouraged to come and tell us what works and what doesn't work. Also, there's a number of staff who—so we also then have a fortnightly management team meeting, and I expect managers to bring stuff from supervision to say, actually, this works, this doesn't work.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Culture: Collaboration • Culture: Open communication • Culture: Supportive environment • Encouragement of Creativity for Innovation: Feedback • Encouragement of Creativity for Innovation: Open discussions • Encouragement of Creativity for Innovation: Team days • Encouragement of Creativity for Innovation: Training • Strategies and Resources for Creativity Support: Getting It Right Days • Strategies and Resources for Creativity Support: Management team meetings • Strategies and Resources for Creativity Support: Team meetings • Training: Enhancing knowledge and skills • Training: Training and development
<p>Yes, fundamentally. I think we have to. I think we should, because again, back to that thing where people just want help. It isn't necessarily I'd need an advocate. Yes, advocacy is critical in people's voice, but there's other ways of doing that and I think advocacy, I always remember at my university lecture, one of my university lecturers who taught us on crime and punishment, remember saying as social workers you're a lot nearer the police than you are the angels and of course we were all terribly shocked by that and he's right and statutory advocacy is the same. We're far closer to the kind of the processes that we really want to be or should be in terms of really making a difference in the fundamental. Yeah, people's right to protect and that's critical, absolutely critical. But again, back to have they had a voice? Is their life better because of our intervention? I'm suspect if we'd look really carefully, not. So we have to diversify financially and for our own position. But also that innovation, there's new ways of doing stuff and we've got to do it because I think that's where the excitement is. And it generates activity, it generates life in the organization, it generates differences for people as well. And, you know, for us, we innovated by taking on this project with people with</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Encouragement of Creativity for Innovation • Embracing innovation • Encouragement of Creativity for Innovation • Financial diversification • Examples of Creative Initiatives and Organizational Innovation • Project with people with mental health issues who are autistic